

EPEMC Tables, Figures, and Graphs

Useful references collected from author's papers including rare figures, collected images from cited works, and animations.

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ABSTRACT¹

Figures, tables, and graphs form the backbone of any scientific paper. They provide convenient eye-catching markers for the reader to be distracted from the text, while conveying a lot of data all at once. In 30 papers thus far written, the author has compiled a long list of images created, altered, augmented, and utilized to convey ideas about Extended Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology (EPEMC). Though not all of the hundreds of figures could be included, in this document are quick references to the top 200 or so, as well as the most important appendices produced thus far.

Keywords: plasma - diffusion - electromagnetism - debunking the standard model and uniformitarianism

Produced² in association with:

$T\Sigma S L \Lambda \beta$ TM

¹ Not included in this collection are a great many figures, and also the tables and figures of [11] , [17], [21] (None to speak of), [27] (literally every figure would need to be included, so please refer directly to that paper), same thing for [28] pp.19-25, 36-50

² Document Best Viewed at <http://bit.ly/2PwFKp5>

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Tables

Table 1 - List of Proposed cataclysms³

Cataclysm	Date	Evidence Known
Tiamat incursion Sinking of Atlantis	14000 or 12600 YBP	Younger Dryas event, Carolina Bays (final series), Solon's report to Plato, Gobekli Tepe "enclosure C," Enuma Elish
The Deluge - mountains?	10000 YBP	End of Tepe mound event, Nevali Cori
"Divine wind"	7000 YBP	Rig Veda?
Great Flood (Storm)	5600 YBP	The Atrahasis and Gilgamesh
Great Comet Venus/Exodus	3600 YBP	Multiple lines, mound-builders/Adena, Egypt, Mexico, Peru, India, Norse, Greek Myths, China, etc...
Mars/Dark Age of Greece	2680 YBP	Biblical era texts and calendar evidence

Table 2 - Epochs of Man (Roughly speaking)⁴

240 kya - 40/36 kya Antiquarian Period	Biologically modern man	Pure animism is expected
36 kya - 12kya Atlantean Period	"Dream Time" aka "Zep Tepi" Origins of language and art Worship of the "Titans" End of Purple Dawn = end of Double Layer plasmasphere around Saturn	Shamanism, cave paintings, crude pyramids slowly refined into Atlantean-esque cultures, especially in Giza area growing in technological prowess; sense of impending Doom
12 kya - 9 kya Tepe Period	Younger Dryas event (Moon or comet) Origins of religious fear of the gods; destructions of Atlantis, Lemuria, Sundaland, Doggerland, etc... Dwarka sunk -> Vedas	Polytheism begins in the form of worshiping planets and animal-gods (Tepe movement); astronomical data kept, buried, first distinct astronomical worship cult
9 kya - 5 kya Archaic Period	Age of Destructions and "Clash of the Titans" (Aesir vs Vanir, the triumph of Asgard); origins unknown, possibly the Moon again, possibly early Venus; Terminates suddenly and	Cave societies, dolmens, more shamanism, use of entheogenic plants, oracles, sky-reading, sorcery and invoking of spirits for protection and prediction of catastrophe

³ [1] p.5

⁴ [2] pp. 2-4

	agriculture resumes in full in Sumer and Egypt, India and China	
3500 BCE - 600 BCE Megalithic Period	Dynastic Age - the origins of Nobility and the Priest-Royal dichotomy "War of the gods" End of Saturnian and Jovian age worship, planets begin to diverge; 2 more cataclysms afflict the world Roots of civilization take hold worldwide	Egypt and India create transcendentalism; Death cults, Polytheism, Emergence of comet fear and expectation of war. Origins of technocracy and obsessions of prediction mechanisms Origins of both wisdom traditions AND messiah phenomena (savior planets)
600 BCE - 100 CE Transition or Hellenistic Period	Age of War and End of Paganism	Messiah cults spring up worldwide, driving man towards imperialism and unification of efforts and resources; religions politicize and organize officially Origins of energy schools, wizardry, and chemistry. Use of technocracy now devoted mostly to warfare and in pockets megalithic architecture devoted to gods of the past. This extends Paganism and Animism in the Americas and Asia and Africa by allowing for cathartic remembrance. But it stokes religious strife. Origins of math and math worship
100 CE - 1900s CE Religious Period	Age of Pisces, and of Productivity and Exploration Aftershock comets and eruptions fortify belief systems in pockets of the world Age of Information roots laid down in the origins of Science as research into causative mechanisms for destruction sought.	Separation of natural self and civilized self; religious fervor intensifies in the form of political, social, and technological (even educational) restructuring. Aftershocks generate unusual war and death cults in the Nordic regions, the Americas (especially mesoAmerica), and former Sundaland. There's a movement over time away from ego-centric explanations of the supernatural into mechanistic and principle-driven explanations. Mankind adjusts religiosity and dogma but continues to seek power of the gods. Discontinuing over time the belief in wisdom traditions' predictive powers.

<p>1700s CE - Present Scientific Period</p>	<p>Modern Age Age of Information and Science End of feudalistic approach to imperialism Age of Money and Finance (intangible tangibles)</p>	<p>Decreasing reliance on superstition alone, origins of modern energy schools and increasing reliance on empirical evidence to form dogma. Decrease in the power of theism in general; where unable to reduce fervor or adjust it with modern knowledge, continued Age of Warfare. Continued modernized versions of Imperialism and Technocracy comes into full; weapons of the gods begin to be understood and sometimes used upon other humans. Continued, even accelerated obsession with space (the Heavens), and with finding out “who are we” and “where do we come from” Shamanism morphs into alien obsessions. Animism laid to rest or melded with paganism, which falls further behind as most non Monotheistic energy/resource efforts are invested into Scientism. Scientific method begins to degrade as it evolves a blend of dogma with accelerated mathematical worship.</p>
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Table 3 - Cross comparison of the gods⁵ & titans with astronomy⁶

Planet/oids, Moons & Stars	Sumerian ⁷	Greco-Roman (T/G)	Egyptian ⁸ (OG/NG)	Indian	Chinese	Norse ⁹ (A/V)
Sun (Sol)	Apsu ¹⁰	Apollo	Harpocrates	Surya ¹¹	Yang 陽	Surtur
Moon (Luna) ¹²	Anu Kingu Nanna ¹³	Janus Pandora ¹⁴ Aphrodite Artemis / Diana ¹⁵	Khonsu Hathor ¹⁶	Chhaya ¹⁷ Sanjna Tara	Yin 陰 Chang-e 嫦娥 ¹⁸	Vali Nana?
Deceased moon	Sin ¹⁹	Prometheus	Tefnet / Maat	Soma		Balder
Sky	Anu	Uranus / Caelus	Shu/Tefnut	Vishnu?	Tian 天	Freya
Earth	Tiamat / Ki	Gaia / Hera? ²⁰	Geb	Prithvi	Nüwa 媧皇	Frigg
Jupiter	Enlil [Marduk]	Zeus Jupiter	Set	Indra Shiva	Fuxi Pangu 盤古	Odin/ Wodan Thor

⁵ See <https://goo.gl/sQZ3ng> for full table

⁶ [2] pp. 6-8

⁷ Sumerian includes all traditions coming down, such as Akkadian, Semites, etc...

⁸ <http://rickriordan.com/extra/meet-the-egyptian-gods/>

⁹ <http://www.crystalinks.com/norsegods.html>

¹⁰ http://www.bulgari-istoria-2010.com/Rechnici/Sumerian_Dictionary.pdf

¹¹ "When Surya married Sanjna, his wife could not bear the intense light and heat. Therefore, she fled into a forest where she transformed herself into a mare to prevent Surya from recognizing her. But Surya soon discovered Sanjna's refuge. He went to the same forest disguised as a horse. Sanjna gave birth to several children, and eventually reunited with her husband.

However, the heat and the light of Surya were so intolerable that Sanjna was always exhausted doing her domestic duties. Finally, Sanjna's father decided to help her and trimmed Surya's body reducing his brightness by an eighth. Thus, Sanjna could more easily live close to her husband." From this we can gather that when the Earth moved closer to the sun, it became too hot, even for our moon. But after some electrical stabilization, we moved into a tolerable orbit 1/8 further away, therefore changing the AU to its present distance. https://www.windows2universe.org/mythology/surya_sun.html

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_lunar_deities

¹³ <http://history-world.org/sumerianwords2.htm>

¹⁴ "Hephaestus also created the first woman, Pandora, at the command of Zeus, in retaliation for the various tricks by which the Titan Prometheus had benefited mortal men at the expense of the gods. Pandora was given to the Titan's brother, Epimetheus, as his wife. For her dowry she brought a jar filled with evils from which she removed the lid, thereby afflicting men for the first time with hard work and sickness. Only hope remained inside the jar." From this account of myth it becomes clear that the moon was once part of the Jovian system, as is predicted by its composition and appearance, and was thrown off by Triton/Hephaestus, which was later banished from Mount Olympus (when it became Neptune's servant). This corresponds to the end of Zep Tepi, or the arrival of the moon, when men were lost to Eden/Edin and thereafter to slave under agriculture (Tepe Period forward). <http://www.mythweb.com/gods/hephaestus.html>

¹⁵ "Diana believed her body was very sacred, and so no man was to see her naked. One day a wandering hunter came across Diana bathing. She became very angry, and turned him into a stag" ; the stag is associated with Loki and Loki's horns. This could mean the Awen conjunction and the moon changing Venus' appearance, or it could mean that the myth was re-visioned as Loki is well known to turn from male to female. https://www.windows2universe.org/mythology/Diana_def.html

¹⁶ The Coffin Texts; Hathor is later in the New Kingdom associated with Venus (Sekhmet), thus the repetition of destruction as associated with a first female fertility goddess, and then destructive warrior princess (true yin vs. false yin).

¹⁷ Literally "shade."

¹⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chang%27e> Heng-i or Chang-e, floated up to Heaven after Hou Yi shot down the 9 stars

¹⁹ Destruction of the first moon by God appears to be the origin of the fear of "living in sin"

²⁰ Hera's depiction as Mother evolved, from first being the primeval sun (Saturn), which was replaced as male, to that of Earth, which had thereafter a tenuous relationship with Zeus. It is unclear if Hera is Earth itself, or the life-force. She has cross-depictions with Venus in the Jason/fleece myth, associated with the beard and electromagnetic display/auroras.

Saturn	Ea / Shamash Kaimanu	Cronus	Ra / Re Osiris	Brahma Sani	Shangdi 上帝	Bor / Hymir
Mars	Nurgal/Utu/Marduk	Ares / Mars	Horus	Vishnu Rama	Houyi 后羿 ²¹	Tyr ²² Thor
Venus / Mother Warrior Goddess	Inanna Ishtar	Aphrodite Athena ²³ Minerva ²⁴	Isis Sekhmet ²⁵ Or Set	Lakshmi	Nüwa 媧皇? ²⁶	Loki ²⁷ Hel(a)
Titan		Demeter?	Nephthys?			Sif? ²⁸
Asteroid Belt	"Hammered Bracelet"	Argus				Heimdall? ²⁹
Deceased planet	Ninhursag?	Metis	Osiris	Krishna		Hod
Mercury	Gudud	Hermes	Thoth	Rama?	Shuixing 水星	Heimdall/Tyr
Milky Way	Babil Nebo	Rhea	Nu'ut	Dharma	Dao 道	Yggdrasil
Uranus		Pluto / Hades	Anubis			Muspelheim
Ariel ³⁰		Persephone				

²¹ "Chinese people believed that there existed ten suns that appeared in turn in the sky during the Chinese ten-day week. Each day the ten suns would travel with their mother, the goddess Xi He, to the Valley of the Light in the East. There, Xi He would wash her children in the lake and put them in the branches of an enormous mulberry tree called fu-sang. From the tree, only one sun would move off into the sky for a journey of one day, to reach the mount Yen-Tzu in the Far West.

Tired of this routine, the ten suns decided to appear all together. The combined heat made the [life](#) on the Earth unbearable. To prevent the destruction of the [Earth](#), the emperor Yao asked Di Jun, the father of the ten suns, to persuade his children to appear one at a time. They would not listen to him, so Di Jun sent the archer, Yi, armed with a magic bow and ten arrows to frighten the disobedient suns. However, Yi shot nine suns, only the [Sun](#) that we see today remained in the sky. Di Jun was so angry for the death of nine of his children that he condemned Yi to live as an ordinary mortal in the earth."

From this we can see that the Chinese remember a time when there were 10 *highly* visible bodies in the sky during the reign of emperor Yao (Yahweh, Ywahoo - the world sound heard from crustal bending), pre Shang Dynasty, or Sumerian times. **1) Sun, 2) Moon, 3) Mercury, 4) Mars, 5) Jupiter, 6) Venus, 7) Saturn, 8) Callisto, 9) Io, and 10) Ganymede.** It is doubtful Europa would have been considered large enough. However, any one of the bodies could be switched. Please note that by this time, Uranus and Neptune (and Triton) would certainly be too far away, as would any Saturnian moon.

https://www.windows2universe.org/mythology/ten_chinese_suns.html

²² Tyr's "hand" was bitten off by Fenrir; he will get his revenge against Garm (giant dog) at the next Ragnarok. Is this an astronomical prediction?

²³ Athena's associated animal is the owl, due to Peratte formation, see Appendix B

²⁴ "Following the Greek myths around Athena, she was born of Metis, who had been swallowed by Jupiter, and burst from her father's head, fully armed and clad in armor.^[2] After impregnating the titaness Metis notably forcefully which resulted in her attempting to change shape or shapeshift to escape him, Jupiter recalled the prophecy that his own child would overthrow him as he had Saturn and in turn, Saturn had Caelus." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Caelus>

²⁵ "A New Kingdom religious composition records rebellion against Ra, prompting him to withdraw to the sky. This 'Tale of the Heavenly Cow' includes the story of Ra sending his eye out from his body, so as a separate offshoot, a 'daughter', to punish mankind. As Sekhmet (meaning 'the mighty goddess') she almost annihilates mankind; the gods trick her into becoming sweetly drunk, by colouring a lake of beer red to look like human blood - she reverts to her sweet character as the loving and maternal Hathor."

<http://www.ucl.ac.uk/museums-static/digitalegypt/religion/deitiescreation.html>

²⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/N%C3%BCwa>

²⁷ Loki is the "father" of three monsters: Fenrir, Hela, and Jormungand; a mother to Sleipnir, the 8 legged horse.

²⁸ The little known fertility goddess could have remembered from the age of Saturnian orbit in the Tepe period.

²⁹ Argus having "100 eyes" and Heimdall's power of sight could be any of the highly cratered bodies, including Ganymede, Mercury, or Mars.

³⁰ Assumption that only the brightest moon would be visible at all to ancient Greeks and Romans.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Moons_of_Uranus#Large_moons

Great Comet		Nemesis/Venus	Apep	Lakshmi		
Comet tail / Snake		Typhon		Naga	Hundun 混沌	Jormungand
Neptune	Enki	Poseidon Theseus? ³¹				Ymir (Nep?)
Thunderbolt (EMF)		Pluvius <i>Habeant</i> ³²	Bast ³³	Trishula Damaru ³⁴	Leidian 雷电	Mjollnir
Dipper/ Great Bear		Callisto		Saptarshi ³⁵	Pih Tow ³⁶ Doumu 斗母	
Thunderbirds			Horus	Garuda		
Savior Mars	Gilgamesh	Hercules	Babi	Hanuman	Sun Wukong	Thor
Traitor Mars		Mars Ultor ³⁷	Set	Kali		
Io		Io ³⁸				Sif?
Callisto		Callisto ³⁹				

³¹ Poseidon's changeable character is likely due to the blue planet's wandering nature. The continued worship of the seas, despite becoming further from Neptune (and Saturn), was continued through his progeny. The myths, over time, became vastly more centered around humanity's efforts to survive. Neptune was often invoked as a friend to humanity as well. The "steed" aspect is also referenced in India and Norse, and probably related to a zodiac or plasma shape which changed shape often. This shape may still exist in dark mode, even if the voltage is too small to brighten it nowadays. These shapes may yet return, and be associated with the zodiacs (housing) if, upon leaving the galactic dust blocking our circuit, the [Milky Way's plasma streams reach our outer solar system](#) and [recharge the outer gas giants](#).

³² Pliny, <https://www.varchive.org/itb/thunder.htm>

³³ Perhaps one of the greatest mysteries of ancient Egyptian religion was the worship of cats. However, research shows that Bast was "like a knife" and his symbol was that of the knife, still a ritualistic ornament in worldwide magical practices. The knife is best symbolized in the Tibetan [Vajrakila or Phurba](#); itself a probable derivative of Kali, goddess of destruction. Bast is therefore associated with electromagnetism. Given the widespread use of the most ancient/Atlantean Period Egyptian "gods" of this mysterious power, the cat therefore symbolised that mysterious power. Their mercurial natures and occasional heterochromia (two different colored eyes) only heightened that mystery and possibly alluded to duality

³⁴ "the damru is known as the instrument of the deity Shiva, and is said to be created by Shiva to produce spiritual sounds by which the whole universe has been created and regulated." The double bell shape is that noted by David LePoint and is electromagnetic.

³⁵ <http://www.seasky.org/constellations/constellation-ursa-major.html>

³⁶ <https://heathenchinese.wordpress.com/2013/09/08/the-big-dipper/> <http://idp.bl.uk/4DCGI/education/astronomy/sky.html>

³⁷ "Mars Ultor, was among the gods who received sacrifices from Julian, the only emperor to reject Christianity after the conversion of Constantine I. In 363 AD, in preparation for the Siege of Ctesiphon, Julian sacrificed **ten "very fine" bulls** to Mars Ultor."

³⁸ "To free Io, Zeus sent his son Mercury to sing and tell boring stories to make Argus sleep with all his eyes. [Mercury](#) told so many stories that finally Argus closed all his hundred eyes. Only then did Mercury kill Argus and untie Io who ran home free. Yet when Hera discovered what had occurred, she was so furious that she sent a vicious gadfly to sting the cow forever. Meanwhile, Io who was still prisoner into the shape of a cow could not get rid of the malicious gadfly. Finally, after Zeus vowed to no longer pursue his beloved Io, Hera released Io from her inhuman prison, and Io settled in Egypt, becoming the first queen of Egypt." <https://www.windows2universe.org/mythology/planets/Jupiter/Io.html>

This cow is of course related to the cow cult of the Near East. However the "stings" clearly relate to Io's electrical nature.

³⁹ As a "favorite companion" of Diana, this would suggest that Venus was, for a time, in tidal lock with a Jovian moon.

Table 4 - Analyzing Absurdities⁴⁰

Assertion	Details	Evidence Offered
Saturn and Jupiter ⁴¹ as Brown Dwarf Parent	The Liquid Metallic Hydrogen model expects non-hydrogen lattice exclusion and induced exfoliation; the Electric Sun/stellar model and plasma cosmology also provides a mechanism for individualization via double layering and plasma sheaths Precedence of tiny dwarf stars has recently been found, however the main issue is that energy is mass, and so most of the mass Saturn and Jupiter had previously is not there, due to drop in charge syphoned off to Sol/Apollo	SAFIRE Paper 1 Dr. Pierre-Marie Robitaille Ralph Juergens Donald Scott (book) (video) (paper) Wal Thornhill (video) (book) (Thunderbolts) Kristian Birkeland (Currents and Nebulae) Marklund Convection (paper) 1956 Terrella Experiments (paper) Nebulae (double layers) (z-pinch) (motors) Galaxies (coplanar rotation) ⁴² (CDM Free) Galaxies "On a String" (Magellanic Cloud) Direct Current Measurement Halton Arp "Intrinsic Redshift" (last talk)
Formation not by Accretion	The accretion has never worked in either simulation or observation. ⁴³ In contrast, many exoplanets have been found by searching near to dwarf stars ⁴⁴ or main sequence stars, and not farther away where dust could theoretically accrete via [weak] gravity over billions of years. Rather, instead the multiple composition of our own solar system suggests a heterogeneous system. The sheer volume of satellites surrounding Jupiter and saturn argue against accretion and for exfoliation. That they have similar magnitudes of them, and even some with water, but all quite diverse, and many with observed electrical relationships, such as Io and Enceladus bolster not only the Electric Star hypothesis but exfoliation as planetoid genesis.	TRAPPIST-1 LMH Model of exfoliation Saturn's Rings made of water (tidal lock) Similarities of Earth with Titan and Europa Similarities of Venus and Mars showing scars of massive discharge and "oversized volcanoes" Venus' superhot, hydrocarbon atmosphere Venus (and Uranus) backwards rotation Venus' rotation slowing down Venus' comet tail Uranus' tilt and this (Sumerian Myth) Retrograde orbits Pluto's eccentric orbit The Asteroid Belt and Boli (Enuma Elish) Lack of evidence of "dirty snowballs" and an "Oort Cloud" Presence of strong solar "wind" ⁴⁵ Quasar Exfoliation (Arp theory) Failure of Dark Matter hypothesis Star dust disks reveal LePoint formations rather than accretion disks. (SPHERE)
Moon late arrival	The two faces of the moon reflect vastly different histories from the standard model. Based upon Accretion, the moon	Eclipse Patterns Moon face machining (matches Mars machining)

⁴⁰ [2] pp. 23-27

⁴¹ It is well known for many decades that Jupiter is still, to this day, putting out more heat than it receives, defying standard gas giant models all by itself.

⁴² https://youtu.be/KUqV_2sj92U and <http://science.sciencemag.org/content/359/6375/534.full>

⁴³ <https://www.space.com/2206-death-spiral-theorists-cant-solar-systems.html> Accretion in any working manner requires electromagnetism: <https://goo.gl/wSmxEV> and <https://goo.gl/b4s2bD>

⁴⁴ <https://astrobiology.nasa.gov/news/red-dwarf-stars-and-the-planets-around-them-2/>

⁴⁵ The Solar charged "wind" is of course not a wind at all, but accelerated (up to 50% the speed of light) elements and particles. On one recorded occasion the sun's transistor-like behavior was displayed when the [SW turned off for two days](#).

	<p>should be uniformly impacted, like Mercury, however it has a massively arc machined “front” face, which always faces Earth. The rotation of the satellite precisely (no coincidence) matches that of the Earth, which cannot and would never happen in the Big Whack, due to angular momentum conservation. The chances of this precision are astronomically low by such a method. Over billions of years such a momentum issue would definitely worsen.</p> <p>Moreover the orbit of the Moon is not planar, nor is it even elliptical.</p>	<p>Hi-res imagery shows close knit arc craters Oblique craters are relatively few while crater chains are common Changing direction crater chains are also common; even defying topography Moonquakes follow a non-standard behavior that is suggestive of hollowness. Angular momentum laws themselves should be consulted for issues of revolution. They are never dealt with over any period of time in discussion of the Big Whack but completely ignored. Myths from certain tribes and cultures specifically mention the Moon as causing destruction worldwide, including the original Tiamat Myth in the Enuma Elish</p>
The Purple Dawn	<p>The sky was reported to be an indigo-purplish color. Meanwhile the current sky is blue due to the frequencies put out by the sun.</p> <p>This is contrary to the natural evolution of plants which should absorb green, if Sol was the original sun.</p>	<p>Qing (blue-green) is a common color phenomenon all over the world. Plants prefer red or blue light, even still it is used in hatcheries. The solar spectrum clearly shows an inordinate volume of green light in the visible spectrum, as opposed to red.</p>
The “Beginning” of Time	<p>Multiple cultures around the world report a “Beginning of the World” that occurred within human memory. It is referred to usually lasting only days. It is usually referred to happening after formation from chaos or the creation of light. This is directly contrary to geological evidence.</p>	<p>Zep Tepi and Egyptian records 36 kya “Dream Time” and Aboriginal Creation Myths Water clocks and off-angle but precise sundials (Worlds In Collision) Sudden emergence of clocks Calendrical problems not arising from bad mathematics.⁴⁶</p>
Change of tilt and/or orbital frequency	<p>Earth and Mars’ tilt axis preclude any possibility of accretion. The phase lock of Earth and Mars⁴⁷ to each other, as well as the orbital angles relative to the sun indicate a previous orbital ellipse path around the sun. Meanwhile myth, archaeology, oral traditions, and biological evidence all suggest major changes to Earth’s tilt and orbit.</p>	<p>Mammoth stomachs full of species too far north. Biblical and Chinese myths agree the planet’s North used to be its South⁴⁸ The Piri Reis map shows a clear outline of Atlantis AND its rivers Astronomical correlations</p>

⁴⁶ It is remarkable that the scientific community feels mound builders, Egyptians, and Mayans (particularly Mayans) are so capable of creating incredibly precise calendar and even mechanisms, such as the antikythera mechanism, and yet are suddenly lax or imprecise with the most important values calculated for farming (and survival): equinoxes. Even the orders of the seasons are reported to have changed, and in sources ranging from the Bible to Chinese record we find reference to vast change in orbit of the sun (as viewed by the observer). This dichotomy, the author speaks of more length in the paper, “Plasma Petroglyphs, Geoglyphs, and the Megafauna Extinction.”

⁴⁷ Tidal or phase locking is a perfect example of electromagnetism overcoming newtonian gravity. Examples include: Earth Mars, Earth-Moon, Earth-Venus ([orbital resonance](#)), Pluto-Charon, and Saturn’s rings.

⁴⁸ There appears to be a strange phenomenon currently where Chinese keep visiting Antarctica. <https://goo.gl/9YvSwP>

<p>Lunar/Thunderbolt causes of megafauna extinction</p>	<p>The bulk of this is covered in the paper “Plasma Petroglyphs...”³⁵ however, there is geological evidence as well as mythological evidence in the extreme that Thunderbolts were the cause of megafauna extinctions.</p> <p>The main argument for them is the overly selective yet unselective almost randomized nature of the extinctions, which has baffled scientists for an explanation. This vector is none other than Step Potential, which kills thousands of people and tens of thousands of animals every year. Only with plasma arc discharge of this magnitude it drastically altered the species populations globally, even where ice and humans had little to no impact on herd populations.</p>	<p>Delaware myth⁴⁹ Lakota myth⁵⁰ MesoAmerican myths⁵¹ Biblical accounts⁵² Greek/Tridents⁵³ & Typhon battles Zeus⁵⁴ Sumerian and Indian Tridents Chinese myths⁵⁵ Indian myths Norse Mammoths blown away where they stood Instant Petrification evidence⁵⁶ Failure of Carolina Bay theories Barringer Crater and the missing impact fracturing⁵⁷ Plus shape and depth issues.⁵⁸ Bullseye craters in Hudson Bay⁵⁹ South American Chibca and other Myths⁶⁰ Devil’s Tower⁶¹ Grand Canyon (a lichtenberg formation) Stone Mountain⁶² & Ayer’s Rock (Uluru)⁶³ The Knobs Region, KY (lichtenbergs)</p>
<p>Unrealism of Dark Matter/Energy</p>	<p>Dark Matter is actually plasma in “dark mode.” Most of the missing matter has been found to be baryons⁶⁴, and the rest is un-needed to explain galactic alignment.</p> <p>Dark Energy is solely evidenced by a misunderstanding of Red Shift. Halton Arp corrected this with Intrinsic Redshift, which means light not only slows down,</p>	<p>Multi-charge CDM Search for electrons in CDM “Black hole” direct current measurement Baryon induced fluctuations in CDM Dark Matter missing in Galaxy Failure to find Neutrinos in CDM decay Dark Matter non-interactivity with matter Milky Way Halo not showing DM decay Halton Arp’s papers on Intrinsic Redshift</p>

⁴⁹ “In Search of Ice Age Americans,” K Tankersley, p 51-52

⁵⁰ “Cycle of Cosmic Catastrophes: How a Stone-Age Comet Changed the Course of the World,” Firestone, West, and Smith

⁵¹ Unfortunately most of the relevant Mayan and Aztec codices were burned (on purpose) in a single great fire July 12, 1562. For more info on Mayan myth see <http://www.mythencyclopedia.com/Le-Me/Mayan-Mythology.html>

⁵² “He gave up their cattle also to the hail, and their flocks to hot thunderbolts” Psalms 78:48

⁵³ And <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trident>

⁵⁴ Compare [Greek coin representation of thunderbolt](#) with [Zoroastrian Zervan](#)

⁵⁵ Most Chinese Myths refer to the later, Archaic and Transition Periods, and to humanity’s survival. Such as that of Houyi. For more info, please see <https://thediomat.com/2015/11/the-apocalypse-psyche-a-look-at-chinese-eschatology/>

⁵⁶ Google has suppressed searches for “Peter Mungo Jupp,” the best continued research of this can be found on his website, [Ancient Destructions](#) or in this forum thread on Thunderbolts.info <https://goo.gl/tX4V7e>

⁵⁷ Strange to say, but the study is difficult to find, whereas numerous examples of shallow/surface seismic studying abound <here> <https://goo.gl/KDSVEs>, <here> <https://goo.gl/Vw3RAc>, and <here> <https://goo.gl/kMUeCB>

⁵⁸ Note the square is not square but octagonal (see below); [the depth is also not conical. The fracture lines are very absent.](#)

⁵⁹ Compare with well known impact sites, such as those in my presentation, or the [Chicxulub Crater](#). They lack bullseye rebounds of rim height altitudes.

⁶⁰ “Fingerprints of the Gods,” G Hancock, p188

⁶¹ http://www.sylvanrocks.com/devils_tower_climbing/legends_history

⁶² [Stone Mountain is 825 ft tall](#), and this very much matches the KY Knobs lichtenbergs which never exceed 900 feet.

⁶³ [Wiki](#) <https://goo.gl/q2eWd2>, [Geology](#) <https://goo.gl/YARHDe>, [Myth](#) <https://goo.gl/3KWRq2>, [History](#) <https://goo.gl/juKr8Q>, [More Info](#) <https://goo.gl/EQSRUK>

⁶⁴ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2149742-half-the-universes-missing-matter-has-just-been-finally-found/>

	but ages, ⁶⁵ as does everything else.	Birkeland Current Efficiency
Electro-gravity	The Structured Atom is able to accomodate for the weakness of the random nucleus model. Using Platonic Solids, it is able to accurately explain bonding and matter changes in a simple way that negates the need for neutrons and explains the nucleus' cohesion using a single unified force: electromagnetism (at close distances). Furthermore this approach explains the analogs of force/weight and gravity/lorentz force. Gravity is merely the resultant of differential of charge and distance	SAM website and new Periodic Table Electro-gravity (video) (diagram) (paper) The Weak and Strong Forces are actually just electromagnetism between quarks, bosons, baryons, etc... at very short distances . ⁶⁶ Note these are already measured in "electronVolts" Physicists eager to make up new matter, energy, and even forces Dinosaur and insect size limits ⁶⁷ Giants, gigantopithecus, and the decline of megafauna species ⁶⁸
Expanding Earth	The expanding Earth is a secret of the USGS. Every year they set the GPS measured growth to 0 and pretend it is an error, however the actual number is closer to 140mm a year in diameter. It is common knowledge that the outer edges of the Atlantic coastlines fit, but few people know that the Pacific coasts and the Indian ocean coasts all fit as well.	Neal Adams Presentations SW Carrey Watch the evidence yourself More Explanations USGS report on growth changes ⁶⁹ Professore Meyl explains neutrino induced growth (and this series) Tectonic Plates Shifting direction (paper 2) The potential Hollow Earth The potential water core ⁷⁰ How water is used to trap radiation ⁷¹ The direction of radiation from Solar Wind entering at the Earth's poles Robert Distinti explains crustal collapse ⁷²
Origins of Tao,	Typhon, the Midgard Serpent, the plague	Earth in Upheaval and Ages in Chaos I & II

⁶⁵ "Tired light cosmology" is actually just part of EPEMC

<https://www.nature.com/news/cosmologist-claims-universe-may-not-be-expanding-1.13379>

⁶⁶ Note how much closer the other forces are to each other, while gravity remains inordinately weak. [Gravity Waves](#) are a concept [invented by Henri Poincare](#), and ultimately they are "bled off" of charge ripples, which of course exhibit wave-particle duality.

http://www.science20.com/relativity_and_beyond_it/henri_poincare_predicted_the_existence_of_gravitational_waves_as_early_as_june_5_1905-165539

⁶⁷ One of the most horrific aspects of the Paleozoic Era and Triassic Period [is that arthropods](#) and [insects reached gigantic proportions](#). The fact that they do not anymore is a strong indication of gravity changes.

⁶⁸ Not ironically, [humans still feel personally responsible for megafauna decline](#), despite the unlikelyhood. The politicization of global warming and climate change has given rise to a false consensus about megafauna extinction. But kill sites found worldwide do not agree with the chronology or numbers. The fact that so many edible species remained later on casts doubts, not to mention the general population sparseness.

⁶⁹ 0.00000038% or 8mm (radius) per annum. <http://subtleatomics.com/expanding-earth>

⁷⁰ In a future Whitepaper, the author will discuss the mechanisms that explain the heavy [EZ] water core and Expanding Earth, as well as crustal displacement and collapse.

⁷¹ Exclusion Zone (EZ) Water: <https://www.pollacklab.org/> and Structured Water: <http://h3o2water.com/>

⁷² Related discussion: Solar convection sources - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eTLVAuvT7e4>

Phaethon, Typhon, etc...	of Darkness, Hundun, etc... share in common a "genesis" of watery, chaotic, dusty, and deadly origins. In truth these events were occurring at the end of the Archaic Period and/or repeated during the Megalithic Period. As such, references to an origin in a black soup of chaos are common religious themes globally.	Taoism: Hundun ⁷³ Pangu ⁷⁴ Wuji Taijitu ⁷⁵ Norse myth & Jörmungandr ; Fenrir Zeus' battle with Typhon Phaethon Book Hamlet's Mill (audiobook) The Squatter Man/Great Man , and other plasma formations that are not planetoids but behave as titans . ⁷⁶
Electroquaking, geo storms, etc...	Weather is well known to be electrically related . The change in cyclone models includes now the understanding that cold wind actually drives tornados, not hot air, and there is no horizontal convection turned upright. Cold air carries static charge. ⁷⁷ But the more enlightened understanding comes from Earth Spots ⁷⁸ : differentials in pressure and temperature, wind vector and intensity and upper atmospheric vortices that induce changes. When thermal energy is added to the equation then powerful vortices can occur. At the next level energy is affecting pressure buildup inside the lithosphere and crust, and a release can be triggered as an earthquake, volcanic eruption, etc... Such geomagnetic storms are related to magnetic tunneling from the sun, driven by Coronal Holes. ⁷⁹	Davidson (SuspiciousObservers) (paper) Weatherman's Guide to the Sun Electroquakes . ⁸⁰ Pakistan, October 8, 2005 China March 17, 2010 Indonesia April 11, 2012 Ionic Precursors M7.0+ Solar Polar Magnetic Aa Index Sept 2017 Solar Flare and hurricanes Triple hurricane event associated with flares SpaceNews Interview Magnetic tunnels Pecos Hank interview on formation of tornadoes

⁷³ "Hundun 混沌 was semantically extended from a mythic "primordial chaos; nebulous state of the universe before heaven and earth separated" to mean "unintelligible; chaotic; messy; mentally dense; innocent as a child".

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hundun>

⁷⁴ "Three main views describe the origin of the Pangu myth. The first is that the story is indigenous and was developed or transmitted through time to Xu Zheng. Senior Scholar Wei Juxian states that the Pangu story is derived from stories during the Western Zhou Dynasty. He cites the story of Zhong (重) and Li (黎) in the "Chuyu" section of the ancient classics Guoyu. In it, King Zhao of Chu asked Guanshefu (觀射父) a question: "What did the ancient classic "Zhou Shu" mean by the sentence that Zhong and Li caused the heaven and earth to disconnect from each other?" The "Zhou Shu" sentence he refers to is about an earlier person, Luu Xing, who converses with King Mu of Zhou. King Mu's reign is much earlier and dates to about 1001 to 946 BC. In their conversation, they discuss a "disconnection" between heaven and earth....

A brother and his sister became the only survivors of the prehistoric Deluge by crouching in a gourd that floated on water. The two got married afterwards, and a mass of flesh in the shape of a whetstone was born. They chopped it and the pieces turned into large crowds of people, who began to reproduce again. The couple were named 'Pan' and 'Gou' in the Zhuang ethnic language, which stand for whetstone and gourd respectively. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pangu>

⁷⁵ The swirl of the [original taiji \(yin+yang\)](#) indicate a similar perspective effect in the Venus/Mars separation from configuration as is demonstrated at the Great Serpent Mound. Twisting around each other is the long plasma streamers.

⁷⁶ <https://goo.gl/W8xBZn>

⁷⁷ The author's paper regarding electrostatic health effects is not yet released. However, [this graph demonstrates this](#).

⁷⁸ <https://goo.gl/xzeKC8>

⁷⁹ <http://www.weatherboy.com/exploring-coronal-holes/>

⁸⁰ Podcast discussion: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9XykMcZBolc>

Table 5 - Worldwide Symbols and Plasma-Electromagnetic Model explanations⁸¹

<p>Taijitu: Mars and Venus (tail) plasma conjunction</p>	<p>Bagua: Compare with Norse Symbol (next); trigrams are clearly toroids (see Peratt)</p>	<p>Helm of Awe: Clear depiction of the Bagua and tridents</p>	<p>Vegvisir: all manner of peratt formations; Note the "Fire" (West) gua appears like a menorah</p>
<p>Eye of Horus; actually eye of Amon-Ra/ Cronus/ Saturn.</p>	<p>Peratt Formation: note the bottom "owl eyes" which are also known as the breasts of the Mother Goddess⁸²</p>	<p>Credit: Dr. Anthony Peratt</p>	<p>Khakassia, Siberia: note the Peratt "tree" and the Celtic Cross, as well as the Squatter Man</p>
<p>Menorah Mound: Hopewell, Ohio⁸³</p>	<p>Birkeland Current: Yin Yang and Owl Eye formation</p>	<p>Nazca Squatter Man & Thunderbolt Structure simulation - Peratt</p>	<p>The Great Man: Kentucky; plasma torus clearly depicted (bottom) as well as pole? of Jupiter (Heaven)</p>
	<p>Credit: A. Perratt</p>		

⁸¹ [2] pp. 38-47

⁸² https://youtu.be/n_l810EVYSU

⁸³ ["Ancient Monuments of the Mississippi Valley," Squier & Davis](#)

<p>Trident/Vajra: various thunderbolt shapes, would depend on angle of perspective and cultural adaptations.</p>			
<p>Ishtar⁸⁴ (Mother Goddess); ruling on behalf of Shamash, Ishtar was enemies with Gilgamesh</p>			
<p>Tawa (Sun Kachina): Planet Jupiter as Helios (the sun)</p>			
<p>Inanna with wings (see Nazca wings), tridents, and foot on lion. Akkad</p>			

⁸⁴ [Ishtar \(Venus\): Innana, Aphrodite \(beauty form\), Athena \(warrior form\), Nu'ut & Isis](#)

<p>Awen Symbol: subjection symbol of 3 powers in Heavens and plasma streamers</p>			
<p>Astronomy site: “owl” conjunction chiseled more recently, as compared to polar configuration; Awen symbol implicated. KY</p>			
<p>“Turkey foot” glyph: asymmetrical (altered perspective) awen depicting conjunction, Kentucky</p>			

⁸⁵ Celtic is an inappropriate term for Welsh/Khumry and Pictish origins, however it is still standard.

<p>Same: sketch of Biggs Site; note the conical mound formation, one of the best examples worldwide until destroyed Compare with Sumerian hats.</p>			
<p>Thunderbird glyph; note the Awen symbol in chest; depicts end of world scenario. Four toed "talons" reach down (thunderbolts). This is after the discharge of one; Kentucky</p>			
<p>Great Serpent Mound: world's largest effigy mound, built on top of Thunderbolt "bullseye" crater; depicts Venus "Great Comet"; note spiral tail is perspective leaving Mars. Ohio</p>			

⁸⁶ Note also the arms are in octagonal shape, and spiral is circular, and compare to Newark and Amazon.

<p>Keiki Beach Squatter Glyphs: even isolated until Modernity, Hawaiians from ancient times (and Haida in Canada) depict the same Peratt formations. Oahu</p>			
<p>Kukulkan: Great dragon that devours the world; note the spiral motif and two spheres (compare to movement glyph at left); the movement of Venus into destroyer mode; Mayan</p>			
<p>Feet glyphs: show clear outlines of celestial bodies, Kentucky</p>			

⁸⁷ <https://www.sciencealert.com/saturn-s-mysterious-hexagon-has-changed-from-blue-to-gold-and-no-one-knows-why>

⁸⁸ Earth, Moon, Mars, and Venus

Owl Glyph: depicts plasma sheath and conjunction; KY	Awen symbol shows clear asymmetry (subject of other paper); Kentucky	Mt. Horeb, Lexington, KY	Henge glyphs: depicting polar configuration; explains entrance mounds such as Mt. Horeb
Jupiter's South Pole: hexagonal, with counter-rotating cylinders in atmosphere ⁸⁹	Jupiter's South Pole (color): Up to 15 layers thick plasma sheathing, as seen in SAFIRE paper 1.	Moon's Bull's Eye Crater: defies impact physics and shows clear discharges ⁹⁰	Hexagonal Bull's Eye crater: impossible impact physics; Mimas
Eye of the Sahara: site of massive Mars to Earth discharge when Mars dumped the Sahara on Earth; Mauritania	Credit: Andrew Hall ⁹¹ Lightning made conical mound, formed by prolonged discharge. This is the anode. Southwest, United States	Concentric circle glyphs: with exit to side, and squatter man (and modified hands); shows clear meaning of cause of craters - the "Great Man";	Credit: Andrew Hall Maars of Pinacate ⁹² : showing clear crater rim discharges, Sonora, Mexico (Properties of Shock Waves) (Electric volcanos) (Arc Blasted Mountains) (Torrential Winds)

⁸⁹ Caused by solar system sized Birkeland "coaxial" currents. [Counter-rotation is expected](#). See Donald Scott and JPL <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>

⁹⁰ Both the Moon's bull's eye(s) and Mimas' famous one, as well as the millions more especially on Mars, account for the counter-rotational shape of a plasma Thunderbolt discharge. The hypothesis therefore being that seemingly random locations for heng mounds worldwide are not random at all. Earth was heaped up upon worn down craters to keep them viable as worship spaces. The entry-ways were rim discharge burns that wore away, **leaving a pathway into the henge**.

⁹¹ <https://thedailyplasma.blog/category/electric-universe/page/2/>

⁹² <https://www.thunderbolts.info/wp/2017/01/20/the-maars-of-pinacate-part-one/>

</p> <p>Credit: SAFIRE Project</p>			
<p>"Dinwoody Site": what at first appears to be a grotesque bearded man is now obviously more conjunction and discharge. Wyoming</p>			
<p>"Newspaper Rock," Utah</p>			

<p>End of Great Conjunction = cause of cometary hail and forming of new mountains. Wyoming</p>			
<p>Coastal Observatory: this is a strange location for preserving art and heritage, but a perfect (no tree cover) location for astronomical observations. This is also what is found in Ireland and Hawaii. The Canadian coastal Haida people pride themselves in their ancient origins; British Columbia. Each of the following four sites below will repeat this motif. Mainstream archaeology has no explanation or even an attempt for this phenomenon.</p>			
<p>Etowah River, GA, USA</p>			

<p>“Pyramid of the Sun”: Set in Mexico City (formerly Tenochtitlan), this amazing pyramid, the best of the movement, has been called an Aztec pyramid. It can now be laid to rest that indeed, the Pyramid of the Sun referred to the previous Sun, Shamash or Quetzalcoatl, which is the primeval sun (for this culture), which at the time was Jupiter/Jesus, unless it be, as usual, in remembrance of the First Age, and to Saturn.</p>			
<p>“Kofun” ‘keys’ mounds: These odd shaped step pyramids should not be misinterpreted to the same period or the same rays. They are newer, from the age of Mars’ descent, which caused red dust to stretch forth towards Earth. However, they may call back to the first time in design; Japan</p>			

⁹³ Subtracting the added 600 years Velikovsky discovered were added by erroneous early Egyptology. See “Ages of Chaos: Volume I”

⁹⁴ This is a particularly important ceremony being depicted. At the end of the conjunction, Venus started to extend far out of phase, and create a long “bowling pin” shape of plasma. The shell shape of the glyphs meant that the gods were falling from the sky. In this context Akhenaten is praying to the two gods to return to position and re-establish the wonder days of Atum-Re, Zep Tepi. He is famous for failing and his movement towards archaic monotheism is overturned. The panic to appease the gods would have been very intense. Some have speculated, for many reasons he was the pharaoh of Exodus, and indeed may have even been Moses, although there is not much physical evidence to go on.

<https://grahamhancock.com/moses-akhenaten-same-person-osman/>

Table 6 - Summary of EPEMC Stellar-Earth Circuit Geology⁹⁵

The EGE exists as part of a stellar electromagnetic network.	These magnetic tunnels and filaments are owing to Birkeland Currents	The HE is formed by a very thin series of layers that act as a transceiver of stellar and planetary signals
The solar system (SS) functions as an effective electrical circuit.	The planets and other bodies have varying levels of conductance, resistance, capacitance, and inductance	The upper layers connect via magnetic tunnels and stellar winds; the inner spongier mantle is where heated materials circulate (due to polarized molecules)
The modular SS forms part of a galactic “pearl necklace” effect, which is overall a greater galactic and intergalactic circuit of energy transfer	The SS functions as an organ, and each planet or satellite, as an organelle, and each layer in them is a tissue, with a specific function in the solar circuit (SC).	The crust is the junction layer, it is a thin permeable membrane of highly reactive chemical substances and unstable molecules which perform electro-magnetic transfer tasks, including accumulation and dispersion.
The sun behaves as a transistor, but exfoliates fused material both in long periods and suddenly, if fused (heavy) material accumulates interiorly to the Hollow Sun (HS)	The sun is affected by a series of analog signals from other stars, which behave in parallel	The parallel galactic stars then act in series with other components (such as nebulae, clusters, quasars, etc...) and galaxies
The Earth behaves as a stellar transformer	It receives energy in both poles, but grows as a fruit on a vine	The cosmic rays, particularly neutrinos, are trapped within the water-producing core
The EGE is in production of EZ-water and other heavy water due to solar winds	The HE holds the water, which is heavy and captures neutrino and other radiation, generating heat	The heat and pressure is augmented by voltage “tension”; the Earth is a spherical capacitor.
The PT is due to crystallization properties and thermoelectric convection	Convection pressure is maintained by current storage (induction)	Crystallization enables piezoelectric circulating along “leylines” much as any circuit diagram
PT movement happens slowly relative to humans, but can accelerate due to thermomagnetic changes in the Field	Crustal bubbling occurs at rapid convection “hotspots” which are places of increased electromagnetic tunnel pressure	Joints between active PT may also influence the Field and release heat and thermoelectromagnetic energy to stabilize the transformer
As the transformer grows, its C,L,R. N1/2 properties will modify	Convections may heat up or shut down as mantle material shifts	Such shifts produce minor wobble in Earth tilt
Earth tilt is also decreasing due to stellar re-configuration	Tidal lock and lunar influence	Stellar cycles have a predictable

⁹⁵ [3] pp. 13-14

	continue to generate convection, but decrease as the moon moves away from Earth	and uniformitarian effect upon solar bodies
Hotspot bubbling may increase the space beneath crusts, introducing large oceanic cavities of heavy water	Heavy water pockets temporarily give buoyancy to the crust, but cracks do form, leaking water through crystalline minerals and changing water to "normal form"	Changes in stellar flow, such as new stars, novae, and comets will alter the growth rate and act as trigger events
When bubbles pop, the weight of the crust may squeeze the rest of the water through causing slow collapse.	When hot spots explode, the collapse may be sudden and violent.	When rifts form, Earth spots (EM tunnels with the sun) may move over them causing sudden tearing movements, precipitating violent earthquakes beyond PT norms.
When the HE is heated up, it will undergo a rapid cooldown internally as high pressure ejecta precipitate to the surface and cover the planet. May be coeval with stellar exfoliation	When the EGE growth rate exceeds the PT subduction rate by a high degree, tears in the rifts may create new megavolcanoes and hotspots, and baby continents.	Heavier continental crusts will dominate thinner crusts, but remain vulnerable to upper atmospheric charge
The SC interacts with the galactic circuit, but the active sun (Sol) dominates the plasma distribution in the SS	The larger gas giants (GG) have greater field effects, which have in turn significant effects on the EGE	Mountains may rise or fall suddenly, as canyons may form suddenly, in the interaction of SC components discharge, and electrogravity uplifts or pushes down crystal lattice formations
The HE inner core may in fact also be a fusion reactor; it is not known	The spongy mantle may also, in fact, produce hydrocarbons, it is not known	The movement of charge distribution in the SC, EGE, and GC's overall conforms to the laws of energy and conductance.

Table 7 - Example evidence of Uplift and Submersion corollaries⁹⁶

Landmass	Uplift Region/value	Downthrust Region/Value
South American Andes	Perú, Bolivia, Titicaca (4 km) ⁹⁷	
North America	Cascades, Sierras	Guyana, Florida, Appalachia ⁹⁸ (3.2km)
Pacific Coast		Marianas, Philippines
Mid-Atlantic Ridge/Azores		Davis Strait (1.1 km+)
Pacific Ridge		Hawaii, Easter Island
African Rift Valley	Kenya, Tanzania	Anti-Atlas Mountains (2-3 miles)
Western Atlantic		Caribbean, Appalachia
North Atlantic		Greenland, Norway (2.75 km)
Eastern Atlantic		African coast, Canary Isles
Southwestern Pacific	Torres Strait, New Zealand (18 km) ⁹⁹	New South Wales, Indonesia
The Orient	Tibet (3km), Bayan Kara (2 km)	Japan, Indochina (50-300 ft), Sea of Okhotsk, Gobi Desert (600-900m)
Western Europe	British Isles, Alps (~3.7-4 km)	Gibraltar
Eastern Europe	Ural Mountains	Aegean Sea
Indian Subcont+Ocean	Kashmir (6k ft - 1.5 km)	Ganges (2 km of fill)

Please note that the Earth also is surrounded by a 64,000 km (40k miles) *crack* that wraps all around it.¹⁰⁰

⁹⁶ [3] p. 27

⁹⁷ Values from "When the Earth Nearly Died," D.S. Allan & J.B. Delair

⁹⁸ aka North Atlantis, *ibid.* P. 33

⁹⁹ "With a horizontal displacement of similar magnitude.," *ibid.* P. 34

¹⁰⁰ *Ibid.* p. 35-36

Table 8 - Ancient Megalith Size and Weight Comparisons, top 50 sites.^{101 102}

Location	Stone Name	Weight (s. tons)	Length (feet)	Width/Diameter (feet)	Depth/Thickness (feet)
Yangshan Quarry	Yangshan Stele	9699.2	162	35.1	14.4
Baalbek	Unnamed Monolith 1	1818.8	64.3	19.7	18.04
Baalbek	Unnamed Monolith 2	1369.1	67.3	16.4	14.75
Aswan	The Unfinished Obelisk	1212.5	137	14.4	8.2
Baalbek	Stone of the Pregnant Woman	1102.3	66.6	14.75	13.9
Thebes	Ramesseum	1102	75		
Mangi Tungi, India	Statue of Ahimsa	990	108		
Madhyah Pradesh	Bawangaja	882	84		
Baalbek	Trilithon	882	70	14	10
Thebes	Colossi of Memnon	771.6	60		
Shravanabelagola, India	Gommateshwara	661	60	30	
Axum, Ethiopia	Great Stele	573	108		
Jerusalem	Western Stone, Holy Temple	569.9	44.6	9.8	10.8
Giza	Great Pyramid Temple	441			
Asuka, Japan	Masuda no Iwafune	440.9	36	26.2	15.4
Locmariaquer, Brittany	The Broken Menhir of Er Grah	363.8	67.6		
Karnak, Egypt	Obelisk of Karnak	328			
Alexandria	Pompey's Pillar	314.2	67.1	8.89	
Gwalior Fort	Rishabha Statue	300	58.4		
Ravenna, Italy	Mausoleum of Theodoric	253.5	3	32.8	
Gochang, Korea	Ganghwa Dolmen	248.2	23.2	18	8.5
Giza	Menkaure's Pyramid stone	242.5			
Mons Claudianus, Egypt	Granite Column	228.2	59		
Luxor, Egypt	Luxor Obelisk	227			
Saqqara	Sahure's Pyramid Stone	220.5			
Giza	Foundation Stones	200	26	19	7.5
Antequarra, Spain	Menga Dolmen	198.4			
Axum, Ethiopia	King Ezana's Stele	187.4	69		
Coatlinchan, Mexico	Statue of Tlaloc	168			
Brittany, France	Kerloas Menhir	150			
Saqqara, Egypt	Khendjer Pyramid	150			
Axum, Ethiopia	Obelisk of Axum	132.3	79		

¹⁰¹ Map: <https://www.google.com/maps/@1.1476503,-72.3674353,3z/data=!3m1!4b1!4m2!6m1!1s1!tUEGd3r3uXXuQaQVCIAzbpz-0pi5DqO>

¹⁰² [3]. Pp. 54-55

Tiwanaku, Bolivia	Ashlars	130			
Cusco, Peru	Sacsayhuamán	125			
Mycenae, Greece	Treasury of Atreus	120	27.2	17.1	3.9
Carlow, Ireland	Brownshill Dolmen	110.2			
Hawara, Egypt	Pyramid of Amenemhet III	110			
Ollantaytambo, Peru	Six large stones	100			
Rome	Baths of Caracalla	100			
Istanbul, Turkey	Hagia Sophia	100			
Easter Island	Moai	90.4	33		
Nyuserre Ini	Nyuserre Pyramid	90	32.8		
Rome	Trajan's Column	84.9	98	12.1	
Asuka, Japan	Ishibatai Kofun	75			
Rome, Italy	Pantheon Columns	60	39	5	
Malta Temple	Ħaġar Qim	57	19	9	2
Stonehenge	Largest Trilithon Sarsen Stone	50	29		
Vaishali, India	Ashoka Pillars	50	50		
Gobekli Tepe	Unfinished T-Pillar	50			
Olmec, Mexico	La Cobata	45	11	9.8	9.8

Table 9 - Relative Speeds of Sound (short list)^{103 104}

Air (for comparison to “normalcy”)	343 m/s
Water	1,498 m/s
Iron	5,130 m/s
Earth's Crust	6,000 - 8,000 m/s ¹⁰⁵

¹⁰³ Google search

¹⁰⁴ [4] p.10

¹⁰⁵ The Earth's crust is highly heterogeneous of mineral solids, which have varying densities and conductivity.

Table 10 - Relative Abundance of elements in Solar System, atoms/ 10⁶ parts silicon^{106 107}

Hydrogen	2.79×10 ¹⁰
Helium	2.72×10 ⁹
Oxygen	2.38×10 ⁷
Carbon	1.01×10 ⁷
Neon	3.44×10 ⁶
Nitrogen	3.13×10 ⁶
Magnesium	1.074×10 ⁶
Silicon	1.00×10 ⁶
Iron	9.00×10 ⁵
Sulfur	5.15×10 ⁵
Argon	1.01×10 ⁵
Aluminum	8.49×10 ⁴
Calcium	6.11×10 ⁴
Sodium	5.74×10 ⁴
Nickel	4.93×10 ⁴
Chromium	1.35×10 ⁴
Phosphorus	1.04×10 ⁴
Manganese	9550
Chlorine	5240
Potassium	3770
Titanium	2400

“As anyone can see, Hydrogen is *extremely* abundant by several orders of magnitude over a likely *padded* iron. The Earth’s crust also carries sound faster, yes, however the slowdown in the outer core is very significant. Iron is only slightly slower than the Earth’s crust and is probably supported in the mantle (in part) due to magma convection. However, the inner core seems far more likely to reflect a liquid heavy water or liquid metallic hydrogen model than an iron core, from a macro-perspective.¹⁰⁸

The main issue is that while air/gas **cannot possibly** be in the core, a thick, viscous, non-iron core can. Based on the relative abundance of hydrogen and oxygen, and upon the presence of water in the mantle¹⁰⁹ and on the surface of an EGE, it can be postulated within reason that the core is in fact a form of proto-water or heavy water.”

¹⁰⁶ Note that Iron here is including cores of Earth, Mars, and Moon, and possibly other moons, *without core samples*.
http://www.knowledgedoor.com/2/elements_handbook/element_abundances_in_the_solar_system.html

¹⁰⁷ [4] p.11

¹⁰⁸ Probably heavy water, as liquid metallic hydrogen is quite rare and difficult to make, and so far, unproven in the main.

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.livescience.com/46292-hidden-ocean-locked-in-earth-mantle.html>

Table 11 - Ratios of large satellites/planetoids to Earth-masses¹¹⁰

Body	# Satellites	Mass	Ratio
Earth	1	0.972×10^{24} kg (1 M \oplus)	1/(1 M \oplus) = 100%
Sol (Sun)	[13] ¹¹¹	1.989×10^{30} kg (3.33 x 10 ⁵ M \oplus)	.0006% ¹¹²
Jupiter	53	1.898×10^{27} kg (317.8 M \oplus)	16.7%
Helios (Saturn)	62	5.683×10^{26} kg (95.16 M \oplus)	65.2%
Uranus	27	8.681×10^{25} kg (14.54 M \oplus)	185.7%
Neptune	14	1.024×10^{26} kg (17.15 M \oplus)	81.6%

¹¹⁰ [4] p.43

¹¹¹ Not including comets and asteroids, or Planet X/Nine

<https://www.space.com/38431-new-evidence-planet-nine-existence.html>

¹¹² This low value would suggest that the sun is a relative newcomer to the solar system or recently charged up.

Table 12 - Side by side comparison of analogs of Electricity and Magnetism

Table 13 - Maxwell's Laws (See Appendix B.IV); credit: wolfram.com

Table 14 - Maxwell's vs Heaviside's Equations, side by side comparison

Table 15 - Maxwell in Differential and Integral form, developed by Heaviside

Table 16 - Original Maxwell and Modern Scalar Notation

Table 17 - Side by side comparison of Electrostatics and Gravity¹¹³

¹¹³ Not shown: EMF is 10^{39} x stronger than gravity, all units being equalized in a Newtonian framework.

Table 18 - Currents in Space scale¹¹⁴

SGEC	MHD derived jets (theoretical) ¹¹⁵	10 ¹⁸ + A
GEC	jet galaxy 3C303 ¹¹⁶	3x10 ¹⁸ A
GEC	jet SGR A* ^{117 118}	1 THz X-rays
SSC	Solar Corona Currents ¹¹⁹	10 ¹¹ - 10 ¹² A
SSC	Solar Wind ^{120 121 122}	10 ¹¹ A
SSC	Jupiter Ring currents/ Io Torus ¹²³	10 ⁹ A
SSC	Jupiter Auroral currents ¹²⁴	650,000 A
SSC	Magnetic Tunnels to Earth ¹²⁵	100,000 A
PEMS	Earth's Ring Current ^{126 127}	10 keV - 50 keV (100 keV)
PEMS	Van Allen/Heliosphere ^{128 129}	3x10 ⁹ A
PEMS	Blue Jets/Sprites ¹³⁰	10 ²³ - 10 ²⁴ photons or atoms
PEMS	Lightning ¹³¹	30k-500k A
HPG*	Powerline ¹³²	40 A (avg)
CVS	Electricity in human heart ¹³³	< 1 mA (1.87x10 ⁻⁴ A) ¹³⁴
HEGEME	Electricity in a plant ¹³⁵	4.5x10 ⁻⁸ A
CNS	Nerve conduction ^{136 137}	4-6 nA

*Human Power Grid; Cardiovascular System; Central Nervous System

¹¹⁴ [6] p.34

¹¹⁵ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1990ApJ...348...61J>

¹¹⁶ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/mg21028174.900-universes-highest-electric-current-found/>

¹¹⁷ <https://phys.org/news/2017-12-cosmic-filament-probes-galaxy-giant.html>

¹¹⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/astro-ph/0102186.pdf>

¹¹⁹ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1997A%26A...318..289K>

¹²⁰ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1967SoPh....1..220A>

¹²¹ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1029/2000JA900165>

¹²² <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1029/JA080i034p04719>

¹²³ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/mg13318093-400-science-the-billion-amp-current-that-flows-round-jupiter/>

¹²⁴ http://www.igpp.ucla.edu/public/mkivelso/refs/PUBLICATIONS/Gerard%20lo_footprint-JCG.pdf

¹²⁵ <https://www.space.com/6614-electricity-measured-space-tornadoes.html>

¹²⁶ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1983SSRv...34..223W>

¹²⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0906.0429.pdf>

¹²⁸ https://www.plasma-universe.com/Electric_currents_in_space_plasmas

¹²⁹ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1029/JZ066i005p01321>

¹³⁰ http://www.uas.alaska.edu/artsscience/naturalsciences/envs/faculty_staff/pubs/chapman.pdf

¹³¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/High_voltage

¹³² https://www.w8ji.com/power_line_voltage.htm

¹³³ <http://circres.ahajournals.org/content/circresaha/33/1/39.full.pdf>

¹³⁴ 50 mV / 268 ohm <http://circres.ahajournals.org/content/circresaha/9/6/1280.full.pdf>

¹³⁵ <https://youtu.be/-MumeA4q-5Q>

¹³⁶ <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/bb00/967a365c81263abd9ac539f954131ae6f13c.pdf>

¹³⁷ <https://physoc.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1113/jphysiol.1952.sp004734>

Although classical electromagnetism has been quite successful for mankind via Maxwell's Laws¹³⁸ (Heaviside), they are not without some glitches¹³⁹, including the Faraday Paradox^{140 141} and Inverse Source Problem.¹⁴²

As a response, in 2007 Distinti published his thesis, "Inductance Modeling Using New Electromagnetism,"¹⁴³ in which he first produced a set of improved Maxwell equations,¹⁴⁴ in order to perform his inductance modeling.

This paper is not meant to reproduce the entirety of this thesis. For brevity, the following tables and figures will demonstrate the improved model.

Table 19 - Page 21 of "New Electromagnetism," Table 3-1 equations

¹³⁸ <http://science.sciencemag.org/content/349/6244/136/tab-e-letters>

¹³⁹ <https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/150493/problem-with-maxwells-theory>

¹⁴⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Faraday_paradox

¹⁴¹ <https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/146628/faradays-paradox>

¹⁴² <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/0266-5611/22/3/018/meta>

¹⁴³ <http://www.distinti.com/docs/nethesis.pdf>

¹⁴⁴ http://www.distinti.com/docs/poster_ne3_gr.pdf

Table 20 - Page 26, Inductance Field Equations

Table 21 - Quantum scales¹⁴⁵

Water Molecule	10^{-9} m
Hydrogen Atom	10^{-10} m
Neutrons and Protons	10^{-15} m
Electrons	10^{-17} m
Quarks ¹⁴⁶	10^{-18} m
Higgs-Boson	10^{-17} m
Graviton/Gravity Wave ¹⁴⁷	10^{-21} m
Proposed strings ¹⁴⁸	10^{-33} m
Planck scale (quanta)	10^{-35} m

In terms of prediction ability, however, Supersymmetry has performed remarkably - remarkably poorly.

- 2010 - SUSY fails first LHC supertest¹⁴⁹
- 2012 - SUSY officially announced as a failure, predictions wildly off (650 GeV!!)^{150 151}
- 2015 - “beauty” quark found defies Relativity¹⁵²
- 2016 - Diphoton bump eliminated; LHC can only find Higgs-Bosons¹⁵³
- 2017 - Sparticles continue to “elude” detection¹⁵⁴ (can’t find what isn’t there fallacy)
- 2017 - Dark Matter officially fails¹⁵⁵
- 2018 - Dark Matter continues to fail¹⁵⁶, Dark energy thwarted by new size¹⁵⁷ and numbers of stars¹⁵⁸ estimates.

¹⁴⁵ [6] p.61

¹⁴⁶ Technically, they are dimensionless. See Figures 45 and 46.

¹⁴⁷

<https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/158385/if-gravitational-waves-exist-are-they-technically-just-another-form-of-light-else>

¹⁴⁸ Note: orders of magnitude are logarithmic, so that strings aren’t 3x smaller than atoms as compared to atoms from us. They are 10 with 23 zeros afterwards times smaller. So small that, obviously they cannot be proven in the least, and are therefore a pseudoscience at best.

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.math.columbia.edu/~woit/wordpress/?p=3338>

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/supersymmetry-fails-test-forcing-physics-look-new-idea/>

¹⁵¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1211.0004v1.pdf>

¹⁵² <https://phys.org/news/2015-07-supersymmetry-physics-theory.html>

¹⁵³ <http://backreaction.blogspot.com/2016/08/the-lhc-nightmare-scenario-has-come-true.html>

¹⁵⁴ <http://www.theworldin.com/article/12781/so-long-susy?fsrc=scn/tw/wi/bl/ed/>

¹⁵⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.04320.pdf>

¹⁵⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.00088.pdf>

¹⁵⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.03888.pdf>

¹⁵⁸

<https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2016/hubble-reveals-observable-universe-contains-10-times-more-galaxies-than-previously-thought>

Table 22 - Mutual Exclusion of Big Bang and Black Holes, Credit: S Crothers [sic]¹⁵⁹

All Black Hole Universes	All Big Bang Universes
(1) Spatially infinite	(1) Spatially finite (k=1) or spatially infinite (k=-1,k=0)
(2) Eternal	(2) Finite age (~13.8 billion yr)
(3) Contain only one mass	(3) Contain many masses and radiation
(4) Not expanding (static, stationary)	(4) Expanding (non-static)
(5) Asymptotically flat (or asymptotically curved)	(5) Not asymptotically anything
(6) No k-curvature	(6) k-curvature ¹⁶⁰

Table 23 - Lensing Data Surrounding the Sun (in units of the solar radius R)¹⁶¹; credit: E Dowdye¹⁶²

Impact Parameter (solar radii R)	Observational History (arsec)	General Relativity (arcsec)
R	1.75	1.75
2R	< 0.875 to negligible	½ of 1.75
3R	negligible	⅓ of 1.75
nR	Not observed	1/n of 1.75

Table 24 - Comparison of Force Scales

Attractive Force	Scale Relative to Strong ¹⁶³	Relative to EMF	Fundamental "particle"
Gravity	10 ⁻⁴¹	10 ⁻³⁶	graviton
Electromagnetism	10 ⁻³	1	photon
Electroweak	10 ⁻¹⁶	10 ⁻⁷	electron, bosons W & Z
Strong	1	102x	gluon

¹⁵⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QBorBKDnE3U>

¹⁶⁰ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0926224509001168>

¹⁶¹ <http://www.extinctionshift.com/SignificantFindings08.htm>.

¹⁶² [6] p.78

¹⁶³ <https://sureshemre.wordpress.com/2013/12/14/why-is-gravity-so-different-from-other-forces/>

Table 25 - Comparison of mass of particles

Proton	$1.6726219 \times 10^{-27}$ kg	938.27203 MeV/c ²
Electron	$9.10938356 \times 10^{-31}$ kg	510.9989 keV/c ²
Neutron	1.674929×10^{-27} kg	939.56536 MeV/c ²
Neutron - Proton	2.306×10^{-30} kg ¹⁶⁴	1.293 MeV/c ²
Proton + Electron	$1.674929\dots9 \times 10^{-27}$ kg	938.783 MeV/c ²
Proton / Electron ¹⁶⁵	1836.153	
Neutron - (Proton + Electron)	1.395×10^{-30} kg	782.3 keV/c ²
Neutron / Proton	1.001378	
Neutron / Electron ¹⁶⁶	1838.684	

Table 26 - Electric vs Gravitational Fields; credit: Physbot¹⁶⁷

¹⁶⁴ Wolfram Alpha for mass comparisons

¹⁶⁵ A human ovum / sperm size ratio is 3-65:1 ; so this ratio is 10² more significant (as a yin:yang ratio); the EMF:EWF is 10⁷ or 10,000x more significant a ratio than Proton/Electron size

¹⁶⁶ Only 1 significant figure more than the Strong Force/EMF ratio!

¹⁶⁷ <http://www.physbot.co.uk/electric-fields-and-potentials.html>

Table 27 - Wheel-city/temple/law/ship/mill International Name list¹⁶⁸

Egypt	also...	Sumer	Greece	Also...		Rome	Hindu
Sektet	Uraeus	Magur	Naus	Ixion	Gyrapsios	Navis	Surya/Rta
	Ikhet		Naos	lynx	Triptolemus		Chakravartin
Norse	Ireland	Babylon	Hebrew	Iran	Mayan	Persia	Ojibwe
Sampo	Arianrhod	Shamash	Yahweh	Siphir	Iguana House	Mithra	Anishinabeg

Table 28 - Crescent Positions seen in Worldwide Motifs¹⁶⁹

The name for the "ship" descending from the left, in Egypt, is Tua. The name for the ship ascending on the right, is Semktet

¹⁶⁸ [7] p.10

¹⁶⁹ [7] p.20

¹⁷⁰ <https://www.templeilluminaus.com/group/ancient-worlds-come-to-life/forum/topics/g-beklitepe-in-turkey>

¹⁷¹ <https://ekstrembilgi.com/blog/silivride-5000-yillik-kurganin-bulunusu-ve-on-turk-kulturu/attachment/kun-ay-sembolu-gobekli-tepe-hakasya/>

Table 29 - Children Riding Dragons¹⁷²

Table 30 - Cosmic Summits from Around the World¹⁷³

Sumer	China	Greece	India	Persia	Zoroastrian
Ilatu	Ze-wei	Olympus/Nyas	Kailash/Agni	Mithra	Kadad-i-Daitik

“King Pentheus of Thebes refused to accept the god's divinity and tried to apprehend him. The god retaliated by driving the king's daughters into a crazed frenzy and they tore him apart limb from limb. “

Table 31 - Comparison of Days of the Week and Greco-Roman vs. Nordic celestial references

Day (English)	Romance Language (Spanish)	Nordic Root	Celestial Body
Sunday	<i>Domingo</i>	The Sun	Sol
Monday	Lunes - Moon	The Moon	Luna
Tuesday	Martes - Mars/Ares	Tyr - God of War	Mars
Wednesday	Miercoles - Mercury/Hermes	Wodin - King of Gods Or Heimdall (1000 eyes)	Jupiter > Mercury
Thursday	Jueves - Jupiter/Zeus	Thor - God of Thunder	Mars/Jupiter (Electricity)
Friday	Viernes - Venus/Athene	Freya - Venus' first phase	Venus (originally Metis)
Saturday	Sabado - <i>Sabbath</i> /Saturn	Bor or Frigg - Saturn	Saturn

¹⁷² [7] p.26

¹⁷³ [7] p.28

Table 32 - Months vs. Roman and Nordic Names

Month	Roman to English	Nordic Month and Meaning ¹⁷⁴
January	Janus or Gemini	4 Dorri - Bare Frost
February	Purity/Purification ¹⁷⁵	5 Goa - Sowing Month
March	Mars Month	6 Einmanudur - One Month
April	Aphrodite	7 Harpa - a female spirit
May	Maia (wife of Vulcan)	8 Skerpla - another goddess
June	Juno (Hera) Month ¹⁷⁶	9 Solmanadur - Sun Month
July	Julius' month (formerly 5th month)	10 Heyannir - Hay Collection
August	Augustus' month (formerly 6th month)	11 Tvimanidur - Two Month
September	7th Month	12 Haustmanadur - Autumn Month
October	8th Month	1 Gormanudur - Butchering Month
November	9th Month	2 Ylir - Yule Month
December	10th Month ¹⁷⁷	3 Morsugur - Gut Fat Suckling Month

Table 33 - Comparison of Eastern and Western Energy-Mass Spectrum¹⁷⁸

Western	Solids, crystals	Liquid	Gases	Plasma	Condensed Matter	Energy	Forces
Greek	Earth	Water	Air	Fire		Pneuma	Bia
Chinese	Earth	Water	Wood ¹⁷⁹	Fire	Metal ¹⁸⁰	Qi, Jin	Dao-de, Li ¹⁸¹
Indian	Earth	Water	Air	Fire	Doshas ¹⁸²	Prajna	Aether

¹⁷⁴ http://freya.theladyofthelabyrinth.com/?page_id=808

¹⁷⁵ <https://www.crowl.org/Lawrence/time/months.html>

¹⁷⁶ Hera/Juno is Saturn after the rings formed.

¹⁷⁷ <https://svmmaapologia.files.wordpress.com/2015/12/images-11.png?w=1000>

¹⁷⁸ [12] p.3

¹⁷⁹ Literally "growing in tendrils". However, in practice it corresponds with Spring and Wind.

¹⁸⁰ Jin ("jeen" 金) is either metal or gold. It actually signifies the solar or etheric force transforming (via fire, its controller), of ordinary ore into iron, then steel, and if worked upon long enough, gold. This is not correct, of course, but the Chinese thought if the furnace was hot enough the metal would turn to gold. As it turns out, via plasma-electromagnetic fusion, this is precisely what happens. Also, during nova explosions. But they could not have known that, so it remains conjecture in Chinese alchemy. See Figure 1

¹⁸¹ Lit: "strength"

¹⁸² Conglomerated phases of energy. There are 3 doshas: vata, pitta, and kapha.

Table 34 - Paradigms Under Fire

Previous Belief/Theories	Challenging Evidence	Emerging Paradigms
Competitive Darwinian Evolution	Co-evolving species of different genres ¹⁸³	Gaia Hypothesis ¹⁸⁴
Redshift	GAIA DR2 galaxy distance data ¹⁸⁵	Intrinsic Redshift ¹⁸⁶
Quantum Mechanics ¹⁸⁷	Unexpected Double-slit results ¹⁸⁸	QED/QCD + MHD transitioning
CDM/DE, SUSY, MOND	Falsifications ¹⁸⁹	Electrical Dynamics ¹⁹⁰ , Baryons ¹⁹¹ , Covert Matter ¹⁹²
Black Hole Theory	AGN "jets" >> Hawking predictions ¹⁹³ Logic inconsistencies in classical Black Hole theory ¹⁹⁴	Electric Motor ¹⁹⁵ / Z pinch ¹⁹⁶ Modified supermassive black hole theories
Clovis First	Earlier Dating found pre-YD ¹⁹⁷	Boat travelers (i.e., diffusionism) ¹⁹⁸
Uniformitarian doctrine	Catastrophic Ice Lakes ¹⁹⁹ , comets ²⁰⁰	Catastrophic Geology resurfaces
Atlantis "fantasy"	Land masses found under ocean ²⁰¹ ; Gobekli Tepe ²⁰²	Atlantean Period Archaeology ²⁰³
Oort Cloud/Dirty Snowballs	Comets are electrified rock ²⁰⁴	Electric cometology ²⁰⁵
Accretion Theory	Multiple Unofficial failure ²⁰⁶	Solar System Rearrangement ²⁰⁷
Maxwellian EMF	Leakage in formulas, failure of Heaviside vectors ²⁰⁸	New Electromagnetism ²⁰⁹ , and Vortrix © Algebra ²¹⁰

¹⁸³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Coevolution>

¹⁸⁴ <https://courses.seas.harvard.edu/climate/eli/Courses/EPS281r/Sources/Gaia/Gaia-hypothesis-wikipedia.pdf>

¹⁸⁵ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.03298.pdf>

¹⁸⁶ https://www.haltonarp.com/articles/intrinsic_redshifts_in_quasars_and_galaxies.pdf

¹⁸⁷ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1707.02857>

¹⁸⁸ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1808/1808.08901.pdf>

¹⁸⁹ [9]. Table 2

¹⁹⁰ NASA and Princeton, as of writing, have gone full PEMC.[9]

¹⁹¹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1709.05024>

¹⁹² <https://sites.google.com/site/electricuniversegateway/recent-news/covertmatteraroundgalaxies>

¹⁹³ Not to mention, also giant "gas" (plasma) bubbles emerging from NGC 5195

<https://www.bbc.com/news/science-environment-35237863>

¹⁹⁴ See [6], pp. 66-73

¹⁹⁵ https://www.plasma-universe.com/Texts:On_Possible_Electric_Phenomena_in_Solar_Systems_and_Nebulae

¹⁹⁶ <http://www.everythingselectric.com/z-pinch/>

¹⁹⁷ <https://arstechnica.com/science/2017/11/majority-of-scientists-now-agree-that-humans-came-to-the-americas-by-boat/>

¹⁹⁸ https://www.science.ku.dk/english/press/news/2012/eske-clovis_jenkins/

¹⁹⁹ <https://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/10.1175/2008JPO3877.1>

²⁰⁰ KT/Chixalub, Younger Dryas, 362 CE, 1491 CE, Barringer, etc...

²⁰¹ [3]

²⁰² le - the Tepe Period is after the end of the Younger Dryas. [2]. Table 1, pp.3-5 and Table 3, pp.8

²⁰³ Various sites: Gunung Padang, Bosnia, Zealandia, Doggerland, Sundaland, etc...

²⁰⁴ <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2018/new-insights-on-comet-tails-are-blowing-in-the-solar-wind>

²⁰⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=34wtt2EUToo>

²⁰⁶ <https://www.space.com/2206-death-spiral-theorists-cant-solar-systems.html>

²⁰⁷ <https://phys.org/news/2018-03-theory-planets-solar-compositions.html>

²⁰⁸ http://lefteris-kaliambos.wikia.com/wiki/ERRORS_IN_MAXWELL%27S_EQUATIONS

²⁰⁹ <http://www.distinti.com/docs/neThesis.pdf>

²¹⁰ [6] pp. 57-58 and <https://www.patreon.com/EtherealMechanics/posts?tag=Vortrix%20Algebra>

Table 35 - Technology Pioneers Comparison²¹¹

Technology	Westerner & Date (CE)	Chinese Counterpart	Δ (years)
Surgery with Anesthesia ²¹²	John Warren, 1846	Hua Tuo ²¹³ , ~200 CE ²¹⁴	1646
Press	Johannes Gutenberg, 1440	868 CE ²¹⁵	572
Legalism ²¹⁶	Magna Carta, 1215	Hanfeizi, ~250 BCE ²¹⁷	1465
Cold/Flu Drugs ²¹⁸	Thomas Dover, 1762	Zhang Zhongjing, 200 CE ²¹⁹	1562
Travel to North America	Christopher Columbus ²²⁰ , 1492	Zhang He ²²¹ , 1421-1434 CE	58-71
Paper	~1100 ²²² (max 1300)	Han Dynasty, 100 BCE (max 105 CE)	~1200
Systematic Chemistry ²²³	Georg Agricola, 1556 ²²⁴	Zhou Dynasty, 1000 BCE ²²⁵	~2500
Earthquake Detector	John Milne et al... ²²⁶ , 1880	Zhang Heng, 132 CE ²²⁷	1748

²¹¹ [12] p.6

²¹² Sumer, India, and possibly Egypt preceded even China, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_surgery

²¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hua_Tuo

²¹⁴ The Sanguozhi (Records of Three Kingdoms) records this as historical idea and fact, including his very method of using boiled cannabis bags. It was written in 369 CE, and all notes completed by 429 CE
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Records_of_the_Three_Kingdoms

²¹⁵ <https://www.history.com/topics/inventions/printing-press>

²¹⁶ As an end to traditional feudal serfdom and beginning of bureaucracy.

²¹⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Han_Feizi

²¹⁸ Drugs pre-existed Dover's Powder, but not as diaphoretics. Mostly they were painkillers such as Opium and Laudanum.

<https://inpu.d.wordpress.com/timeline-of-events-in-the-history-of-drugs/>

²¹⁹ Shang Han Lun (On Cold Damage), https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zhang_Zhongjing

²²⁰ Madoc and King Arthwys, as well as the Vikings preceded Columbus by hundreds of years, but this is not accepted. China's Shang Dynasty however, preceded them by several hundred years. Here we only consider the Age of Exploration

<https://www.amazon.co.uk/Gates-Fengtu-translation-chapters-exploration-ebook/dp/B078QD9VR7>

²²¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_paper

²²² Non-alchemy, production of complex alloy or functional compounds; Paracelsus was 1515, however his work on diethyl ether was not necessarily systematic.

²²³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_chemistry#Medieval_alchemy

²²⁴ "In 2006 scientists at Stanford, Los Alamos National Laboratory and the Institute for Solid State Physics (University of Tokyo), showed that Han purple "loses a dimension" under suitable conditions when it enters a new state, as a Bose-Einstein Condensate. The researchers noted that "We have shown, for the first time, that the collective behavior in a bulk three-dimensional material can actually occur in just two dimensions. Low dimensionality is a key ingredient in many exotic theories that purport to account for various poorly understood phenomena, including high-temperature superconductivity, but until now there were no clear examples of 'dimensional reduction' in real materials," said Ian Fisher" https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Han_purple_and_Han_blue

²²⁵ <https://www.thoughtco.com/who-invented-the-seismograph-1992425>

²²⁶ <https://blogs.wsj.com/chinarealtime/2008/06/05/earthquake-detection-past-and-present/>

Table 36 - Original Fibonacci Code^{228 229}

0	Wuji / Hundun
1	Dao / Tian / Shen
1	Shang Di / De
2	Taiji (Yin+Yang) / Heaven (Creative) & Earth (Receptive)
3	Tian-ren-di (Heaven, mankind, and Earth)
5	Wuxing (5 Elements)
8	Bagua (8 trigram laws ²³⁰)
13	12+1 (eg, 12 meridian channels + center pole in body)

Table 37 - Rates of c in various materials²³¹

Material	v _L (km/s)	% less than c (in vacuum, 299,792.5)
Plasma/Solar Wind	299,000	0.26%
Air (ground level)	299,700	0.03%
Water	225,000	24.9%
Glass (clear)	200,000	33.3%
Fibre ²³²	204,190	31.8%
Crystal (diamond)	124,000	58.6%
Copper (electrons)	59,600	80.3%

²²⁸ Leonardo Fibonacci (1170-1250) was a genius, but not first; for that matter maybe the Chinese weren't either. But they were the most systematic prior to the Qabbalists and Rosicrucians (and other numerologists).

²²⁹ [12] p.8

²³⁰ Heaven/Causality; Wind/Flux/Change/Evolution; River/Water/Relativity/Danger; Mountain/Conservation; Earth/Vibration/quantum; Thunder/Rotation; Fire/Lightning/Polarity (electromagnetism); Lake/Essence/Dao/Resonance

²³¹ [13] p.9

²³² <https://www.quora.com/What-is-precisely-the-speed-of-light-in-fiber-optics>

Table 38 - Chart of illogical juxtapositions and deductions about archaic and woodland era aboriginals²³³

Observed Advanced Cultural Aspects	Perceived Weaknesses of Allegewi Culture
Advanced geometrical and surveying skills ²³⁴	Could not discover the wheel ²³⁵
Worship of animals in complex ritualistic practice	Decreased or absent capability in accurate effigy depictions (despite earlier precise depictions)
Complex chemical and agricultural processes ²³⁶	Weak or absent strategic fortification techniques ²³⁷
Advanced pottery and art forms	Difficulty building lasting civilizations ²³⁸
Industrial and trade networks ²³⁹	Simplistic hunter-gatherer tribal society
Use of sophisticated numerology, such as 51.8 degree angle ^{240 241} , as reflected in Giza pyramid slope, ²⁴² showing engineering and design skills ²⁴³	Inability to make clear, clean cut effigies and art work due to a lack of advancement or sophistication (literally: neolithic or paleolithic)

²³³ [16] p.8

²³⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0706.1325.pdf>

²³⁵ The Wheel of the Creator was a well known shape or glyph world-wide. All the Saturn Myth relations are contained in the large table generated by the author. The lack of writing inherited does not diminish the simple fact that the entire world saw this formation, and the Allegewi-Hopewell and Mississippians undoubtedly knew about the wheel, but found it too sacred to use.

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/118Tbu6mdDBTRaYJyBtLwMSkN4-Usz02j_tR_pKx6uos/edit?usp=sharing

²³⁶ <https://chequamegonhistory.wordpress.com/2017/05/04/ancient-garden-beds-of-michigan/>

²³⁷ For example, at the Fort Ancient Park, Ohio... this is clearly **not** a military fort. But that does not mean that they did not build stockades, such as the Cahokians did. They just did not live inside forts as was originally thought when Ft. Ancient culture was named. (Surely it should be renamed).

²³⁸ Archaic cultures lasted in areas something 3,000-6,000 years, even in KY. However (without cataclysms) the current model for the Allegewi and Hopewell cultures are that they struggled to build long-term societies due mostly to war, disease, and agricultural decline. However, many of the important times in these periods are punctuated by known cataclysmic periods from the Old World: 5,500 YBP, 3,600 YBP, 2,600 YBP, and 1,700 YBP. The author agrees that smallpox introduced to the New World is a reasonable vector for the beginning of the total end for Pre-historic tribes. C. 1550-1650 CE

²³⁹ Copper, pearl, mica, fluorite, etc...

²⁴⁰ <https://moundbuilder.blogspot.com/2014/08/advanced-mathematics-used-in.html>

²⁴¹ http://www.allanstime.com/Spiritual/Hopewell_Civilization_Great_Octagon/

²⁴² <http://www.tony5m17h.net/pyramid.html>

²⁴³ Randall Carlson makes the point that the Universal Language at the time of Babylon is symbology and sacred numerology. Chris Dunn has recorded fascinating engineering and machining evidence in his second book "Lost Technologies of Ancient Egypt"

Table 39 - Effigy Themes that Cross-correlate irrespective of geography and linguistics²⁴⁴

Culture	Earthworks/Stoneworks	Petro/picto/hieroglyphs	Another Culture
Allegewi	Mt. Horeb, Lexington, KY Cosmic egg over Atum-Re (Ra)		
Hopewell	Newark Earthworks, OH Credit: NatGeo		
Paracas	Cone-head Man, Peru Credit: Quora		
Nazca	"Hummingbird" ²⁴⁸	Burnt Ridge, KY	Egypt (Horus again):

²⁴⁴ [16] pp.12-15

²⁴⁵ [26] Note: this is clearly not a fort. The intrusion of water into the earthworks is likely not accidental ("Waters of Chaos")

²⁴⁶ [15]

²⁴⁷ Note the "turtle" is 5 legged (compare to Alligator Mound), and the body is the strange octagon shape

²⁴⁸ Most assuredly not a hummingbird but a "Thunderbird"

	 Credit: Pinterest		
Amazonia			
British Isles	Avebury, England Credit: Squire & Davis (upside down)		
Pueblo	Pueblo Bonito Credit: Wikipedia ²⁵⁰		
Mexico	Chichen Itza, Mexico	Mauritius	Anna Site, MS

²⁴⁹ <https://apah.wikispaces.com/Earthworks>

²⁵⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Troyville_Earthworks

	 Miss. Culture Credit: Wikipedia ²⁵¹		
England	Knowlton, England Credit: Dreamstime		
Ireland	Tara Henges 		

²⁵¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Anna_Site

²⁵² <https://trailhiker.wordpress.com/2014/08/09/tour-of-the-hill-of-tara-and-newgrange/>

²⁵³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ancestral_Puebloans

Table 40 - Comparison of Angles and Resultant Vectors²⁵⁴

<u>Angle</u>	<u>Distanced by X</u>	<u>Distanced by Y</u>	<u>Same Distance Traveled by iceblock</u>	<u>Origin Based on length only</u>
Dead Center	583km	2690km	2752km	From Hudson Bay
30 degree vectors ²⁵⁵	583km; 336km	4660km; 2690km	2383km; 1376km	Big Snowy Mtns, MT
60 degree vectors ²⁵⁶	583km; 1010km	1553km; 2690km	1376km; 2383km	Grass River Prov. Park, Canada
48 degree vectors	583km; 648km	2422km; 2690km	1841km; 2045km	Nokomis, Saskatchewan
75 degree vectors	583km; 2176km	721km; 2690km	712km; 2658km	SW-C Hudson Bay

See Figures 58-60

Table 41 - Events/Phases in Human Memory simplified via EPEMC²⁵⁷

Event, or situation described	Cultural or other Evidence	More Complex Mainstream Explanation(s)
Out of Place errata/till (esp. in Africa and India) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In Africa the errata seem to be going from the equator NORTH²⁵⁸ ● In India the errata come from no main direction and descend south. 	 Portuguese ²⁵⁹ errata	Unexplained (but Deluge exclusion principle applied at any rate).
Mid-crustal Basalt formations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Devil's Tower ● Ayer's Rock ● Pilot Rock ● Stone Mountain ● Looking Glass Rock <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The Appalachian mountains are famously unvolcanic 	 Devil's Tower, Wyoming	Standard plate tectonics; plate weakness? There seems to be no indication as to why a volcanic formation would occur in these locations, nor any reason for upthrust, and the geologies are very out of character. Explanations given are difficult to believe.

²⁵⁴ Very Rough Angles!

²⁵⁵ The ones creating the lips in shallow angles in Figure 4

²⁵⁶ The Michigan directed ones

²⁵⁷ [16] pp.23-30

²⁵⁸ "When the Earth Nearly Died: Compelling Evidence of a Cosmic Catastrophe in 9,500 B.C.," DS Allan, 1997

²⁵⁹ The Ice Age? Very unlikely.

Siesmicless crater formations, especially geometric ones	 Barringer Crater ²⁶⁰ , AZ	Cometary Impacts There are some incredibly <i>poor</i> “astroblemes” out there as examples. However, in KY there are two <i>excellent</i> true examples of oblique astroblemes. (see Figures 3 - 12) The third (Figure 1) is clearly not a real impact. Neither are the Carolina Bays ²⁶¹
Mound building genesis	Conical mounds are almost always not typical burial mounds. “Fort” or “effigy” mounds are not forts nor villages Long, oblong mounds are burial mounds, but usually only for elit or religious or warrior folks.	Unexplained; supraterrain burial formations are without a mainstream explanation.
Dolmen phenomenon	 North Salem, Hudson Valley	Stone Age “architecture” Despite the absurdity of the formations, mainstream archaeology either claims dolmens of such ridiculously heavy roofs are primitive architecture or somehow natural, which is equally preposterous.
Calendar alterations	Chinese changes ^{262 263 264 265} Roman changes ^{266 267} Egyptian changes ^{268 269}	Continual attempts to figure out how to farm and follow the sun (but wouldn’t people that rely on the sun and moon to farm pass on their knowledge yearly and generationally?).

²⁶⁰ Inexplicably octagonal, perpendicular, and undisturbed in soil at depth 100’ below crater basin. 0 shock ripples around

²⁶¹ See aforementioned presentation for detailed analysis

²⁶² http://www.math.nus.edu.sg/aslaksen/gem-projects/hm/Chinese_Calendar.pdf

²⁶³ <https://www2.ihp.sinica.edu.tw/file/1097kaBVwNb.pdf>

²⁶⁴ “1. Examining into antiquity, (we find that) the Tî Yâo[1] was styled Fang-hsün[2]. He was reverential, intelligent, accomplished, and thoughtful, --naturally and without effort. He was sincerely courteous, and capable of (all) complaisance. The bright (influence of –these qualities) was felt through the four quarters (of the land), and reached to (heaven) above and (earth) beneath....

2. He commanded the Hsîs and Hos[3], in reverent accordance with (their observation of) the wide heavens, to calculate and delineate (the movements and appearances of) the sun, the moon, the stars, and the zodiacal spaces, and so to deliver respectfully the seasons to be observed by the people.” Shi King, Book of Thang, Canon of Yao, translated by Legge

²⁶⁵ https://scholar.princeton.edu/sites/default/files/mkern/files/canon_of_yao.pdf

²⁶⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Roman_calendar

²⁶⁷ <http://www.historyworld.net/wrldhis/PlainTextHistories.asp?ParagraphID=bvt>

²⁶⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/science/Egyptian-calendar>

²⁶⁹ <https://www.infoplease.com/calendar-holidays/calendars/history-calendar>

<p>Enormous earthwork calendars but also...</p>	<p>Great Serpent Mound, Ohio</p>	<p>Highly religious agricultural worship; obsession with fertility.</p> <p>The implication of the mainstream was that worship of the fertility goddess²⁷⁰ (with no apparent tie to a greater Saturn/Creator worship offered²⁷¹) required superstitious belief but scientific endeavor.²⁷²</p>
<p>Incredibly precise sundials and water clocks²⁷³, which are no longer accurate; from same era as antikythera and other devices</p>	<p>Water clocks in Mesopotamia appear to have changed to reflect a 365 year²⁷⁴ India as well²⁷⁵ Egypt²⁷⁶ and China²⁷⁷ appear to use a different kind of water clock after a time (perhaps to change rate, or to improve precision?)</p>	<p>More obsession, but inexplicable technological development considering the inability to explore most of the world.</p> <p>[A similar issue is how the mainstream proposes to explain the many noted precisions^{278 279} of the Great Pyramid, but with primitive knowledge and technology.]</p>
<p>Megalithic architecture, in general</p>		<p>Blind religious worship and slavery The pyramid of Qin Shihuangdi was built by slaves but <u>abandoned</u> the moment of his death. But somehow all of the pyramids of Egypt were built via slavery. Gobekli Tepe, like Egypt is put down to</p>

²⁷⁰ According to all cultures around the world the Mother Goddess' womb was the Cosmic Egg of the Creator, where he "seeded himself" and she was his wife, sister, and daughter. Therefore to have an abundant harvest the king would need to himself reflect the internal balance demonstrated by the Creator. The end of this era (of Atum-Re and his Aten) signaled the end of the balance of divine Male and Female.

²⁷¹ See previously mentioned "Saturn Myth" table by author(credit: D Talbott)

²⁷² This is another example of Postmodern and Post-Enlightenment projectionism onto the past. Because *our time* is "after" the Religious Period (in the Noble West), the belief is that the only means to science is through overcoming superstition. When it comes to analyzing people of the Past, that means everything scientific was essentially lucky calibration, or occasional breakthroughs, whilst the majority of behavior is religious [idolatry]. When in fact the scientific was the aim of the religious. Again: Great Serpent Mound was a scientific endeavor to record important **new** information, history, and to obey the new Order of things (hence the solstice and lunar information encoded). It probably was, in fact, a religiously symbolic behavior but not as we see religion. Probably more how Muslims see religion: all encompassing. The location was also almost certainly not accidentally chosen.

²⁷³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Water_clock

²⁷⁴ https://www.jstor.org/stable/41668444?seq=1#page_scan_tab_contents

²⁷⁵ https://www.academia.edu/2097773/Measuring_time_in_Mesopotamia_and_ancient_India

²⁷⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0305440386900257>

²⁷⁷ "Joseph Needham speculated that the introduction of the outflow clepsydra to China, perhaps from Mesopotamia, occurred as far back as the 2nd millennium bc, during the Shang Dynasty, and at the latest by the 1st millennium bc. By the beginning of the Han Dynasty, in 202 bc, the outflow clepsydra was gradually replaced by the inflow clepsydra, which featured an indicator rod on a float" Sic, Ibid.

Note - the time of the Mars/Kali cataclysm was ~670 BCE whereas the Exodus cataclysm which would have actually changed the calendar was ~1,600 BCE (Author, using Velikovskian model)

²⁷⁸

<https://www.ancient-origins.net/ancient-places-africa-opinion-guest-authors/mathematical-encoding-great-pyramid-002323>

²⁷⁹ <http://blog.world-mysteries.com/mystic-places/the-precision-engineered-great-pyramid/>

	Gobekli Tepe ²⁸⁰ , Turkey	an “obsession with Death” and one’s mortality. ²⁸¹
Cometary astronomical obsession	<p>Gobekli Tepe Stele (Credit: Getty images/NatGeo)</p>	<p>Minor plagues and droughts associated with eclipses and comets, for no reason given except when the cases result in impact</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greeks^{282 283} • Chinese²⁸⁴ • Sumerians^{285 286} • Aborigines²⁸⁷ • Tepe Period²⁸⁸ • European Fears²⁸⁹ • India does not mention comets so much as “weapons of the gods” such as those in the Mahabharata’s destruction of Dvaraka
Carolina Bays	<p>Carolina Bays</p>	<p>Sinkholes, essentially; or ice-errata from comet impact</p> <p>See Introduction and Figures 3-13 See Table 3</p>
Parallel symbolism in Stone, Bronze and Iron Age cultures; even across continents and oceans	The greater part of evidence is seen in previous tables and in the Appendix of “On the Origins of Religions”; here shown is the concentric circle with rays glyph/earthwork, which is	No explanation (Atlantis refused) In a related discussion the Celtic Cross and the connection to the worldwide belief in a Morning Star/Evening Star is also not discussed. The reader should try to guess the

²⁸⁰ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2017/06/skulls-cult-turkey-archaeology-neolithic-gobekli/>

Skull cult? Not likely.

²⁸¹ People today do many things to deal with mortality: drugs, therapy, thrill-seeking, religion... but they never build megalithic structures. All the cases of religious/megalithic architecture the author can think of that is modern always have more complex and/or positive values to them. It would be a mistake to assume motivations (ie, programming) were so different at that time.

²⁸² <https://www.space.com/9116-halley-comet-spotted-ancient-greeks.html>

²⁸³ <http://www.newsweek.com/when-comet-flew-through-ancient-evenings-170630>

²⁸⁴ <http://deepimpact.umd.edu/science/comets-cultures.html>

²⁸⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=66QAnQXgVnU>

²⁸⁶ <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/sodom-and-gomorrah-destroyed-by-a-comet-say-astronomers-1275763.html>

²⁸⁷ Ancient Destructions: 1491AD <http://www.mungoflix.com/mungoflix/ancient-destructions/>

²⁸⁸ <http://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-4432554/Stone-carvings-confirm-comet-hit-Earth-13-000-years-ago.html>

²⁸⁹ <https://www.mpg.de/research/comets-cultural-history>

	<p>worldwide. The current sun (Sol) never looks like this.</p>	
<p>Repetitive glyph morphology especially...</p>	<p>The issue of this repeating star and solar glyph imagery is simply not dealt with by the mainstream.</p> <p>Big Turtle Rockshelter, KY Credit: Coy et al...²⁹¹</p>	<p>No explanation specifically (Aliens refused; diffusionism resisted, ala Clovis First/land bridge)</p> <p>Consider at right: The “Concentric Circle glyph” It is neither a circle, nor merely concentric. The center is bass relief, and as perfectly hemispherical as can be found after hundreds of years of weathering. The outside is an uneven <i>hexagon</i>.²⁹²</p>
<p>Thereonthrop/chimera epoch of art (even non-animal)</p>	<p>Khakassia, Siberia</p>	<p>Early Stone Age entheogenic use (saying this <i>plausible</i> theory is mainstream is being generous, the vast majority of archaeologists have incredibly fanciful ideas about the superstitious beliefs of Natives around the world, even when they turn out right. See: Dogon and the Dog-Star)</p>

²⁹⁰ Mayan

²⁹¹ Although Coy & Fuller are not mainstream archaeologists, reading their Introduction it is made clear that their work was heavily edited and influenced by the mainstream. Were the rock art names chosen for them? Some are ridiculously far off.

²⁹² In the D Talbott “Saturn Myth” model, a collinear rotation is preferred. But this formation indicates either a plasma discharge, or more succinctly a *coplanar* rotation above the Saturnian pole, where site of the hexagon would have been clear and alignment, perhaps with Mars or Venus, would have been **spectacular** and worth recording in bass relief.

Use of conductive materials in pyramid building	Gold or Electrum ²⁹³ Benben ²⁹⁴ 295 Quartz casing stones ²⁹⁶ Piezoelectricity ²⁹⁷ is a fundamental and known property of quartz ²⁹⁸ , which can cause light disturbances at night or birds to fall out of the sky. Standing waves have been allegedly observed over conical hills, mountains, and pyramids (natural or otherwise) ²⁹⁹	Pure vanity of Middle Kingdom pharaohs There is seriously no other explanation provided. Not even a structural one. There are some good theories to suggest the pyramids were built in phases ³⁰⁰ , and the casing stones were the last thing done.
Widespread Mesopotamian Destruction of entire cities and...	Sumerian Tablet that predicted Sodom's destruction 	Droughts, warfare, and minor floods; however nothing cataclysmic (Uniformitarian only) In recent years this has softened quite a bit. For example it is now widely accepted amongst geologists that the Channeled Scablands ³⁰¹ were produced when an ice-rock dam broke at Lake Missoula and created one of the largest waterfalls in human times. ³⁰² Also, see: Burckle Crater
Presence of radioactive materials and spherules on site	Sodom ³⁰³ 304 305 Mohenjo Daro ³⁰⁶ 307 308 vs. ³⁰⁹ Related: vitrification ³¹⁰ 311 312	No explanation, perhaps minor meteorite explosions, ala Tunguska

²⁹³ *“Electrum is a naturally occurring alloy of gold and silver, with trace amounts of copper and other metals. It has also been produced artificially, and is often known as **green gold**. The ancient Greeks called it 'gold' or 'white gold', as opposed to 'refined gold'. Its colour ranges from pale to bright yellow, depending on the proportions of gold and silver.”*

[sic] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electrum>

²⁹⁴ <https://www.ancient-origins.net/artifacts-other-artifacts/mythical-benben-stone-landing-site-egyptian-god-atum-006513>

²⁹⁵ <http://robertbauval.co.uk/articles/articles/DE14.html>

²⁹⁶ <https://www.cheops-pyramide.ch/khufu-pyramid/casing-stones.html>

²⁹⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Piezoelectricity>

²⁹⁸ <https://www.explainthatstuff.com/piezoelectricity.html>

²⁹⁹ <https://www.express.co.uk/news/weird/773789/Bosnian-Pyramid-Nikola-Tesla-standing-waves-aliens>

³⁰⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iktAUyOaX8s>

³⁰¹ <https://news.nationalgeographic.com/2017/03/channeled-scablands/>

³⁰² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Missoula_Floods

³⁰³ <http://blogs.christianpost.com/comets-of-god/human-remains-found-at-sodom-16700/>

³⁰⁴ <https://aleteia.org/2018/01/22/is-this-the-site-where-sodom-once-stood/>

³⁰⁵

<http://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-3270999/Has-Biblical-city-Sodom-Monstrous-site-Jordan-matches-descriptions-area-destroyed-God.html>

³⁰⁶ <https://www.indiavivine.org/8000-year-old-indian-city-irradiated-by-atomic-blast/>

³⁰⁷ <https://www.eyeofthepsychic.com/bestevidence/>

³⁰⁸ <https://www.ancient-origins.net/ancient-places-asia/mohenjo-daro-massacre-00819>

³⁰⁹ <http://www.jasoncolavito.com/ancient-atom-bombs.html>

³¹⁰ https://www.bibliotecapleyades.net/ancientatomicwar/esp_ancient_atomic_02.htm

³¹¹ A later comet: 356-362CE <https://skeptoid.com/episodes/4326>

³¹² <https://secretsofthesunsects.wordpress.com/2011/12/05/incan-vitrified-stones/>

<p>Driving force of shifting Sea Peoples</p>	<p>The discussion of this is definitely skewed in the direction of smaller catastrophes, and for the most part the author agrees with these answers.³¹³ However, the fact remains that the Mediterranean has greatly changed sea level and much of the land people lived on is now gone. For more information read the author's paper, "Unboxing Atlantis," which contains diagrams specific to this topic.³¹⁴</p>	<p>Droughts, warfare; they are not exactly know who they are or where they came from.</p> <p>There are actually a number of candidates for the "Sea Peoples" and this makes sense. When one's lands are destroyed: go elsewhere. While the Hebrews were leaving Egypt to go North, the Amalekites were leaving Arabia to go West, and they crossed in Sinai, and had war.³¹⁵</p>
<p>Origin of Sahara and "Desert Belt"</p> <p>The truth is that there is no explanation currently for how the Sahara Savannah turned into hundreds of feet thick of sand, across an entire continent. And no one wants to talk about it, either, including from the EU, Hancock et al..., Sitchin-Donakin et al..., camps. It is a major problem. Though Wal Thornhill has mentioned it, and some of the EU Geology catastrophists, nobody has specifically done a study comparing the Sahara sands with the Martian samples. The author did a brief sampling, but results are not written, as of yet.</p>	<p>Eye of the Sahara - Biggest Thunderbolt strike</p> <p>Credit: theecologist.org</p>	<p>"Desertification" (cyclical definition) due to unexplained shifting climate forces.</p> <p>Sometimes a comet is blamed, sometimes Precession/wobble, sometimes humans.</p> <p>The simplicity of the answer is obvious: the desert belt was dumped on Earth. However, not by the moon, but by Venus and then Mars.</p> <p>The shift in climate was first caused by the Moon and the Younger Dryas. The two events go hand in hand. A mutually supportive discordant cycle.</p>
<p>Tilt of Lake Titicaca³¹⁶</p> <p>The testimony of the Uru People³¹⁷ is that this most definitely happened, and in the remote past.</p> <p>Overall the area has uplifted about 4 km within the last</p>	<p>Credit: NephiCode³²⁰</p>	<p>Massive regional earthquake</p> <p>The most interesting thing is that the Chinese said the same thing about the Taklamakan Desert³²¹, which also looks like a former lake that was emptied out.³²²</p>

³¹³ "1177 B.C.: The Year Civilization Collapsed: Turning Points in Ancient History," E Cline, 2015

³¹⁴ [3] Figure 13

³¹⁵ Bible, "Ages in Chaos," I Velikovsky, 1952

³¹⁶ <https://www.britannica.com/place/Lake-Titicaca>

³¹⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uru_people

³²⁰ <http://nephicode.blogspot.com/2016/10/the-flood-that-destroyed-tiwanaku-part-i.html>

³²¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taklamakan_Desert

³²² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taklamakan_Desert#/media/File:Taklamakan.png

11,000-12,000 years. ^{318 319}		
Geoglyph-Earthwork North/South America parallelism; specifically circle+square offset arrangement	See Table 2 and “On the Origins of Religions” Appendix B See also Dave Talbott’s “Discourses of an Alien Sky” ³²³	Unexplained (Amazonian earthworks only recently found) Note the Chinese saying, “Heaven is round, Earth is square,” ³²⁴ which has been interpreted by sinologists and Taoists in a large milieu of psychological and philosophical meanings. ³²⁵
Biblical Exodus/Ipuwer Egyptian text cataclysmic testimony	See “Ages in Chaos” series by Immanuel Velikovsky. Ignoring a hypothesis is not a rebuttal. The conjunction of the Ipuwer text ³²⁶ with the Book of Exodus is not uncanny, it is in fact reflective of a historical event. ³²⁷	Unexplained (Velikovsky refused; Deluge exclusion principle) Again: refusing to deal with a hypothesis is not a valid scientific rebuttal. As for Carl Sagan’s response to Velikovsky, it has been itself, roundly debunked. ^{328 329}

³¹⁸ [3] Table 2

³¹⁹ Ibid.

³²³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=svfWvSHh4AY&list=PLwOAYhBuU3UeFB-ygaH63Seg6r6C_dtqB

³²⁴ <https://www.orthodoxartsjournal.org/heaven-round-earth-square/>

³²⁵ <https://www.purplemotes.net/2010/12/05/earths-a-square-heaven-a-circle/>

³²⁶ <http://www.reshafim.org.il/ad/egypt/texts/ipuwer.htm>

³²⁷ <https://ohr.edu/838>

³²⁸ <http://immanuelvelikovsky.com/Svbasic.htm>

³²⁹ <http://www.procars-clean.com/carl-sagan-and-immanuel-velikovsky-english.pdf>

Table 42 - Proposed vectors for the End of Eastern Cultures³³⁰

pre-Archaic	> 12,800 YBP	Early cavemen and Travelers	Younger Dryas cataclysm (moon)
Tepe Period transition	12,800-8,000 YBP	Atlantean remnants	End of Saturnian Age
Archaic	9,000-5,000 YBP ³³¹	PaleoIndians and Europeans ³³²	End of Jovian Age Deluge?
Allegewi First Phase	5,500-3,600 YBP	Atlantean or Amazonia remnants	Exodus Cataclysm (Venus) & Plague
Allegewi Second Phase	3,600-1,700 YBP	Allegewi Loyalists	Mars & 300 CE comet
Hopewell	3,600-1,000 YBP	Traveler ³³³ -Indian mixing	Waning of the gods
Woodland Era	5,500-500 YBP	American Indian arrivals	Disease and warfare?
Miss. Culture	2,600-500 YBP	Hopewell-traveler mixing	Disease ³³⁴ and flood ³³⁵
Cahokia Dominance	1,700-500 YBP	Welsh/Celtic mixing	Warfare with Lakota
Ft. Ancient	1,300-300 YBP	Hopewell remnant +American Indian	Warfare, disease, depopulation
Mandan Remnants	500-200 YBP	Cahokians and other Miss. survivors	Smallpox and warfare with Lakota
Historic Indians	400YBP-present	Displaced survivors of smallpox and warfare	Warfare, mixing with white pioneer populations

³³⁰ [16] p.31

³³¹ Author defined dates

³³² See: "Windover Bog Bodies - European?," Ancient American, September 2018

<http://www.ancientworldreview.com/2016/10/the-windover-bog-bodies-european.html>

³³³ Traveler as in from Asia, Asia minor, MesoAmerica or Europe

³³⁴ Possibly smallpox introduced by the Chinese in 1529 or thereabouts, as per the Nickless hypothesis, see "Chasing Dragons: the True History of the Piasa." This hypothesis has several merits which will be discussed in a later paper For more information, see, "To the Gates of Fengtu" by Laurie Bonner-Nickless which is a translation of this account.

³³⁵ <https://www.nature.com/news/floods-might-have-doomed-prehistoric-american-city-1.17470>

Table 43 - Logic Summary for Glyphs and Earthworks; conclusions otherwise offered when possible.³³⁶

Issue	Illogicism	Solution Offered
Turkey "Tracks" (see Plate L5, Figure 20)	One-legged turkeys, hopping along? With no width to the feet?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Awen Symbol; ie from Diffusionist peoples (travelers) 2) Conjunction of Earth, Moon, Mars, and Venus or of Earth, Venus, Jupiter and Mars or Saturn^{337 338} 3) Might be the same thing, anciently.
Asymmetric Turkey Foot and Eagle Mound center (see Figures 16-18) Asymmetric Alligator Awen (see Figure 19-20)	Nothing offered by mainstream (unnoticed)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Different angle view of the sky than Old World Awen³³⁹ counterparts 2) Different era, when conjunction was failing 3) Combination of the two
Bear Print (see Figure 22)	Doesn't look like a bear print ³⁴⁰	Jupiter and 4 Galilean moons + Mars in rare conjunction
Left foot glyphs (see Figures 24-25)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) No solution offered as to out of proportion amount of randomly arranged left feet (vs. right) 2) Left feet are anatomically incorrect³⁴¹ 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Same conjunction as seen in "Bear Print" glyph 2) Different conjunction, similar to that of Awen symbol, but different angles or time periods
Alligator Mound ³⁴² & Turtle Glyph "5 legs" (see Figures 19-20, G & S Plates)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The Alligator mound doesn't look like an alligator and reptiles do not have a 5th leg on their right flank. 2) No alligators above Florida naturally³⁴³ (nor above Georgia) 3) Alligators would not have 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A further stage of the conjunction that led to the catastrophe 2) Part of the Alligator mound shape is the basic Eagle Mound plasmaglyph, but it's been added to to include Earth and Moon. 3) The turtle glyph was

³³⁶ [16] pp.38-40

³³⁷ It is no accident that the same 5 planets and our moon come up repeatedly, again and again in every culture. It would be no different for the Allegewi-Hopewell. The obsessions with Draco, Pleiades, Ursa Major, Polaris, etc... may be rather modern by comparison.

³³⁸ In the Eagle and Alligator mounds in particular, the bulbous shape of celestial bodies surrounded by plasma sheaths is just discernable or imaginable (at least as a possibility).

³³⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Awen>

³⁴⁰ Not to anyone trained in tracking. But if it were a foot, notice it is the **left** print.

³⁴¹ The instep (medial) should be curved (arched) and the lateral aspect of the foot straight, not the other way around.

³⁴² Ohio. http://www.ohiohistorycentral.org/w/Alligator_Mound

³⁴³ <http://www.georgiasfossils.com/uploads/3/7/6/1/37616615/alligator-thermal-enclave.jpg?1467758644>

	been a power animal for the Allegewi-hopewell ³⁴⁴	possibly re-imagined as a turtle god or spirit while the alligator mound was reimagined as a lizard.
Minora glyphs & Mound (see Figures 40-41)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Nothing offered but.... 2) Most definitely not Jewish in origins³⁴⁵ 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Evidence of Jewish “Lost Ten Tribes”³⁴⁶ travelers in Siberia, America, and Sweden. (Diffusion theory) 2) Another plasmaglyph formation seen around the world. 3) Replicates a strengthening current-syphon³⁴⁷ prior to a massive discharge.
Concentric Sun Glyphs (and spiral suns) (see Figures 32-34,36-38)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Native just love spirals 2) They were testing out their basic cognitive art skills, like Kindergarten students (though we are talking most likely adult males) 3) No explanation for concentric suns offered 4) The author will donate a theory: a sun halo in the sky (through cirrus clouds) and a Moon Dog³⁴⁸. However, both only provide a single ring, while these concentric circles are always multiple rings³⁴⁹. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Plasma shells (sheaths) 2) Planet rings of Jupiter and Saturn 3) Paths of orbits of large moons observed³⁵⁰ 4) Glowing plasmaspheres (Spheres of Heaven) for Venus and Mars³⁵¹ 5) Electric Comets passing near to each other³⁵²
Henges and C-henges and glyphs (see Figures 26,35,37,39,42-46, S & P plates)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The henge calendar is a very unsophisticated and oversized way of doing something that could also 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) All the henges are explainable via Birkeland current plasma arc discharges³⁵³

³⁴⁴ Nor would the Rat Snake, the only egg-eating snake in Eastern US.

³⁴⁵ Apparently the idea that Hebrew/Jewish people could sail seems impossible. The author can only mention the Victorian anti-semitism of Europe in the formation days of early Archaeology, and shrugs his shoulders. There appears to be no logical reason why not. It’s just “because.”

³⁴⁶ Here the author offers that they possibly went in ten different directions. But the author does not think the mound and glyphs are Jewish.

³⁴⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VAwnxlc0-6E>

³⁴⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Moon_dog

³⁴⁹ Anywhere from 2 to 15, with some exceptions no doubt.

³⁵⁰ The author feels this is unlikely as there appears to be no other attempt at pathway representation in aboriginal astro-archaeology. Also, there are plenty of discussions of the Aten (circular enclosure) and the Khu(t)/henhenu (circular orbit) in worldwide glyphology, and these do not refer to orbit alone but to a halo-like glow around the cosmic egg (Khat/shentit); Translations of the ancient Egyptian are by D Talbot

³⁵¹ [4], see Spheres of Heaven and Spheres of Earth. An excellent demonstration of these spheres in motion can be found in this hyperlapse video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oagszCmJLpU>

³⁵² The author feels this is highly unlikely because the glyphs do not display dynamism.

³⁵³ Essentially co-axial, concentric circle discharges. See [5], section on Birkeland Currents, pp 28-32

	<p>have been done at a smaller and more practical scale</p> <p>2) The C-henge is explained with adding and entrance... but then why wouldn't regular henges (circles) have entrances?</p> <p>3) Sometimes they have four entrances, sometimes 8</p>	<p>2) C-henges are explained via crater-rim discharge at end of arc stroke</p> <p>3) Multiple entrances are added after the one discharge, in order to honor the Celtic cross shape sun glyph, which was the same Midnight Sun seen everywhere, but now remembered in antiquity as the power of the Creator God (Tiawara)</p>
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Table 44 - Summary of Figure 69

(1) A = 0.89	B = 0.51	C = 0.58	D = 0.043
(2) A = 0.63	B = 0.43	C = 0.44	D = 0.045
(3) A/D = .363/.038 = 14.8	(4) .495/.055 = 9.34	(5) .378/.029 = 13.03	(6) .476/.029 = 16.4
(7) .580/.040 = 14.5	Avg ³⁵⁴ A=.76, B=.47, C=.51, D=.044	Avg A/D (2 samples) = 17.27	Avg A/D (7 samples ³⁵⁵) = 14.68

³⁵⁴ 2 samples

³⁵⁵ More samples might be taken but their differences are inscrutable. The point here is to show the A/D ratio is not accidental and is both visible and statistically relevant.

Table 45 - Cosmic Mountain Correspondences Worldwide³⁵⁶

³⁵⁶ [16] p.94

Table 46 - Unavoidable Assumptions in Vajra Calculations³⁵⁷

Constant moon and Io size	Constant EMF properties and physical laws	Similarity of Current Solar wind with Saturnian and Jovian winds
Constant Earth - no EGE ³⁵⁸	Linearized Lightning models ³⁵⁹	Even crystal lattice and charge distribution in Earth's soils ³⁶⁰
Earth = ground (0 V)	Single Phase power (no 3-phase or 6-phase ³⁶¹)	Constant permeability of free space ³⁶²
Atmosphere negligibility for classical interpretations ³⁶³	Single Body interaction (moon)	Equivalence of negative and positive stepped bolts ³⁶⁴
Equivalent destructive power for origin & destinations	Single impedance values	Non-surge or pump behavior ³⁶⁵
Single strike (no repeat strokes)	Ignore wet-dry soil/air conditions	Straight or curvi-linear arc paths
Glow arc mode for classical model	Dark mode until ionospheric cascade for Birkeland model	Ignore neutron sequestration ³⁶⁶ and general radiation effects
Jupiter-Earth position offset ³⁶⁷	Assumed ranges of power scales ³⁶⁸	Constant Gravity - that is, negligible, non-relativistic

³⁵⁷ [16] p.106

³⁵⁸ Although we have plenty of evidence for the Expanding-Growing-Earth, the current Earth size will be assumed.

³⁵⁹ As opposed to parabolic growth or hyperbolic limitations/asymptotes.

³⁶⁰ Obviously limestone and granite and sandstone, etc... will not distribute charge evenly. Some will saturate faster, and some will feed the charge into the HEME (Hollow-Electromagnetic-Earth) more quickly, preventing widespread Step Potential.

³⁶¹ Saturn's hexagonal pole may be therefore discounted, and Jupiter's octagonal pole, in favor of counter-rotating cylinders.

³⁶² We must, especially for the classical model, assume an empty vacuum. Obviously this is not correct at all, given the known Magnetohydrodynamic measurements from the MMR mission. So, in reality, the same positions and all other things the same, some vajra would be heightened and some would be buffered.

³⁶³ Examples of the changes in lightning potential based on atmospheric elevation can be found here: <http://bit.ly/2CrDgFA>

³⁶⁴ Positive strokes, on Earth, can be 3x as powerful as negative strokes, but only occur 1/10 of the time, as per Uman

³⁶⁵ Pumping is similar to repeat strokes, but in this case a magnitude or several higher in charge syphoning.

³⁶⁶ Artifacts (OOPArts) and certain archaeological sites have been found with impossibly low carbon-14 values. Given the Structured Atom hypothesis (see [6]), in arc modes, it is possible that the electrons in the "neutron" (positron-electron duo) will have been sequestered, reducing the C14 values.

³⁶⁷ Jupiter has 2×10^4 the size and power of the magnetosphere to the Earth, but receives only 4% the solar wind strength. Therefore, considering the assumptions in the next note, the relative position of these bodies will be offset/equivocated.

³⁶⁸ Using [6]. Table 7, some rough assumptions for order of magnitude will be set. For example AGN's operate at 10^{14-15} A, so it will not be possible to have anywhere near this current. Rather, since Earth and Jupiter operate in the 350-600 kA range, a 10^5 A range will be assumed. In this case an average between the two.

Table 47 - Vajra Calculations using Coulomb's Law & Capacitance^{369 370}

	Full distance	½ distance	⅓ distance	¼ distance
d (m)	3.84E+08	1.92E+08	1.28E+08	9.61E+07
C (F)	3.40E-06	1.70E-06	1.13E-06	8.51E-07
e (F/m)	1.31E+00	3.27E-01	1.45E-01	8.18E-02
V = 20MV/m*d	7.69E+15	3.84E+15	2.56E+15	1.92E+15
E (j)	2.01E+26	2.51E+25	7.42E+24	3.14E+24
E (kC)	4.80E+22	6.00E+21	1.77E+21	7.51E+20
Lightning Bolts	4.02E+16	5.02E+15	1.48E+15	6.29E+14
# Vajra to boil Antarctica ³⁷¹	1.33E+05	1.66E+04	4.90E+03	2.08E+03
<i>Adjusting down (10³)</i>	2.01E+23	2.51E+22	7.42E+21	3.14E+21
<i>E (kC)</i>	4.80E+19	6.00E+18	1.77E+18	7.51E+17
<i>Lightning Bolts</i>	4.02E+13	5.02E+12	1.48E+12	6.29E+11
# Vajra to boil Antarctica	1.33E+02	1.66E+01	4.90E+00	2.08E+00

Table 48 - Vajra Calculations using MHD and Satellite data

	Minimum	Maximum	Avg	Limited
V	1.00E+06	1.00E+08	5.00E+07	2.00E+05
I	2.50E+05	5.00E+08	5.00E+06	6.50E+05
R (space)	4.00E+00	2.00E-01	1.00E+01	3.08E-01
R (soil)	3.00E+07	3.00E+10	1.00E+08	1.00E+08
V (discharge)	7.50E+12	1.50E+19	5.00E+14	6.50E+13
P (V*I)/1000=KW	1.88E+15	7.50E+24	2.50E+18	4.23E+16

“Comparing Table 48 and 49, we see that the voltages hover from 10⁻³ to 10⁴ higher in Table 49. The avg expected voltage to soil is 10⁻¹ than table 10. So the delivery power is *expected* to be about an order of magnitude smaller than in table 10, not 10⁻³. Nevertheless, within reasonability, we are arriving at the “understanding” of what we are dealing with. That is to say from 1.88 exa-watts to 7.5 yolta-watts, with an expected avg of 2.5 zelta-watts, and a assumed limitation of 42.3 exa-watts.” [edited]³⁷²

³⁶⁹ <http://bit.ly/2Qd9ffy> for Spreadsheet

³⁷⁰ [16] p.108

³⁷¹ 1 kC raises 1kg of water from ice to a boil; Antarctica has avg mass of ice of 3.62x10¹⁷ kg

<https://www.wired.com/2016/10/lets-put-water-back-top-antarctica/>

³⁷² [16] p.115

“The average lightning stroke, as per Dwyer & Uman, lasts about 20-30 microseconds. We are assuming here that the Vajras are behaving similarly, although we have previously stated they won’t, and certain sites demonstrate reliable geophysical evidence of prolonged return strokes and charge pumping (to saturation). However, to establish conservative boundaries (because the upper end cannot be known), we will use the 30 microsecond value to calculate, again, the joules and kC:

Table 49 - Energy values at the upper and lower limits

	Minimum	Maximum	Avg	Limited
joules in .3*10 ⁻⁶ s	5.63E+11	2.25E+21	7.50E+14	1.27E+13
E (kC)	1.34E+08	5.38E+17	1.79E+11	3.03E+09
Lightning Bolts	1.13E+02	4.50E+11	1.50E+05	2.54E+03
Upper Boundary (j)	5.63E+15	2.25E+25	7.50E+18	1.27E+17
Lower Boundary (j)	5.63E+08	2.25E+18	7.50E+11	1.27E+10
Avg Limit (j)	5.63E+10	2.25E+20	7.50E+13	1.27E+12

Note - the energy released in Bikini H-bomb was 8 M-ton TNT or $8 \times 10^6 \times 4.184 \times 10^9$ j/ton = 3.3472E+16 j

It’s important not to get hung up on the sigfigs because actual values are incalculable without *in situ* measurement, which is both impossible and unlikely. It’d be deadly at any rate.

So we see that at the lower boundary, such as a small strike sie, we can expect a vajra to be worth 113 or so lightning bolts, while at the upper end, possibly 450 billion bolts, with an average of about 150-250 thousand bolts of typical lightning. This seems far more reasonable than our classical model. Moreover, it demonstrates a new problem: either the event would have to be massively prolonged (as is expected), or some other mechanism would need to be proposed or at least appended to this mechanism for the melting of the ice sheets. The author proposes that the meltdown was caused by four factors:

1. Change in ocean current behavior as HEME and PEC behaviors adapted to SSC changes
2. Change in orbit and tilt, altering slightly the received plasma characteristics, which slightly changed Earth’s own PEC behaviors.
3. Vajra/thunderbolt mechanisms, and sure, some impacts
4. Tectonic heating caused by SSC changes due to shifting positions relative to the sun³⁷³³⁷⁴

Table 50 - Radial Propagation voltages based on Table 48

	V_min	V_max	V_avg	V_limit
100m	1.19E+05	2.39E+08	2.39E+06	3.10E+05
1000m	1.19E+04	2.39E+07	2.39E+05	3.10E+04
10000m	1.19E+03	2.39E+06	2.39E+04	3.10E+03

³⁷³ The author believes the sun was part of the SSC before but its characteristics may have altered, for reasons unknown, rather than merely intercepting the Jovian-Saturnian solar system. Mytho-historical evidence supports both postulates. One thing is for sure, the sun’s color changed, and the sky also changed color as the plasma sheath behaviors altered. The best evidence for this is in the green leafy plant color, which - to the author - is inexplicable because the sun puts out green the most. Also, a great number of people are red-green colorblind, suggesting a lack of adaptive necessity. Lighting may have actually been more muted before, and full of more blue-purple.

³⁷⁴ [16] pp.115-116

“The drop-off in voltage using (5.6) is linear, but in Table 14, we see that according to the 3.5m footprint of the mammoth’s position, it will drop off geometrically, with an imposed limit of potential killing power (again using the smallest Vajra) at 2000-2500 m (over 6,000 feet)

A couple things to note: the current may be deadlier for a human or other small animal, or it may be better, being a smaller step potential. Also, the resistivity of different bodies are different. The author does not know the true resistivity of a Columbian Mammoth, he expects it would be higher than 300hm but perhaps not as high as for a human since elephant species are renowned for sensitive feet with many nerves. Finally, there is the issue of core versus surface spread of the charge of the body. Given that the literature varies in how many mA it takes to stop a heart, the author will assume 10 mA is the safe current (as high as 30 mA may be considered deadly in houses) and then quote the author,

“At a current of 0.04 to 0.06 amperes, asphyxia may occur from prolonged contraction of the chest muscles... From Dalziel (1953) the threshold energy level for fibrillation of the 700 ohm individual... is about 350 j... If we linearly extrapolate to a 70 kilogram human, certainly a questionable extrapolation, the lethal energy is 4410 j.”³⁷⁵

The question arises, what is the lethal energy for a dire wolf, mammoth, mastodon, or ground sloth? The author certainly does not know.”³⁷⁶

Table 51 - Step Potential Calculations for Columbian Mammoth 3.5m footprint

Distances (m)	Voltages	I_ground @ 300ohm (mA)	I_body @ 700 ohm (mA)
100	3,346.37	11,154.56	4,780.53
200	931.85	3,106.16	1,331.21
300	429.90	1,432.99	614.14
400	246.44	821.45	352.05
500	159.53	531.78	227.90
600	111.64	372.13	159.48
700	82.47	274.91	117.82
800	63.40	211.35	90.58
900	50.26	167.53	71.80
1000	40.81	136.05	58.31
2000	10.32	34.41	14.75
3000	4.61	15.35	6.58
4000	2.60	8.65	3.71
5000	1.66	5.54	2.38
10000	0.42	1.39	0.60
100000	0.00	0.01	0.01

³⁷⁵ Ibid. pp 129

³⁷⁶ [16] pp. 123-124

Table 52 - Max and Limited Vajra Voltages and Currents

Voltages	<i>Maximum Vajra</i>		Voltages	<i>Limited Vajra</i>	
	I_ground (mA)	I_body (mA)		I_ground (mA)	I_body (mA)
6,692,736.04	22,309,120.14	9,561,051.49	8,700.56	29,001.86	12,429.37
1,863,695.98	6,212,319.95	2,662,422.84	2,422.80	8,076.02	3,461.15
859,791.22	2,865,970.73	1,228,273.17	1,117.73	3,725.76	1,596.76
492,870.55	1,642,901.85	704,100.79	640.73	2,135.77	915.33
319,066.80	1,063,556.01	455,809.72	414.79	1,382.62	592.55
223,278.98	744,263.27	318,969.97	290.26	967.54	414.66
164,945.29	549,817.63	235,636.13	214.43	714.76	306.33
126,808.88	422,696.27	181,155.54	164.85	549.51	235.50
100,517.64	335,058.81	143,596.63	130.67	435.58	186.68
81,629.50	272,098.32	116,613.57	106.12	353.73	151.60
20,646.41	68,821.37	29,494.87	26.84	89.47	38.34
9,212.01	30,706.71	13,160.02	11.98	39.92	17.11
5,191.88	17,306.26	7,416.97	6.75	22.50	9.64
3,326.70	11,089.00	4,752.43	4.32	14.42	6.18
833.63	2,778.76	1,190.90	1.08	3.61	1.55
8.35	27.85	11.93	0.01	0.04	0.02

“The max powered Vajra remains deadly at 100,000 m (62 miles), which surely a location such as Devil’s Tower+Black Hills would have been quite able to propagate that far, or further, given the soil type³⁷⁷. This would definitely constitute a power worth worshiping (same for Ayer’s Rock, in Australia). But even the limited Vajra has potency out to 3000 - 4000 m (1.86 - 2.48 miles)! That is truly the power of the gods. This supplies us both our vector for selective worldwide extinction (not to mention Younger Dryas mechanism), but explains not only “out of place” geology, but also “out of place” anthropology.”³⁷⁸

³⁷⁷ Please note that the voltages and currents listed are more than sufficient to empower earth removal on a vast scale, and scorching/vaporizing the land, and as noted before, the energy levels are consistent with Bikini sized H-bombs 10¹⁶ j or more.

³⁷⁸ [16] p.125

Table 53 - Weapons of the Gods Names or god who wielded them ³⁷⁹ 380381

	Greece	Babylonian	India [Norse]	Brittain/Celtic	Americas	China [Japan]
<i>Thunder...</i>		Sharur	Vajra [Mjolnir]	Caladbolg	Thunderbird	Jiu-feng (bird)
<i>Spear/Trident</i>	Poseidon		Vel/Trishula Pashupatastra	Lugh/Invincible Gae Bulg		[Ame-no-nuhoko]
<i>Sword</i>	Harpē		Asi Nandaka [Hq̄fuð]	Claíomh-Solais Fragarach Dyrnwyn		Gan Jiang Mo Xie/Ye [Kusanagi]
<i>Archery</i>	Apollo		Pinaka, etc ³⁸²			
<i>Winds</i>	Titans		“Seven Winds”		Jem of Kukulcan	
<i>Tectonics</i>	Titans	Tiamat cracked ½ by Marduk	Sinking of Dwaraka		Lakota Creator-God	
<i>Floods</i>	Titans	Enlil	Missile>sinking of Dwaraka			
<i>Blasts</i>	Titans		Narayanastra Brahmastra	Balor’s Eye	Xiuhcoatl	
<i>Hammer, etc..</i>	Hephaestus	Sharur	Gada Agneyastra ³⁸³		Foot of God (Delaware)	Ruyi Jingu Bang

³⁷⁹ <http://www.ancientpages.com/2015/07/28/10-divine-weapons-of-the-gods/>

³⁸⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_magical_weapons

³⁸¹ <https://tenmania.com/mythological-weapons-ancient-gods/>

³⁸² Arrow of Brahma, Gandiva, Kaundinya, Kodandam, Sharanga, Sharkha, Dhanush, Teen Baan (arrows), Vijaya

³⁸³ <https://www.ancient-code.com/fire-of-the-gods-mythological-weapons-of-the-ancient-past/>

Table 54 - Proper Physics Chronology³⁸⁴

Electricity	Ben Franklin	1751
Gaussian Theory	Carl Gauss	1813
Electromagnetism Unification	Michael Faraday	1831
Doppler Redshift	Hippolyte Fizeau	1848
Maxwell's Equations	James Maxwell	1861-62
Quantized Hypothesis	Ludwig Boltzmann	1877
Photoelectric effect	Heinrich Hertz	1887
Electron Theory	JJ Thomson	1897
Quantum Theory	Max Planck	1900
Relativity theory	Henri Poincare	1900-1904
Mass-energy relation	Henri Poincare	1900
Gravity Waves	Henri Poincare	1905
Special Relativity	Albert Einstein	1905
Photoelectric Effect Explained	Albert Einstein	1905
Birkeland Currents	Kristian Birkeland	1908
Atomic Theory Proved	Ernest Rutherford	1911
Particle-Wave Theory of Atoms and Particles	Niels Bohr	1913
General Relativity	Albert Einstein	1915
Proton discovered	Ernest Rutherford	1919
Quantum Radiation Interaction	Paul Dirac	1920
Quantum Mechanics Codified	Born, Heisenberg, Pauli	1924
Bose-Einstein Condensate	Bose, Einstein	1924
Plasma Cosmology	Irving Langmuir	1927
Big Bang Cosmology	Georges Lemaitre	1927
Missing Matter	Edward Zwicky	1933
Magnetohydrodynamics	Hannes Alfvén	1940
QEM/QED	Bethe to Feynman	1947-1960
Electroweak Theory	JC Ward	1959
Quarks	M Gell-Mann & G Zweig	1964
Black Hole Theory	John Wheeler	1967
Dark Matter	Rubin & Ford	1970
Electric Star Theory	Ralph Juergens ³⁸⁵	1972
QCD	Gross, Wilczek, & Politzer	1973
Axions	Peicci & Quinn	1977
SUSY	Werner Nahm	1978
WIMPs	unclear ³⁸⁶	1980
MOND	Mordehai Milgrom	1982
String Theory	Green & Schwarz	1984
Dark Energy	Friedman ³⁸⁷ or Sivaram ³⁸⁸	1924 or 1986
M Theory	Edward Witten	1995
Intrinsic Redshift	Halton Arp ³⁸⁹	1998

³⁸⁴ Tables 1 and 2 reproduced from [11]; all references in [18] included, as this paper is a follow-up.

³⁸⁵ https://www.velikovsky.info/Ralph_Juergens

³⁸⁶ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/dark-matter-exotic-possibilities/>

³⁸⁷ <http://home.fnal.gov/~skent/early.html>

³⁸⁸ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0809/0809.3364.pdf>

³⁸⁹ https://www.haltonarp.com/articles/intrinsic_redshifts_in_quasars_and_galaxies.pdf

Table 55 - Falsifications

Cosmic Background Radiation	2007 ³⁹² & 2019 ³⁹³
ΛCDM	2010 ³⁹⁴ , 2014 ³⁹⁵
SUSY	2012 ³⁹⁶ - 2017 ³⁹⁷
CDM	2012 ³⁹⁸ , 2015 ³⁹⁹ , 2016 ⁴⁰⁰ - 2018 ^{401 402 403 404}
WIMPs & MACHOs	2017 ⁴⁰⁵
Galaxy Rotation and DM	2017 ^{406 407}
Standard Redshift	2017 ^{408 409 410}
MOND	2018 ^{411 412 413}
Galaxy Rotation and MOND	2018 ⁴¹⁴
Higgs-boson as non-standard Quark	2018 ⁴¹⁵
Dark Energy	2018 ⁴¹⁶
LDM	2018 ^{417 418}
Classical Black Holes	2018 ⁴¹⁹
Accretion Model	2019 ⁴²⁰

³⁹⁰ <http://www.astro.caltech.edu/~george/ay20/ea-wimps-machos.pdf>

³⁹¹ <https://theconversation.com/from-machos-to-wimps-meet-the-top-five-candidates-for-dark-matter-51516>

³⁹² <http://rnas.asj-oa.am/2542/1/73.pdf>

³⁹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p8IKQMEYYLw>

³⁹⁴ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1011.0004>

³⁹⁵ https://astro.uni-bonn.de/~pavel/kroupa_SciLogs.html

³⁹⁶ <http://backreaction.blogspot.com/2016/08/the-lhc-nightmare-scenario-has-come-true.html>

³⁹⁷ <https://www.space.com/39001-dark-matter-doesnt-exist-study-suggests.html>

³⁹⁸ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1204.2546>

³⁹⁹ http://adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/bib_query?arXiv:1406.4860

⁴⁰⁰ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2016arXiv161003854K>

⁴⁰¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.09823.pdf>

⁴⁰² <https://academic.oup.com/mnras/article/476/3/3124/4875952>

⁴⁰³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1807.07113.pdf>

⁴⁰⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.04817.pdf>

⁴⁰⁵ <https://phys.org/news/2017-12-machos-dead-wimps-no-shows-simps.html>

⁴⁰⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.10706.pdf>

⁴⁰⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08843.pdf>

⁴⁰⁸ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1805.03298.pdf>

⁴⁰⁹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.09409>

⁴¹⁰ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.03888.pdf>

⁴¹¹ <https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/falsifications-and-constraints-due-to-gw-measurements.929254/>

⁴¹² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1804.04167.pdf>

⁴¹³ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1809/1809.09019.pdf>

⁴¹⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1801.09304.pdf>

⁴¹⁵ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-06130-9>

⁴¹⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.05027.pdf>

⁴¹⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.10543.pdf>

⁴¹⁸ Several, see previous papers to the series

⁴¹⁹ Ibid.

⁴²⁰ Ibid.

Table 56 - Progression of Related Words with Etymology⁴²¹

Character	人 ren - man	大 da - big	天 tian- Heaven	太 tai - Highest or Greatest	灾 zai - disaster
Etymology	Person ⁴²²	Large Man	God/Celestial	Extreme, Very, too much	Calamity, catastrophe
Oracle Script				n/a	n/a
Seal/Bronze				n/a	
Stroke	The original oracles look alternately like an old man bent, or like a lightning bolt, and may have reflected God	Clearly the Great Man plasmaglyph, again reflecting God	The modern form shows “one above the Great” but seals show the Great Man glyph and the Creator glyph with Crescent Ship	The dangling stroke is a phallus; see Da	Compound 灾 from fire-huo 火 huǒ and building-mian 宀 mián. Meaning: dolmen (take cover)

Table 57 - Thunder God Characters⁴²³

Script	Chinese & Meaning	Etymology	Oracle or Seal
Takemikazuchi	Brave-Awful-Possessing		
建	Jian - Build/Erect	from road-long-yin 廾 yǐn and brush-and-paper-yu 聿 yù (rem+ 廾 carpenters square).	

⁴²¹ [22] p.8

⁴²² All Etymology from <http://hanziyuan.net> L=Liushutong; B=Bronze; J=Shang Oracle bone; S = Seal

⁴²³ [22] pp.9-10

御

Yu - ride/chariot

from road-left-chi 𠂔 chī and related phonetic drive-chariot-xie 卸 xiè.

Compare with Phaethon
Note: asymmetric “bird track”

雷

Lei - thunder

from rain-yu 雨 yǔ and (rem- 田 tián) from phonetic three-fields-lei 轟 léi. Three fields, but four shown
Note: prayer to planets under plasmoid Great God

武

Wu - martial

from foot-forward-zhi 止 zhǐ and weapon-ge 戈 gē.

甕

Weng - earthen jar

from building-tile-wa 瓦 wǎ

and phonetic harmony-yong 雍 yōng
Compare with Ra; note B05632 different sizes of circles

槌

Chui - hammer or beat

from tree-wood-mu 木 mù and phonetic pursue-zhui 追 zhuī.

Compare right with (9)

Raijin

Thunder God

雷

Lei - Thunder

from rain-yu 雨 yǔ and (rem- 田 tián) from phonetic three-fields-lei 轟 léi.

Compare right with (2)

<p>神</p>	<p>Shen - spirit or god</p> <p>(- 工 the sound of thunder) (- 弓 the shape of lightning) (- 口 the sound of thunder) (- lightning as in in 電) (- lightning implies god 申 神)</p>	<p>from altar-shi 示 shì</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 100px; height: 100px;"></div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; width: 100px; height: 100px;"></div> </div> <p>and phonetic lightning-god-shen 申 shēn Literally: praying at an altar of thunder god; also: yin-yang Showing: plasma movement</p>	
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Yokozuna

Horizontal Rope

<p>横</p>	<p>Heng - crossbeam</p> <p>Containing both the thunder god, lightning, and the weapon/power</p>	<p>rom tree-wood-mu 木 mù and phonetic yellow-sun-huang 黄黄 huáng</p>	
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綱

Gang - rope

(literally depicting the
alignment of two bodies
producing comets and
thunderbolts)

from single-thread-mi 纆 纆 纆 mi
and
phonetic mountain ridge-gang 岡
岡 gāng
simp 纲.

Table 58 - Comparisons of X/Y ratios of 3 stele for Figures 113-115⁴²⁴

	Ramesses Stele	Ramesses II	Chia Stele	Average
X	0.4852	0.799	0.861	0.715
Y	0.393	0.694	0.692	0.593
X:Y	1.23	1.15	1.24	1.21
Stand_Dev	5.11%			

Table 59 - Solar, Jovian, and Saturnian Comparisons and Standard Deviations⁴²⁵

	Sun (km)⁴²⁶	Jupiter⁴²⁷	Saturn⁴²⁸	Ratio J:S
X	1,391,982.8	142,984	120,536	1.186234818
Y	1,391,972.8	133,709	108,728	1.229756824
X:Y	1.000007184	1.069367058	1.10860128	
C_X		0.259	0.2475	1.046464646
C_Y		0.245	0.224	1.09375
C X:Y		1.057142857	1.104910714	
Stand_dev		0.86%	0.26%	
Avg C & Real		1.063254958	1.106755997	
Stand_dev vs. Stele		10.38%	7.30%	

⁴²⁴ [24] p.4

⁴²⁵ [24] p.5

⁴²⁶ <https://www.space.com/17001-how-big-is-the-sun-size-of-the-sun.html>

⁴²⁷ <https://space-facts.com/jupiter-diameter/>

⁴²⁸ <https://nineplanets.org/saturn.html>

Table 60 - Runic for Gold and Iron vs. Chinese⁴²⁹

	Chinese ⁴³⁰ 金	Khumry	Coelbren ^{431 432}	Ogam ⁴³³	Futhark ⁴³⁴
Gold					
Golden					
Iron					
True 真 (Real)					

⁴²⁹ [28] p.35

⁴³⁰ Each row is a different script, all for Jin

⁴³¹ <https://www.omniglot.com/conscripts/coelbren.htm>

⁴³² <https://deriv.nls.uk/dcn23/7661/76612002.23.pdf>

⁴³³ <https://ogham.co/>

⁴³⁴ <https://www.vikingrune.com/rune-converter/>

⁴³⁵ There is no y or w in Ogam

Table 61: Segment Ratios and Standard Deviation

<i>Segments</i>	<i>(1)</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>(2)</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>(3)</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>Stan_dev_rat</i>
AB	0.2989	1.064458689	0.248	0.99638409	0.3361	0.9885294118	4.18%
BC	0.2808	1	0.2489	0.9995983936	0.34	0.9577464789	2.43%
CD	0.2808	0.9996440014	0.249	1	0.355	0.9997183892	0.02%
DE	0.2809	0.9243172096	0.249	1.02892562	0.3551	1.00028169	5.41%
EF	0.3039	0.9589775955	0.242	1.039072563	0.355	1.064467766	5.51%
FG	0.3169	1.103028194	0.2329	0.964389234	0.3335	0.9840660962	7.50%
GH	0.2873	1.011619718	0.2415	1.069530558	0.3389	0.9935502785	3.97%
HA	0.284	0.950150552	0.2258	0.910483871	0.3411	1.014876525	5.27%
Triangular							
AC	0.4858	1.62529274	0.4041	1.629435484	0.5711	1.699196668	4.15%
AD	0.6969	2.331549013	0.5751	2.318951613	0.852	2.534959833	12.12%
AE	0.6913	2.31281365	0.591	2.383064516	0.8298	2.468908063	7.82%
Vert:Horiz							
CG	0.6841	0.9895848402	0.5807	0.982571912	0.79	0.9520366353	2.00%
Cross							
DH	0.8305	1.023600241	0.6295	1.267831612	0.9599	1.010521929	14.49%
BF	0.8501		0.7981		0.97		

“Please note the ratio for HA is in reference to AB; the ratios for Triangulation are all in reference to AB. The ratio for Vert:Horiz is in relation to AE”⁴³⁶

⁴³⁶ [30] pp.12-17

Table 62: Table of Segment Ratio Averages, etc.

<i>Avg of Figures</i>	<i>Avg Ratio of Avg of Figures</i>	<i>Avg of Ratios</i>	<i>Stand_dev_Avgs</i>	<i>Avg of Avgs</i>
0.2943333333	1.01529263	1.016457397	0.08%	1.015875013
0.2899	0.9829339964	0.9857816241	0.20%	0.9843578103
0.2949333333	0.9997740113	0.9997874635	0.00%	0.9997807374
0.295	0.9823509824	0.9845081732	0.15%	0.9834295778
0.3003	1.01992528	1.020839308	0.06%	1.020382294
0.2944333333	1.017978564	1.017161175	0.06%	1.017569869
0.2892333333	1.019743801	1.024900185	0.36%	1.022321993
0.2836333333	0.9636466591	0.9585036493	0.36%	0.9610751542
0.487	1.654586636	1.651308297	0.23%	1.652947467
0.708	2.405436014	2.395153486	0.73%	2.40029475
0.7040333333	2.39195923	2.388262076	0.26%	2.390110653
0.6849333333	0.9728706027	0.9747311292	0.13%	0.9738008659
0.8066333333	1.081945535	1.100651261	1.32%	1.091298398
0.8727333333				

Note same rows as Table 61

Table 63: Jovian Ratios and Standard Deviations from Averages in Table 2

<i>Jupiter</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>Standev with Avgs</i>
0.613	1.01322314	0.19%
0.605	0.9280564504	3.98%
0.6519	1.011167985	0.81%
0.6447	1.041686864	4.12%
0.6189	0.9823809524	2.69%
0.63	0.9331950822	5.97%
0.6751	1.048129172	1.82%
0.6441	1.050734095	6.34%
1.1099	1.810603589	11.15%
1.5488	2.526590538	8.93%
1.553	2.533442088	10.14%
1.5159	0.9761107534	0.16%
1.8224	1.088780022	0.18%
1.6738		

“Please note that this table demonstrates that the crosses of AE:CG **and** the criss-cross ratio DH:BF are both less than 0.2% standard deviation with the Jovian APVO. This is one of the measurements which gives such a ridiculously impossible probability, and even by itself might be considered proof of concept. However, the author will continue further with the experiment.”

Table 64: Side Triangulations for all four oblique sides of the JOPV

<i>Jupiter Triangulars</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>Standev with Avg Triangular</i>	
AB	0.613		
AC	1.1099	1.810603589	11.15%
AD	1.5488	2.526590538	8.93%
AE	1.553	2.533442088	10.14%
		Avg standdev	10.07%
CD	0.6519		
CE	1.0858	1.665592882	0.89%
CF	1.4945	2.292529529	7.62%
CG	1.5159	2.32535665	4.58%
		Avg standdev	4.36%
EF	0.6189		
EG	1.0748	1.736629504	5.92%
EH	1.5911	2.570851511	12.06%
EA	1.553	2.509290677	8.43%
		Avg standdev	8.80%
GH	0.6751		
GA	1.0608	1.571322767	5.77%
GB	1.4082	2.085913198	22.23%
GC	1.5159	2.245445119	10.23%
		Avg standdev	12.74%

“From this we can easily see that node C for Figure 11 is the only one within 5% deviation of the averages of the 3 surveys, and is by far the best angular alignment. To verify if this is correct, the rest of the angular alignments can now be calculated and compared with Jupiter.”

Table 65: Angular Ratios and Standard Deviations, Avg Angles

<i>Angles</i>	<i>(1)</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>(2)</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>(3)</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>Stan_dev_rat</i>	<i>Avg Figures</i>
BAH	159	1.514285714	150	1.388888889	146	1.216666667	14.94%	151.6666667
CBA	105	0.6176470588	108	0.675	120	0.7594936709	7.14%	111
DCB	170	1.588785047	160	1.300813008	158	1.476635514	14.52%	162.6666667
EDC	107	0.6604938272	123	0.8424657534	107	0.6645962733	10.39%	112.3333333
FED	162	1.5	146	1.149606299	161	1.578431373	22.83%	156.3333333
GFE	108	0.6878980892	127	0.8881118881	102	0.6181818182	14.01%	112.3333333
HGF	157	1.440366972	143	1.191666667	165	1.398305085	13.31%	155
GHA	109	0.6855345912	120	0.8	118	0.8082191781	6.86%	115.6666667
Triangle								
EBH	67	1.31372549	62	1.24	64	1.333333333	4.92%	64.33333333
BEH	51	0.8225806452	50	0.7352941176	48	0.7058823529	6.07%	49.66666667
EHB	62	0.9253731343	68	1.096774194	68	1.0625	9.07%	66

Table 66: Averages for Angular Ratios

<i>Avg Ratio of Avg Figures</i>	<i>Avg of Ratios</i>	<i>StanddevAvgs</i>	<i>Avg of Avgs</i>
1.366366366	1.373280423	0.49%	1.369823395
0.6823770492	0.6840469099	0.12%	0.6832119795
1.448071217	1.45541119	0.52%	1.451741203
0.7185501066	0.722518618	0.28%	0.7205343623
1.391691395	1.409345891	1.25%	1.400518643
0.7247311828	0.7313972652	0.47%	0.728064224
1.340057637	1.343446241	0.24%	1.341751939
0.7626373626	0.7645845898	0.14%	0.7636109762
1.295302013	1.295686275	0.03%	1.295494144
0.7525252525	0.7545857052	0.15%	0.7535554789
1.025906736	1.028215776	0.16%	1.027061256

Table 67: Jovian Angles, Rotated, and Standard Deviations of ratios with Avg Table 65,66

<i>Jupiter angles</i>	<i>rotated</i>	<i>Stdev angle</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>Stdev Ratios</i>
-----------------------	----------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------------

147	149	1.89	1.307017544	4.44%
131	114	2.12	0.76	5.43%
149	150	8.96	1.282051282	12.00%
114	117	3.30	0.7452229299	1.75%
150	157	0.47	1.453703704	3.76%
117	108	3.06	0.7346938776	0.47%
157	147	5.66	1.122137405	15.53%
108	131	10.84	0.8791946309	8.17%
73	61.5	2.00	1.268041237	1.94%
46.5	48.5	0.82	0.6928571429	4.29%
60.5	70	2.83	1.138211382	7.86%

Table 68: Standard Deviations for 3 diagrams to Avg, and for Jupiter, angle and %

<i>Stdev (1)</i>	<i>Stdev (2)</i>	<i>Stdev (3)</i>	<i>Avg (2) & (3)</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>Stdev Jupiter angles</i>	<i>Stdev Jupiter vs Newark Ratios</i>
14.66%	5.79%	6.39%	148	1.30	0.71	0.62%
10.07%	6.01%	0.04%	114	0.72	0.00	3.04%
21.69%	1.33%	13.76%	159	1.38	6.36	7.11%
5.99%	6.88%	5.70%	115	0.75	1.41	0.28%
3.27%	21.50%	8.82%	153.5	1.34	2.47	8.00%
3.31%	10.85%	8.24%	114.5	0.74	4.60	0.62%
22.50%	4.92%	19.53%	154	1.29	4.95	12.16%
13.69%	5.60%	5.02%	119	0.80	8.49	5.31%
3.23%	1.98%	4.62%	63	1.29	1.06	1.25%
9.17%	3.00%	0.92%	49	0.72	0.35	1.96%
15.05%	2.93%	5.35%	68	1.08	1.41	4.16%

“Please note that the bold on the left are to show the excellent triangulation for Newark (as opposed to Chillicothe), and the bold on the right are the angle deviations (in degrees) and % deviations of Newark with Jupiter’s APVO! Please note they are all +/- 1 degree and definitely under 5% deviation, which is simply impossible for a randomly created asymmetric octagon earthwork made out of dirt... **unless it were planned with precision.**”

Table 69: High Bank vs other Surveys and vs Jupiter⁴³⁷

3 Figure ratios	Segments	High Bank	Ratios	Standev	Jupiter Ratios	Standev Jupiter
1.015875013	AB	0.6189	0.9153971306	7.10%	1.01322314	6.92%
0.9843578103	BC	0.6761	1.128526123	10.19%	0.9280564504	14.18%
0.9997807374	CD	0.5991	0.9400596265	4.22%	1.011167985	5.03%
0.9834295778	DE	0.6373	0.9743158538	0.64%	1.041686864	4.76%
1.020382294	EF	0.6541	0.9627612599	4.07%	0.9823809524	1.39%
1.017569869	FG	0.6794	1.071946986	3.85%	0.9331950822	9.81%
1.022321993	GH	0.6338	0.9814183958	2.89%	1.048129172	4.72%
0.9610751542	HA	0.6458	1.043464211	5.83%	1.050734095	0.51%
	Triangular	0.6430625	1.002236198	4.85%	1.001071718	5.91%
1.652947467	AC	1.042	1.683632251	2.17%	1.810603589	8.98%
2.40029475	AD	1.525	2.464049119	4.51%	2.526590538	4.42%
2.390110653	AE	1.5185	2.453546615	4.49%	2.533442088	5.65%
	Vert:Horiz	1.361833333	2.200409328	3.72%	2.290212072	6.35%
0.9738008659	CG	1.4289	0.9409944024	2.32%	0.9761107534	2.48%
	Cross					
1.091298398	DH	1.818	1.013806381	5.48%	1.088780022	5.30%
	BF	1.8431				
		1.696666667	0.9774003915	3.90%	1.032445387	3.89%

Table 70: High Bank Constraints and Conformations

	standev segments	segment ratios	Jupiter ratios	standev Jupiter	triang	standev	cross	standev
average	4.28%	1.001524495	1.001071718	3.24%	2.290212072	10.07%	1.032445387	0.17%
+5%	4.50%	1.05160072	1.051125304	3.40%	2.404722675	10.57%	1.084067657	0.18%
-5%	4.07%	0.9514482702	0.951018131	3.08%	2.175701468	9.57%	0.9808231181	0.16%
Within Range?	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	NO
%error	13.22%	0.07%	0.12%	82.60%	3.92%	63.05%	5.33%	2180.12%

⁴³⁷ [30] pp.22-24

Table 71: Combined 4 Surveys vs. Jupiter

<i>Combined with other surveys</i>	<i>standev Jupiter</i>	<i>All surveys</i>	<i>Standev</i>	<i>Triang</i>	<i>Standev</i>	<i>Cross</i>	<i>standev</i>
0.9911923305	1.56%	1.001303328	3.78%	2.158783297	9.29%	1.022618494	0.69%
1.021467749	6.61%	1.051368495	3.97%	2.266722462	9.76%	1.073749419	0.73%
0.9848555043	1.86%	0.9512381621	3.60%	2.050844132	8.83%	0.9714875694	0.66%
0.9819600934	4.22%						
1.006319796	1.69%						
1.030857628	6.91%						
1.014029738	2.41%						
0.9797437896	5.02%						
1.659389286	10.69%						
2.412377395	8.08%						
2.404583211	9.11%						
0.9662969475	0.69%						
1.078940041	0.70%						

Note: Rows are otherwise the same as last two tables.

“The answer is that all of the results become acceptable with Table 70 constraints!” (edited)

Table 72: Angular Deviations and Constraints on High Bank

<i>Angles</i>	<i>Avg of Avgs</i>	<i>Jupiter</i>	<i>Stdev 3 Surveys</i>	<i>High Bank angles</i>	<i>Ratios</i>	<i>Stdev 3 Surveys</i>	<i>Stdev Jupiter</i>	<i>Avg Stdev</i>
BAH	1.369823395	1.307017544	4.44%	164	1.56937799	14.11%	18.55%	16.33%
CBA	0.6832119795	0.76	5.43%	104.5	0.6220238095	4.33%	9.76%	7.04%
DCB	1.451741203	1.282051282	12.00%	168	1.592417062	9.95%	21.95%	15.95%
EDC	0.7205343623	0.7452229299	1.75%	105.5	0.6552795031	4.61%	6.36%	5.49%
FED	1.400518643	1.453703704	3.76%	161	1.548076923	10.43%	6.67%	8.55%
GFE	0.728064224	0.7346938776	0.47%	104	0.619047619	7.71%	8.18%	7.94%
HGF	1.341751939	1.122137405	15.53%	168	1.555555556	15.12%	30.65%	22.88%
GHA	0.7636109762	0.8791946309	8.17%	108	0.6585365854	7.43%	15.60%	11.52%
Triangle	1.05740709	1.035502672	6.44%	135.4	1.102539381	9.21%	14.71%	11.96%
EBH	1.295494144	1.268041237	1.94%	66	1.346938776	3.64%	5.58%	4.61%
BEH	0.7535554789	0.6928571429	4.29%	49	0.7538461538	0.02%	4.31%	2.17%
EHB	1.027061256	1.138211382	7.86%	65	0.9848484848	2.98%	10.84%	6.91%
	1.025370293	1.033036587	4.70%	60	1.028544471	2.21%	6.91%	4.56%

Note: Bold = averages.

Graphs and Figures

Figure 1 - Cultural Phase and Architecture comparison chart (with dates of flourishing)^{438 439}

⁴³⁸ Some dates have been modified based on EPEMC evidence. Others follow standard dating, especially the later periods. The start of a Period does not mean, necessarily, that it was built up. There is no known date to start Atlantean peoples, of all fallen continents, therefore the start date is assumed to be Modern man (language plus brain size).

⁴³⁹ [2] p.8

Figure 2 - Sorted by Size and color-coded^{440 441}

⁴⁴⁰ Red *might be* descended from Atlantean OR Archaic period; Orange is Tepe Period (direct descendent culture of Atlanteans Period); Purple is [likely] from the cataclysmic age, possibly one or another period; Green is confirmed Venus to Mars cataclysm; Blue are, for the most part Historic-Ancient and Megalithic Period, Dynastic times, or the Transition Period of religious movement. As can be seen there is no discernable pattern between age and size, despite usual assertions from catastrophist and diffusionist parties. Several of the red pillars all belong to Baalbek.

⁴⁴¹ [3]. p.56

Figure 3 - The Electrothermal Vine; credit: Careaga⁴⁴²

⁴⁴² [4] p.20

Figure 4 - Comparisons of efficiency between EMF in field, wire, and Birkeland Current form; Careaga
443 444

443

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/e/2PACX-1vTcQhgisF1-tdf2VcAf2uubrvJj7eGpcn8O5NBU7tSGrh6KOnwdoTMFU5a3fB9NOe_bYcEvZTWDTY58/pubhtml?gid=0&single=true

444 [4] p.27

Figure 5 - Investment Categories in Millions of dollars, note: log scale^{445 446}

⁴⁴⁵ For Data sources, see Bibliography [14]

⁴⁴⁶ [5] p.3

Figure 6 - Expenses by percentage⁴⁴⁷

Figure 7 - Media Investments, by % (including Production costs)⁴⁴⁸

⁴⁴⁷ Both: [5] p.4

⁴⁴⁸ Previous statistics included Production in Business expenses

Figure 8 - ESO's "coaxial jets"; credit: Gabuzda et al.⁴⁴⁹

⁴⁴⁹ "The jets of AGN as giant coaxial cables," Gabuzda, Nagle, and Roche, 2017 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1712.08414.pdf>

Figure 9 - Counter-rotating cylinders; Credit: D Scott

“Of the two sets of equations, almost universally the most obvious and distinct change is in the transformation of B field to M field using vector mechanics. In both the “charge force” and “charge field” equations, a long additional vector term utilizing dot products is rendered. In most cases, these will cancel out or be reduced to where they disappear, yielding the original classic Gaussian equation. But when they do not, the vector behavior and the so-called “edge currents”⁴⁵⁰ produced will explain away all sorts of behavior, such as Faraday’s paradox,^{451 452} and Wheeler’s paradox⁴⁵³.

Regarding New Magnetism,⁴⁵⁴ Distinti has been known to say that electricity might be capable of being reduced down to simply magnetism (as it produces these edge currents). However, there has not been a specific mathematical attempt at this as of yet.^{455 456}

“

Figure 10 - BMP Diagram; credit: R Distinti⁴⁵⁷

⁴⁵⁰ <http://www.distinti.com/docs/nm.pdf>

⁴⁵¹

<https://sites.google.com/site/electricuniversegateway/recent-news/pdx107paradox1a1b1cuncoveringthesecretsofmagnetism-distinti>

⁴⁵² <https://youtu.be/hNcR72HAuw0>

⁴⁵³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QReGWNp5fSs>

⁴⁵⁴ http://www.distinti.com/docs/the_secrets_of_qvxb.pdf

⁴⁵⁵ <http://www.distinti.com/docs/ng.pdf>

⁴⁵⁶ [6] pp.37-38

⁴⁵⁷ [6] p.39

Figure 11 - Flow of proposed BMP ether⁴⁵⁸; credit: R Distinti⁴⁵⁹

Figure 12 - force mechanics on BMP ether; credit: R Distinti

⁴⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁵⁹ [6] p.41

Figure 13 - New Magnetism; credit: R Distinti⁴⁶⁰

⁴⁶⁰ Ibid.

Figure 14 - Edge Current model proposed;⁴⁶¹ credit: R Distinti

⁴⁶¹ Ibid. Pg 56-57

Figure 15 - Effective EdC; credit R Distinti

“Although it is premature to release any major details of Robert Distinti’s potentially *groundbreaking* work on vector-matrix algebra, it is worth mentioning here that Distinti has not been satisfied with Heaviside’s treatment of vector algebra⁴⁶² (and any vector calculus thereby derived⁴⁶³) as it makes use of the mathematical anomaly, i (the root of -1, which is undefined).^{464 465}

His new set of Vortrix methods enable not only proper matrix division⁴⁶⁶ and full use of trigonometry and calculus in vectors and matrices of multiple dimensions, he is able to derive [-1] as a matrix that is multiplied (cross produced) with itself.”⁴⁶⁷

⁴⁶² <http://www.math.utah.edu/~gustafso/s2010/HeavisideCoverup2008.pdf>

⁴⁶³ https://www.whitman.edu/mathematics/multivariable/multivariable_16_Vector_Calculus.pdf

⁴⁶⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Imaginary_number

⁴⁶⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eigen_Vectors

⁴⁶⁶ <https://math.stackexchange.com/questions/228229/is-division-of-matrices-possible>

⁴⁶⁷ [6] p.57-58

Figure 16 - Vortrix dealing of i with commutative properties⁴⁶⁸; credit: R Distinti

Figure 17 - Quark Masses turned into scales⁴⁶⁹

⁴⁶⁸ "Vortrix Algebra © Robert Distinti, rev1.2," 2018, R Distinti, all rights reserved.

⁴⁶⁹ http://chemphys.armstrong.edu/secrest/Astro/astro_1.html

Figure 18 - Quark Masses (in GeV)

Figure 19 - Time Dilation according to Relativity Theory

Figure 20 - Length Contraction according to Relativity Theory

The issue that this poses is not with the formulas alone, but with their application. As Stephen Crothers calls it, “Einstein’s Fantastical Clocks.” Much of this is predicated upon a most assuredly - woefully - bad understanding of what math means in the real physical world.^{470 471}

- Time is not a dimension *proper*, it is a measure of the passage of events of change. Change (as a derivative) might be the fourth dimension (or perhaps volume), but time is not a dimension.
- Space is a void of volume, that is filled with other matter, which has mass but isn’t mass itself.
- Mass is electrical charge density (see quanta)
- Energy is a measure of activity level, frequency or vibration rate, or of movement or potential.
- Length Contraction does change one’s apparent perception of electromagnetic **age**, but actual space **does not**: bend, fold, ripple, swirl, tear, blow up, expand, contract, or move in any way. (see Figure 49)

⁴⁷⁰ <https://www.thunderbolts.info/wp/2016/02/19/wal-thornhill-an-examination-of-gravitational-waves-space-news/>

⁴⁷¹ Richard Feynman once explained that the physicist must use the mathematical tool to describe something real in real space. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MZZPF9rXzes>

- Gravity waves are electromagnetic ripples⁴⁷² - EMF is its own medium; the ether is plasma-electricity.
- Gravitons and photons are not particles; they are rates of induction through the plasma and magnetic field "medium."⁴⁷³
- Space-time is not a real Aether and cannot be the UF, hence its failure to combine with much more rigorous Quantum Electrodynamics and Quantum Mechanics in general.

Figure 21 - Bent/Curved Space (this is wrong)⁴⁷⁴

⁴⁷²

<https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/158385/if-gravitational-waves-exist-are-they-technically-just-another-form-of-light-ele>

⁴⁷³ K Wheeler

⁴⁷⁴ There are 3 proofs of the invalidity of this diagram. The first proof is that it relies on the Newtonian concept of weight, despite belonging to Einsteinian mechanics. The second is that down (and up) is arbitrarily assigned, as well as a 2D space-time fabric but it uses 3D objects (mathematically inconsistent). The third proof is that if there was a bowl, all objects would fall towards the center, and either gain energy or have to leave the bowl and decelerate, losing energy and momentum. We find instead that velocity does not decrease, yet bodies remain in orbit or even slowly move away, despite supposed "bending" pushing them towards the center. While it is true that *light* has been shown to bend or refract, this hasn't been shown to be true microlensing (see subsection below). In fact it may mostly be an aging light (so called "tired light") rather than pure relativistic effects. It is certainly true that some concepts of time dilation have been proven with experiments in space, their meanings have been misinterpreted to be about space-time, rather than the changes inherent in electromagnetic signals as they travel back and forth to objects in differential reference frames.

Figure 22 - No lensing Observed; credit: E Dowdye⁴⁷⁵

Figure 23 - Gaussian Spheres in Space; credit: E Dowdye⁴⁷⁶

⁴⁷⁵ <http://www.extinctionshift.com/SignificantFindings01.htm>

⁴⁷⁶ Ibid. Explanations also found [6] pp.74-79

Figure 24 - Electron Density Profile predicts Refraction⁴⁷⁷

Figure 25 - Electron wavelength in terms of voltage and Planck's constant; credit: Hyper-Physics⁴⁷⁸

⁴⁷⁷ "Summary

The electron density profile of solar wind is found to behave very nearly as an inverse square of r , namely as r^{-2} , with electron density profile models ranging from $r^{-2.05}$ to $r^{-2.08}$, and with effects that engulf the outermost planets of the solar system. The bulk of all the Shapiro delay measurements were done using microwave frequencies from 500 MHz to 8.8GHz (with wavelengths from 80cm to 3.5cm). Significant findings of this research reveal that, for all microwave signals propagating in the solar wind atmosphere of the solar system, the waves are subjected to a frequency dependent plasma index of refraction $n(r)$ that exceeds unity, i.e., $n > 1.0000000000$. For optical, IR and UV wavelengths, the plasma index of refraction is practically $n = 1.0000000000$ and these wavelengths are virtually unaffected by the widespread atmosphere of the expanding solar wind described by the electron density profile. As a consequence, the Shapiro delay is only a very good measurement of a frequency dependent transit-time effect and can not be or have anything to do with a space-time effect of General Relativity which is independent of frequency." ~ Dowdye, Ibid.

⁴⁷⁸ [6] p.83

Quantum Mechanics came from laboratory observation and made successful laboratory predictions.

- ❖ “Thomas Young's double-slit experiment demonstrating the wave nature of light. (c. 1805)
- ❖ Henri Becquerel discovers radioactivity. (1896)
- ❖ J. J. Thomson's cathode ray tube experiments (discovers the electron and its negative charge). (1897)
- ❖ The study of black-body radiation between 1850 and 1900, which could not be explained without quantum concepts.
- ❖ The photoelectric effect: Einstein explained this in 1905 (and later received a Nobel prize for it) using the concept of photons, particles of light with quantized energy.
- ❖ Robert Millikan's oil-drop experiment, which showed that electric charge occurs as *quanta*. (whole units) (1909)
- ❖ Ernest Rutherford's gold foil experiment disproved the plum pudding model of the atom which suggested that the mass and positive charge of the atom are almost uniformly distributed. This led to the planetary model of the atom. (1911)
- ❖ James Franck and Gustav Hertz's electron collision experiment shows that energy absorption by mercury atoms is quantized. (1914)
- ❖ Otto Stern and Walther Gerlach conduct the Stern–Gerlach experiment, which demonstrates the quantized nature of particle spin. (1920)
- ❖ Clinton Davisson and Lester Germer demonstrate the wave nature of the electron^[10] in the Electron diffraction experiment. (1927)
- ❖ Clyde L. Cowan and Frederick Reines confirm the existence of the neutrino in the neutrino experiment. (1955)
- ❖ Clauss Jönsson's double-slit experiment with electrons. (1961)” [sic]^{479 480}

Figure 26 - Laser release (series of steps left to right); credit: Wikipedia

⁴⁷⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_quantum_mechanics

⁴⁸⁰ [10] refers to <http://hyperphysics.phy-astr.gsu.edu/hbase/quantum/DavGer2.html>

Figure 27 - Quantum Entanglement; credit: phys.org⁴⁸¹

Figure 28 - Feynman Diagram; credit: Wikipedia

Figure 29 - Evolving Atomic Model; note it hasn't continued to evolve

“Recently, in May of 2018, it was announced that MMS had mapped MHD “eddy” current structures just outside the plasmasphere of the Earth, which has further reinforced the model.

⁴⁸¹ <https://phys.org/news/2015-06-physicists-quantum-coherence-entanglement-sides.html>

Figure 30 - MMS currents in space (open in web view for movement); credit: NASA⁴⁸²

The failings of the model are, however, three-fold.

- The author has demonstrated with a simple experiment⁴⁸³ that there is no such thing as “magnetic reconnection”⁴⁸⁴; See Donald Scott.⁴⁸⁵
- There are no “frozen in fields”⁴⁸⁶ in magnetism, it is always roiling and coiling; Alfven agreed.⁴⁸⁷
- You cannot have magnetism without either electric current, or an electric field.^{488 489}
 - ◆ If you wish to make electricity into shadow-magnetism, it still must be modelled.

The difficulties posed by incorporating QED⁴⁹⁰ with MHD are not to be taken lightly⁴⁹¹, and considering that QED is electrical in one direction, it poses an even stiffer challenge to model plasmas and current sheets⁴⁹² in situ. Even starting one of the most difficult aspects is deciding on and creating a matrix cross product, which produces a field of vectors⁴⁹³ in the orthogonal direction⁴⁹⁴. Then there is the issue posed by Distinti’s Vortex Algebra: is there a 4th dimensional “volume” component Axyz?

“The volume dimension would be defined as dimension xyz and the vector would be written arithmetically as $A = Ax + Ay + Az + Axyz$ ”⁴⁹⁵ ~Distinti

⁴⁸² <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2018/nasa-spacecraft-discovers-new-magnetic-process-in-turbulent-space>

⁴⁸³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZPYEsigZUgU>

⁴⁸⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1711.11284.pdf>

⁴⁸⁵ www.youtube.com/watch?v=ILUmJmDi6uM

⁴⁸⁶ <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1978Ap%26SS..56....3S>

⁴⁸⁷ https://www.nobelprize.org/nobel_prizes/physics/laureates/1970/alfven-lecture.pdf

⁴⁸⁸ Definition of magnetism, see Appendix A and B.IV

⁴⁸⁹ *“Alfvén was the first to predict (in 1963) the large-scale filamentary structure of the universe, a discovery that confounded astrophysicists in 1991 and added to the woes of Big Bang cosmology. Hannes Alfvén has played a central role in the development of several modern fields of physics, including plasma physics, the physics of charged particle beams, and interplanetary and magnetospheric physics.*

Twenty years before the discovery of the Van Allen radiation belt, Alfvén developed the basic tools we use today to describe it. He proposed a mechanism explaining the acceleration of cosmic rays that is now known as the Fermi Mechanism. Alfvén did it before Fermi. And he fought for years to make astronomers aware of the existence and importance of electric fields and currents in space.” ~Electric Sky, by Donald Scott

⁴⁹⁰ <http://fy.chalmers.se/~f3ail/Publications/Jakobsberg.pdf>

⁴⁹¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0370269301009868>

⁴⁹² <https://arxiv.org/abs/1610.01873>

⁴⁹³ The author has created a free, cloud matrix multiplier tool that provides a realistic matrix cross product AND the 4th dimensional term.

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1dwu9AgiNKdtpH5V44W9CHbbRUvLcL2fsyRThfqG4T14/edit?usp=sharing>

⁴⁹⁴ Each entry in the 3-d array is a result of vector cross products. See figure 82

⁴⁹⁵ Ibid. “Vortex Algebra,” pg 16

Figure 31 - AxB: 3D array of vectors and with 4th dimensional Volume component; credit: author

Nevertheless, the discovery of Alfvén waves and the Alfvén length⁴⁹⁶ requires a squaring up of Birkeland currents and Alfvén’s magnetohydrodynamics in plasma physics⁴⁹⁷. The author offers no concrete solutions, but would reiterate that it will likely be necessary to utilize New Electromagnetism in order to eliminate the errors in Maxwell-Heaviside, first, and then proceed from there.”⁴⁹⁸

Figure 32 - Double Helix model of natural EMF; credit: Leedskalnin

“Returning to the mystique of Mr. Leedskalnin’s “levitation” [tuning fork], some have speculated it had to do with his knowledge of the Golden Ratio, also known as Phi.

Figure 33 - Phi

Of course the ratio he left behind was *not* expressed in this way. Rather it was left as a pair of numbers (and no indication as to some form of tabulation, or mental meditation, etc...):

❖ 7129

⁴⁹⁶ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1711.04876.pdf>

⁴⁹⁷ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1707.04182.pdf>

⁴⁹⁸ [6] pp.96-97

❖ 6105195

The division of which yields: 0.0011676940703778

The above equation in figure 85 yields 1.618033988749895”⁴⁹⁹

Figure 33 - Heaviside's EMF wave; credit: Wikicommons

Figure 34 - The electron (early model) collapsing into the Aether; credit: TeslaResearch⁵⁰⁰

⁴⁹⁹ [6] pp.104-105

⁵⁰⁰ Ibid.

Figure 35 - LaPointian Double Bell model

“LaPoint is not of the same eminence as Tesla or Leedskalnin, however he is a practicable man with some laboratory experimentation⁵⁰¹ with basic magnetism, and some patents⁵⁰². Below in Figure 87 is the basic LaPointian “Double bell” magnetic shape⁵⁰³. Compare with Figure 88 and 89. LaPoint is also known for having creating a sort of “monopole”⁵⁰⁴, that is to say, a custom made magnet which favors one side of the poles versus the other.”⁵⁰⁵

Figure 36 - LaPoint plasma/B field experiments; credit: D LaPoint

⁵⁰¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9EPlyiW-xGI>
⁵⁰² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2NogyJ0k8Kw>
⁵⁰³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lpI6ikj1G-s>
⁵⁰⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HSDolf5FY2s>
⁵⁰⁵ [6] pp. 107-108

Figure 37 - Nebulae displaying double bell shape (aka “Bulbs”); credit: NASA

Figure 38 - Structured Hydrogen; credit: everythingselectric.com⁵⁰⁶

⁵⁰⁶ <https://www.everythingselectric.com/elements-electric-universe/>

Figure 39 - He³,⁵⁰⁷ credit: Ethereal Matters⁵⁰⁸

Figure 40 - the Making of Ne²⁰ from C¹²; credit: Ethereal Matters

⁵⁰⁷ Wants to be more stable tetrahedron (and inert) but remains open

⁵⁰⁸ Note that H² (Deuterium) is the model for new neutron: two protons with an inner electron (causing an outer electron)

Figure 41 - Cu⁶³; credit: Ethereal Matters⁵⁰⁹

⁵⁰⁹ Normally is said to have 29 protons. The geometry shows the stable structure but highly electrically active geometry at a “receptor” site

Figure 42 - Electric Gravity; credit: everythingselectric.com⁵¹⁰

Figure 43 - Charged Planets' Shells; credit: everythingselectric.com

⁵¹⁰ <https://www.everythingselectric.com/electric-gravity/>

Figure 44 - Force Evolution in Big Bang Cosmology; credit: HyperPhysics⁵¹¹

⁵¹¹ <http://hyperphysics.phy-astr.gsu.edu/hbase/Astro/unify.html#c1>

“That is, he was worshiped in Thebes. This is clearly the story of the destruction of the female planet, usually called Metis, in her mating with Zeus-Jupiter. Please remember that by this time, Saturn had become a female planet as well in the name of Hera, and was always seen as jealous. Probably on account of the former glory and fall of its power (men losing vital power is seen as womanly). The birth of the planet Venus is from then on attributed to Jupiter. So Dionysus is *also* mixed in as Venus.”

Figure 45 - “Lineage” of Dionysus; clearly a duplication of the Venus origin story⁵¹²

Figure 46 - the Day's Astrology Signs

Figure 47 - The Planets' Signs credit: P. Guinard⁵¹³

⁵¹² [7] p.28

⁵¹³ [8] p.2

Figure 48 - the Zodiacal Signs

Figure 49 - the Sign "Rulers"⁵¹⁴

Figure 50 - Signs with Rulers and dates⁵¹⁵

⁵¹⁴ [8] p.2

⁵¹⁵ [8] p.3

Figure 51 - Zodiacs correlated with common images⁵¹⁶

Figure 52 - Funding for BBC related projects^{517 518}

⁵¹⁶ [8] p.3

⁵¹⁷ <http://bit.ly/2C0DYrp>

⁵¹⁸ [10] p.6

Figure 53 - Taijitu & Bagua (Xiantian arrangement)⁵¹⁹

“But it wasn’t that Dao was not a greater force than Humanity. In three separate documents we see the Chinese conceptualization (which, again, owed to event witnessed in the sky, see Figure 4 at right) is clearly cosmological:

“25

There was something formless and perfect before the universe was born.

It is serene. Empty.

Solitary. Unchanging.

Infinite. Eternally present.

It is the mother of the universe.

*For lack of a better name,
I call it the Tao. It flows through all things,
inside and outside, and returns
to the origin of all things.*

Figure 54 - Birkeland Current Taijitu;
credit: Holoscience.com

The Tao is great.

The universe is great.

Earth is great.

*Man is great.*⁵²⁰

These are the four great powers. Man follows the earth.

Earth follows the universe.

The universe follows the Tao.

The Tao follows only itself.

26

The heavy is the root of the light.

The unmoved is the source of all movement.” ~ Taote Ching (Daode Jing, aka the Laozi)⁵²¹

⁵¹⁹ Literally “Before Heaven,” meaning balanced.

⁵²⁰ Man, and for that matter, King, as Giles translates it, is not really cutting it. Because neither a king nor a man is comparable (not even mankind) to the cosmos; only the Heaven-Man, that is Saturn as the god-man (Shang Di) fits this. So a better translation is clearly, God. That would be the hermaphroditic God: he who “seeds himself” in the sky. Of course by the time of the Warring States, the feminine aspect of the Great God would long be ignored for the masculine. Therefore the symbol for Yang is a solid line (phallus), as is the ‘dangling chad’ stroke on Big (da, 大) (itself a modification of mankind, ren 人), makes the symbol for Great (Tai 太).

⁵²¹ Transl. S Mitchell

“From the above it is clear in these two foundational texts that the cosmological preexists *and* that it determines the model for human behavior. By first observing the cosmos, mankind is able to discern the proper model of behavior. It is therefore clear, that for the Chinese, “as above, so below.”⁵²² This is reflected in the

truth of electromagnetism, which also demonstrates the very self-same properties of Tao. The line that the Universe follows Tao, but Tao follows only itself is especially clear. The Tao is in fact the Unified Force Field that was sought, and was originally observed in the electrical movements of heat, water, and wind. Therefore, the Chinese cosmological roots are not only scientific (being empirical), but internally consistent and consistent with the UAF/PEMS/HEGEME - in short the Electrothermal Vine that is the Universal electric circuit.⁵²³

⁵²⁴

Figure 55 - Marklund Convection: the Dragon⁵²⁵

⁵²² [6].Table 7, pp. 34

⁵²³ ie , the cosmic Dragon. “*MERLIN [says] There are infinite worlds within the infinite coils of the Dragon. In one of them, which I have not traveled, the sword was forged. I only know that the King is returned to us through the instrument of his power.*” <https://www.dailyscript.com/scripts/Excalibur.txt>

⁵²⁴ [12] p.11

⁵²⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=slQRBrmEIXo>

Figure 56 - Speed of Lights vs Intensity; proof that photonic particles would break the law of conservation of energy-mass; Credit: Author⁵²⁶

Figure 57 - “Big Sink” “Astrobleme” (Versailles Crater, KY)⁵²⁷

⁵²⁷ Neither a sink, nor an astrobleme. It is a Thunderbolt crater (the stamp of his foot), and a medium/healthy sized, short lived one, at that (1640 m diameter). In this paper my calculations are for much smaller henge-sized Vajra, around 1000m²

Figure 58 - Carolina Bays vector analysis; Credit: LiDAR⁵²⁸

Figure 59 - Multiple Issues in Carolina Bays theory; Credit: Tatum (Author edited)

- “3 different general vectors (see below for distance issue created), some vastly different.
- The ages of the craters (judged by erosion, which should be similar in the area to each other)
- Crater chaining
- Crater clustering
- Fill in ridges to what should be **empty** craters (so how did the material come up and form a perfect wall)
- Curving crater chains, with inexplicable valleys opposite a gorge.

- Ridiculously flat basins, which is statistically impossible when erosion into shatter cones is considered. Larger cone holes should have some emptiness, and small holes should be almost flat, even the ridges.⁵²⁹

Figure 60 - Continued Analysis with aging shown; Credit: Bowman (Author edited)⁵³⁰

⁵²⁹ [16] p.17

⁵³⁰ [16] p.18

Figure 61 - Middlesboro, KY Crater oblique strike⁵³¹

Figure 62 - Jephtha Knob, KY oblique strike⁵³²

Figure 62 - Big Sink, KY below: no bow shock, no clear vector in or outblast center and out + clear signs of electric arc discharge sputtering, scalloping (albeit eroded), and crater chaining (and vector change)

⁵³¹ All of these are taken with KY From Above LiDAR scans. Author added vector analysis

⁵³² [16] p.19

Figure 63 - Rim Fracturing around Big Sink? Credit: Harris, NASA/ADS⁵³³

⁵³³ <http://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1991Metic..26...47H/0000048.000.html>

Figure 64 - Jeptha Knob Seismic Shattering caused by a true oblique strike; credit: C Jung⁵³⁴

Figure 65 - Side view of Jeptha Knob; Credit: US GEO Survey⁵³⁵

⁵³⁴ http://academic.emporia.edu/aberjame/student/jung1/jeptha_knob.htm

⁵³⁵ [16] p.21

Figure 65 - Hudson Bay Craters, supposedly below 2000m of ice, and obliquely struck; Credit: Roger et al...⁵³⁶

Figure 66 - Chicxulub Crater⁵³⁷, Yucatan; credit: Athenapup.com

“Please compare to a well known and studied oblique strike at the K-T boundary (dinosaur killer). Note the central peak collapse, and the out blasting and explosion away.”⁵³⁸

⁵³⁶ <https://cosmictusk.com/multi-ringed-depressions-beneath-hudson-bay-imitate-impact-craters/>

⁵³⁷

<https://www.news.com.au/technology/science/evolution/drilling-into-dinosaur-ground-zero/news-story/f7309dc0b276bbff6974495a5103944c?sv=857fb417f1dbd461ad8c2aa3829161ef>

⁵³⁸ [16] p.22

Figure 67 - Select Portion of Map of Eastern Cultures⁵³⁹

Figure 68 - Cahokian Pole-Sun Worship Cosmogony; credit: Cahokia Visitor Center, Illinois⁵⁴⁰

⁵³⁹ [16] p.32

⁵⁴⁰ [16] p.34

Figure 69 - Caliper measurements⁵⁴¹ of various Turkey feet shows definite differential⁵⁴²

⁵⁴¹ In fractions of the inch using caliper.

⁵⁴² Next figures [16] pp.41-45

Figure 70 - Eagle Mound; A/D (same convention) = $145/9 = 16.1$ ⁵⁴³

⁵⁴³ 8.8% diff with 7 sample avg

Figure 71 - Secondary Analysis with fine pencil and dual limb vectors on C limb (right)

$A/D = 148/17 = 8.7$; $A/E = 148/7 = 21.14$; Avg 2 vectors ratio (composite A/D) = 14.92^{544}

⁵⁴⁴ 1.6% diff with 7 sample avg; -7.9% diff with Figure 17

Figure 72 - Alligator Analysis attempt 1; $c/d = A/D$ previous Figures = $36/5 = 7.2$ ⁵⁴⁵

⁵⁴⁵ Compare with Figure 18 $A/D = 8.7$, or a -20.1% difference; but their absolute difference (1.5) is much more significant when considered against the avg ~14-15

Figure 73 - Alligator Mound; $A/D = 1.428/.171 = 8.35$ ⁵⁴⁶

⁵⁴⁶ 13.8 % diff with Figure 19; therefore the results can only be conclusive with an on site investigation. However, the difference remains clear and unambiguous. Which is the main point of the exercise. 8.35 is >8000% the ratio to expect with perfectly acceptable symmetry, considering time, erosion, being built by hand, etc...

Figure 74 - Analysis of hexagonal glyph⁵⁴⁷

“The handwriting says,

$$L = 34 \text{ mm}$$

$$k = 30 \text{ mm}$$

$$d_{\text{center}} = 12\text{mm}$$

$$r = 30\text{mm}$$

$$A_{\text{outside}} = 2827.4 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$A_{\text{center}} = 113.1 \text{ mm}^2$$

$$A_{\text{O}} / A_{\text{C}} = 25$$

$$D_{\text{hexagon}} = 65\text{mm} \quad \text{or } 2.402''$$

$$C_{\text{center}} = 13\text{mm} \quad \text{or } 0.549''$$

$$D/C = 5 \quad \text{or } 4.38$$

Below is in inches (caliper)

$$L_1 = 1.683$$

$$D_1 = 0.536$$

$$\Delta_{\text{max}} = 0.069$$

$$\Delta_{\text{mean}} = 0.037$$

$$L_2 = 1.338$$

$$D_2 = 0.605$$

$$\Delta_{\text{min}} = 0.005$$

$$L_3 = 0.692$$

$$D_3 = 0.582$$

$$\Delta_{\text{avg}} = 0.044$$

$$L_4 = 1.221$$

$$D_4 = 0.600$$

$$L_5 = \text{indistinct}$$

$$D_{\text{avg}} = 0.064$$

$$L_6 = 0.969$$

$$\Delta_{\text{max}} = 0.991$$

$$\Delta_{\text{mean}} = 0.554$$

$$\Delta_{\text{hex}} / \Delta_{\text{circle}} = 14.97 \sim 15^{548}$$

$$\Delta_{\text{min}} = 0.117''$$

⁵⁴⁷ [16] pp.54-55

⁵⁴⁸ This shows that the differentials of the hexagon are significantly larger than for the center, meaning it was purposeful

Figure 75 - Amazonia Earthworks that reflect Newark & Chillicothe shapes

Figure 76 - Nazca Circle+Square earthwork effigy (very advanced); calculations using caliper

Figure 77 - Newark Earthworks, including Eagle Mound

Figure 78 - Nazca "Monkey" Earthwork

Figure 79 - Lichtenburg Formation in wood

Figure 80 - in human flesh⁵⁴⁹

Figure 81 - Lightning carved earth, Oklahoma baseball field⁵⁵⁰

Once you see examples of lightning and arc-discharge machining formations, they are quite easy to spot. Their stratification is vastly different from folding, over/underthrust, and other tectonics. Usually, and almost always, they stand out in stark contrast. Subjectively, the regions where they are, such as Devil's tower, Grand Canyon, certain knobs, mounds, earthworks, etc... all have an odd "energetic" sense to them, that is usually attributed to awe or amazement. But, the author maintains, this is a physiological response to an energy-signature, the presence of previous charge deposit or exchange. As for the geological formations, primarily listed by experts Andy Hall⁵⁵¹ and geologist Peter "Mungo" Jupp, as well as engineer Wal Thornhill⁵⁵², they include (but are not limited to):

- ❖ Lichtenburg shapes
- ❖ Lightning rills
- ❖ Scalloping
- ❖ Crater-rim discharges
- ❖ Crater-chains (even which change direction, such as on the moon)
- ❖ Bull's eye (multiple even) cratering irrespective of spherical geometries
- ❖ Sputtering discharges, such as arches and outcroppings
- ❖ Oddly created "Sinks" (Carolina bays, Big Sink, Eye of the Sahara, etc...)
- ❖ Anode/fulgaritic mounds (such as Half-dome, Ayer's Rock, Stone Mtn, and Looking-Glass Rock)
- ❖ Mountain geometries, especially those that fold inwards to a center (Wudangshan, Black Hills)
- ❖ Canyons deeper in center with no outlet (Valles Marineris)⁵⁵³
- ❖ "Shield" Volcanoes which do not have the characteristics of known active volcanoes (Olympus Mons is a prime example)

⁵⁴⁹ [16] p.80

⁵⁵⁰ <https://www.ldsfreedomforum.com/viewtopic.php?t=17155&start=30>

⁵⁵¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM>

⁵⁵² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gJdjZm67bWk>

⁵⁵³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tRV1e5_tB6Y

Figure 82 - Lichtenburg Geo-formations in Knobs Region, Kentucky; credit: Google⁵⁵⁴

⁵⁵⁴ The Knobs region are known for being an odd geological formation where the hills all reach a similar height, ~800-900'

Figure 83 - Barringer Crater⁵⁵⁵; Figure 84 - Newark Earthworks Octagon; credit: Acuah⁵⁵⁶

Figure 85 - Bagua & Taijitu (China)

Figure 86 - Aegishjalmur (Norse)⁵⁵⁷

⁵⁵⁵ Formed by single arc blast, quickly, and impossibly perpendicularly (for an asteroid)

⁵⁵⁶ <https://ahcuah.wordpress.com/2011/11/05/fun-with-lidar/>

⁵⁵⁷ Note the trigram mirroring with the Chinese and Nordic shape: these are 2D representations of the the toroid. The Chinese chose to alternate yin and yang in lines and broken lines, while the Norse alternated the ends and runes.

Figure 86 - Spratt Site Forked Serpent and Great Man (Running Man), Frenchburg, KY; credit: AKHA

558

Figure 87 - Spaas Creek (Skidmore) Rockshelter, Red River Gorge, KY; credit: Tim & Georgie Keith⁵⁵⁹

Figure 88 - Power Scales Based on Table 47; author

⁵⁵⁹ <http://www.kywilderness.com/forum/index.php?topic=7574.msg50863:topicseen#new>

Figure 89 - Vajra to boil Antarctica; author⁵⁶⁰

Figure 90 - Author's idea of Earth-Moon Intercept Path (2D)⁵⁶¹

⁵⁶¹ A 3 dimensional discussion of the proposed swath of destruction is contained in another paper, see [5]

Figure 91 - Birkeland Current Simulations; credit: A Peratt

Figure 92 - Io-Jupiter simulated connection credit: K Lang⁵⁶²

⁵⁶² https://ase.tufts.edu/cosmos/view_picture.asp?id=1174

Figure 93 - Marklund Convection; credit: i-sis.org⁵⁶³

Figure 94 - Stellar Current; credit: Kimura et al...⁵⁶⁴

⁵⁶³ http://www.i-sis.org.uk/Continuous_Creation_from_Electric_Plasma.php

⁵⁶⁴ Ibid. pp. 12-13

Figure 95 - Jeurgens Model; author/R Juergens⁵⁶⁵

⁵⁶⁵ <https://www.kronos-press.com/juergens/1982-electric-solar-energy-juergens.pdf>

Figure 96 - Surge Protection spherical propagation; credit: D Gurnett⁵⁶⁶

⁵⁶⁶ Ibid. pp. 90

Figure 97 - Step voltage/Potential model by Dr. Gurnett⁵⁶⁷

⁵⁶⁷ Ibid. pp. 91

Figure 98 - Step Voltages for Table 51 credit: author⁵⁶⁸

⁵⁶⁸ Source data provided in previous spreadsheet link

Figure 99 - The One God depicted towards the end of the Purple Dawn, Mars in foreground; credit: qaz2008⁵⁶⁹

Note this is certainly too big, as per Ramesses II Stele

⁵⁶⁹ <https://mindbendingtruth.com/2015/06/30/symbols-of-an-alien-sky-part-1/>

“CDN is a concept the author has innovated. A Charge Distributive Network is an active network of circuit nodes, with built in active sensing of mutual voltage and current levels.”⁵⁷⁰

Figure 100 - Charge Distributive Network (version 1); credit: author (circuitlab.com)⁵⁷¹

Figure 101 - Charge as a source of disease; credit: author⁵⁷²

⁵⁷⁰ [18] p.12

⁵⁷¹ <https://www.circuitlab.com/circuit/4x4z74b8v24z/meridian/>

⁵⁷² [11].Appendix B or [18] pp.14

Figure 102 - Five Phases and 12 Channel/6 Division Correspondences; credit: author⁵⁷³

Figure 103 - Complete Solar Flare Eruption, with acceleration/deceleration along electromagnetic field gradients^{574 575}

⁵⁷³ [18] p.21

⁵⁷⁴ <https://news.ucar.edu/132648/emergence-eruption> Image: Courtesy Mark Cheung, Lockheed Martin, and Matthias Rempel, NCAR

⁵⁷⁵ [23] p.5

Figure 104 - Artist rendition of supposed black holes; Corichi/Ruiz⁵⁷⁶

Figure 105 - *“This image shows the inner 30 light-years of a dark matter halo in a cluster of young galaxies. The rotating gaseous disk breaks apart into three clumps that collapse under their own gravity to form supermassive stars. Credits: John Wise, Georgia Institute of Technology”*⁵⁷⁷

“Please note the filamentary structures, and the lack of mention of underlying baryonic structure.”

⁵⁷⁶ [23] p.7 for both images

⁵⁷⁷ <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2019/birth-of-massive-black-holes-in-the-early-universe-revealed>

Figure 106 - This visualization of a general-relativistic collisionless plasma simulation shows the density of positrons near the event horizon of a rotating black hole. Plasma instabilities produce island-like structures in the region of intense electric current. (Credit: Kyle Parfrey et al./Berkeley Lab)

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<https://newscenter.lbl.gov/2019/01/24/how-to-escape-a-black-hole-simulations-provide-new-clues-to-whats-driving-powerful-plasma-jets>

579 [23] p.8

Figure 107 - Plasmoids forming in mysterious Vacuum Tube; credit: E. Dollard⁵⁸⁰

“Nature also has suggested that space is filled with large electrical current sheets⁵⁸¹, of various thicknesses. Could these mysterious objects⁵⁸² be driving disc formation? They are certainly involved at solar⁵⁸³ and “micro-scales”.⁵⁸⁴ They have also been implicated at interstellar medium scales.⁵⁸⁵

Figure 108 - *“The electric field forms vortices propagating past two of the Cluster spacecraft. Since the electrons have much lower mass than the ions and can easily be moved around by the electric field, the electrons create a magnetic field, as shown in the bottom panel. (Fig. from Norgren et*

*al., PRL, 2012)*⁵⁸⁶

In the presence of these large structures, is accretion via gravity necessary or tenable? Something tells the author that the SM will *make it so*, and marry things that may not necessarily even need each other, just to

⁵⁸⁰

⁵⁸¹ <https://phys.org/news/2012-08-thin-current-sheets-space-action.html>

⁵⁸² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1811.08563.pdf>

⁵⁸³

http://articles.adsabs.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/nph-iarticle_query?1988ApJ...326..418S&data_type=PDF_HIGH&whole_paper=YES&type=PRINTER&filetype=.pdf

⁵⁸⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1711.11284.pdf>

⁵⁸⁵ <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1086/303824/pdf>

⁵⁸⁶ Ibid.

avoid admitting they didn't consider electricity important enough, early enough, or listen to Hannes Alfvén.⁵⁸⁷

Figure 109 - Musca Sheet; *“Computer simulation of the Musca cloud, performed at the Metropolis HPC Facility of the Crete Center for Quantum Complexity and Nanotechnology (CCQCN) of the University of Crete. The colour scale denotes density of the gas in the cloud. Black lines threading the cloud almost at right angles to its plane are the magnetic field lines.”*⁵⁸⁸

⁵⁸⁷ [23] p.12

⁵⁸⁸ <https://www.physics.uoc.gr/en/565958200>

Figure 110 - Vajra/Thunderbolts of the Gods, seen in lab and glyph

Figure 111 - Mars depicted as exchanging dust with Earth, creating the Bull of Heaven; D. Talbott⁵⁸⁹

Figure 112 - Kofun and 3 “step-pyramids”; Osaka University⁵⁹⁰

⁵⁸⁹ “Discourses of an Alien Sky,” and “Symbols of an Alien Sky,” are both properties of the Thunderbolts Project™
⁵⁹⁰ [22] p. 12

“On the Ramesses stele (dating according to the mainstream of Egyptology to the 1200s BCE [or as old as 2,494 BCE]), it says the following,

*“The gracious god directed Ramesses, the lord of the upper, and of the lower world, the ‘sun’, the director of truth, approved of the ‘sun’, the lord of **diadems**⁵⁹¹, Ramesses, beloved of Amun⁵⁹², the giver of life, like the ‘sun’ forever, Har-Hat, the giver of life, of stability, and of power. A gift of incense and libations. Har⁵⁹³ - **of the two solar abodes**, of life, of stability, and of power, the giver of victory and of magnanimity; like the ‘sun’, continually.”⁵⁹⁴ (emphasis added, see Figure 1)”⁵⁹⁵*

Figure 113 - Stele of Ramesses left near the Sphinx, with selected highlights

X: 0.4852

Y: 0.393

Note measurements are slightly cropped on stele

⁵⁹¹ Clear indication that the first ‘sun’ is Saturn. This text indicates the transfer of power from the previous lord (Saturn/Osiris) to the son, (Jupiter/Horus). This puts doubts to the stele relating to the pharaoh Ramses, who was probably named after this event, but at the end of the Jovian rule in the sky. Rather, it would point to the era following the Great Flood or less likely, before it. However, the stele could also be a memorial of re-creation and an affirmation of holy authority of the nobility, hearkening back to the original transfer of power from father to son.

⁵⁹² Saturn

⁵⁹³ Probably an early rendition of Horus.

⁵⁹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rfd9pFEbZA0>

⁵⁹⁵ [24] p.2

Figure 114 - Stele of Pharaoh Ramesses II; credit: Wikipedia

X: 0.799

Y: 0.694

Figure 115 - Stele of Chia (scribe of Ramesses II)

X: 0.861
Y: 0.692

Figure 116 - Saturn's North Pole⁵⁹⁶

Figure 117 - counter-rotating bands of Jupiter⁵⁹⁷

⁵⁹⁶ [26] p.2

⁵⁹⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mdl-6uLSIOI>

Figure 118 - Jupiter's Aurora Borealis⁵⁹⁸

Figure 119 - Juno Mission (NASA)⁵⁹⁹

⁵⁹⁸ [26] p.3

⁵⁹⁹ It may interest the reader to note this photo clinched the proof that ancient mound-builders in Ohio saw Jupiter's North Pole.

Figure 120 - multiple arc modes only seen in slow motion of slow motion⁶⁰⁰; credit: Warped Perception

Figure 121 - Phase 1 includes the collections of solar rays, solar 'wind', charge distributed within the asteroid belts (see Figure 9), charge farms [large rectangle], satellite arrays [squares] that distribute with larger bodies [circles].⁶⁰¹

⁶⁰⁰ Green arrows are pointing to moving and fading electric current arcs which are changing from arc mode to glow mode
in arc

⁶⁰¹ [26] p.7

Figure 122 - Phase 2 Area necessitates different kinds of satellite transfer distribution methods

Figure 123 - Paths of useful planetoids

“Note that the vast area covered out past the asteroid belt requires the development of Birkeland Current generators, and the distance is too vast to use laser/maser-arc transfer. Inside the belts (Phase 1 area), it should be possible to use densely arrayed BC laser-arc relays, combined with gold-foil collection, to relay between all sorts of places, back and forth. And outside the Phase 1 area, there are also asteroid clusters from shredded satellites which can act to store a lot of charge till it is collected via swarm or other relay.”

Figure 124 - Solar System distances; credit: britannica.com⁶⁰²

Figure 125 - Planets in size scale comparison; credit: createdheavens.com

⁶⁰² [26] pp.8-11

Figure 126 - Moon and Planetoid Size Comparison Chart; credit: The Planetary Society

Figure 127 - Outer Kuiper Belt orbits, Phase 4 Colonization; Planet Nine involved?⁶⁰³ ⁶⁰⁴

⁶⁰³

<https://www.cam.ac.uk/research/news/mystery-orbits-in-outermost-reaches-of-solar-system-not-caused-by-planet-nine-say-researchers>

⁶⁰⁴ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1809.02571.pdf>

Figure 128 - Proposed Cold Brown Dwarf (Black God/Nemesis); credit: viewzone.com⁶⁰⁵

Figure 129 - Phase 5
Colonization, the nearest stellar
neighbors, with distances given

⁶⁰⁵ <http://www.viewzone.com/browndwarf.html>

Figure 130 - Survey of Devil's Backbone by E.T. Cox⁶⁰⁶, 1874⁶⁰⁷

⁶⁰⁶ https://igws.indiana.edu/CMIS/library/Annual_Report_1875.pdf

⁶⁰⁷ [28] p.2

Figure 131 - Locations of 2nd - 3rd century Roman coin finds⁶⁰⁸; credit: EnchantedLearning.com⁶⁰⁹

Figure 132 - the Coelbren Alphabet⁶¹⁰

⁶⁰⁸ The mainstream claims they come from WW2 veterans. Supposing therefore that western Americans only fought in Japan and Eastern Americans found in Europe? Ridiculous.

⁶⁰⁹ [28] pp.3-4

⁶¹⁰ Our first note should be that all the characters of U-ch-e-ll are plasmaglyph shapes

Figure 133 - Grave Creek Tablet translation; credit: Wilson & Blackett⁶¹¹

Figure 134 - Ren, 人, mankind; credit: Hanziyuan.net⁶¹²

“Of these, only Da has the relevant etymology. Tai is a very new word, as covered in a previous paper. It is descended from Da, with an added phallus. Meanwhile Gao seems to have the image of a house up on a hill. It might refer to the Saturn myth, but it doesn’t have anything in common with Uch.

So what are the origins of Da?”⁶¹³

Figure 135 - Da, Big (One) Man

⁶¹¹ [28] pp. 7-8

⁶¹² <https://hanziyuan.net/#%E4%BA%BA>

⁶¹³ [28] p.9

Figure 136 - Shang, 上, Above; credit Hanziyuan.net⁶¹⁴

⁶¹⁴ [28] p.9

“Compare J23197 to the etymology for Di (God/Lord) and to Tian (Heaven/Above).

Figure 137 - Di (imagine the hands outstretched and note the two lines for the head, as they compare to L17521 in Figure 136.”⁶¹⁵

Figure 138 - Tian 天, Shang Oracle bones; note the double line head, or the toroid of Peratt instability

⁶¹⁵ [28] p.10

“Yet, this is precisely the type of rock art found at the Spratt site⁶¹⁶ (15MF355)⁶¹⁷ near Frenchburg, Kentucky. What is also found, however, are Welsh/Celtic style stone mounds of interlocking rock, rock walls, fortifications⁶¹⁸, “serpent” mounds⁶¹⁹ and effigies⁶²⁰ and plentiful awen scripts. The importance of the latter cannot be underestimated, for although the asymmetric “turkey” glyph is found worldwide⁶²¹, and especially in Kentucky and China (in oracle bones), the tripart name for God is definitely associated with Nordic, Germanic, and Celtic/Pictish cultures. Of these languages, Coelbren is the oldest script, and is mother to others, such as Ogam.⁶²²”

Figure 139 - Shang like scripts at 15MF355 Figure 140 - Coelbren name for God, Pig Pen site⁶²³

Looking at Figure 10, we see from left to right, top to bottom:

- I. Two differential oblate globes
- II. The Heaven/Gream Man glyph
- III. The Bull of Heaven motif
- IV. The cosmic pole and Midnight Sun motif
- V. The ram-head horn motif
- VI. The moving Venus?
- VII. The Great Man motif at adjusted location or angle
- VIII. The x- croes (cross), that is the center of Feng, 𠄎, wind. Probably signifying a catastrophe
- IX. The Bull of Heaven or head glyph, again modified to the right
- X. The L or B rune; possibly upside down.

⁶¹⁶ Officially, a Woodland era site, which would date it from 500 BC - 1100 AD, perfect for the Welsh Indians. Woodland cultures share elements of Allegewi (Adena/Hopewell) cultures, and with Mississippi cultures, and may indicate Welsh/Native cross breeding and cultural share.

<https://npgallery.nps.gov/GetAsset?assetID=54ace52e-4040-4a5a-8b7e-b3c96d8ebae1>

⁶¹⁷ <https://nationalregisterofhistoricplaces.com/ky/menifee/state.html> Possibly as old as 1500 BC, as late as 1000 AD and very well preserved, except the destroyed items discussed.

⁶¹⁸ Arguments for this by the author are contained in a separate work, which will be published online later in the year at <http://uky.academia.edu/ShifuCareaga>

⁶¹⁹ Ie, Great Comet Venus, [15] S Plates ; Dates site to 1600 BC (as per Velikovsky), which matches mainstream dating.

⁶²⁰ Note the bow-shock at the lower left of Figure 13

⁶²¹ [15] Part 2 and Plates

⁶²² As per Wilson & Blackett

⁶²³ Quite clearly over 1,000 years old carving. Photos from 15MF355 courtesy of Lee Pennington, President AKHA.

One question which arises is will we be able to find some of the Saturn Myth motifs in the Coelbren/Khumry?”

Figure 141 & 142 - “Nutting” holes at Spratt site, in “serpent” effigy⁶²⁴

Figure 143 - Spratt Site Plasmaglyphs⁶²⁵

⁶²⁴ “In December 2015 and to a lesser extent in April and May 2016, researchers working on Japan’s Akatsuki mission observed bow shapes in the atmosphere of Venus. This was considered direct evidence of the existence of perhaps the largest stationary gravity waves in the solar system.[83][84][85]... The induced magnetosphere of Venus has a bow shock, magnetosheath, magnetopause and magnetotail with the current sheet.[32][33]

At the subsolar point the bow shock stands 1900 km (0.3 R_v, where R_v is the radius of Venus) above the surface of Venus. This distance was measured in 2007 near the solar activity minimum.[33] Near the solar activity maximum it can be several times further from the planet.[32] The magnetopause is located at the altitude of 300 km.[33] The upper boundary of the ionosphere (ionopause) is near 250 km. Between the magnetopause and ionopause there exists a magnetic barrier—a local enhancement of the magnetic field, which prevents solar plasma from penetrating deeper into the Venusian atmosphere, at least near solar activity minimum. The magnetic field in the barrier reaches up to 40 nT.[33] The magnetotail continues up to ten radii from the planet. It is the most active part of the Venusian magnetosphere. There are reconnection events and particle acceleration in the tail. The energies of electrons and ions in the magnetotail are around 100 eV and 1000 eV respectively.[35] <http://saturniancosmology.org/epi.php>

⁶²⁵ [28] pp.12-13

Figure 144 - Oneself, ↑ Ge; note the dual powers (Saturn and Jupiter), the use of Ren, and the Bull of Heaven

“L23673 is obviously on the money for the awen glyph or t rune. Could it be that Th for “thunder” is derived of this idea of the triple power of God?”⁶²⁶

⁶²⁶ [289] pp.14-15 (for next page)

Figure 145 - the subject of God in Coelbren/Khumric⁶²⁷

⁶²⁷ "Dosparth Edeyrn Davod Aur; or, the Ancient Welsh Grammar," John Williams et al... 1856; one author lived 1530-1606

Figure 146 & 147 - Scratched runes at Spratt Site; note the similarities to Di, 帝 in Figure 138 and below.⁶²⁸

Figure 148 - Etymology for Di

⁶²⁸ [28] p.17

Figure 149 - Shen, 申 in Liushutong⁶²⁹

“Here we are particularly interested in L04623, L04531, 543, and 544.

While other glyphs are certainly poignant for the Saturn Myth discussion, especially regarding the vying of Mars and Venus, what we want to understand is the splitting or separating concept. So what is it that is breaking apart the glyph in only some of these references to the lightning god Shen/spirit?

Perhaps it is the same pulsing power from the above? Or maybe it is an abstraction of yin and yang in reference to Mars (male) and Venus (female). But what does the rune tell us? It also shows two strokes > and < aiming towards one another and split by a vertical rune (I is the Preserver, if we recall). >|< also generates a hexagon, which could indicate the idea of the separation of the solar glyph (a worldwide motif), which would indicate the idea of heaven and earth separating. But, as they are right and left of each other, just as in Shen, then it must be presumed to be opposing and equal powers. This reminds the author of the battle between Raijin and Fujin, as covered in the Sumo Ritual. Two equal, rounded powers facing off, discharging plasma bolts, would generate massive rock chunks that would form like a barrier between the objects.”

Figure 150 - Thunderbolts of the Gods⁶³⁰; D. Talbott & W. Thornhill

⁶²⁹ [28] p.33

⁶³⁰ Calculations examples, in [15] Part 3

Figure 151: Jupiter's North Pole (APVO); credit: NASA/JPL⁶³¹

Figure 152: Newark, OH Earthworks - an astronomic marvel

⁶³¹ [30] pp.3-4

Figure 153 & 154: Orthogonal View of Jupiter's Poles (JPL); Chillicothe Earthworks, credit: Squier-Davis⁶³²

⁶³² "Ancient Monuments in the Mississippi Valley," Squier & Davis, 1848

Figure 155: (1) - Chillicothe, lined⁶³³

⁶³³ [30] pp.8-11

Figure 156: (2) - Newark Survey #1, lined

Figure 157: (3) - Newark Survey #2, lined

Figure 158: Jupiter North Pole, labeled

Figure 159: Segment Ratios for (1), (2), (3) & Jupiter⁶³⁴

Figure 160: Node Testing for all 4 oblique sides of the JOPV vs avg of three surveys.

⁶³⁴ [30] pp. 18-20

Figure 161: Average Standard Deviations throughout the experiment

Figure 162: Angle Measurements for three surveys and Jupiter

Figure 163: Triangular Ratios and the Standard Deviation (in degrees)

Figure 164: High Bank with lines; credit Squier & Davis, and author⁶³⁵

⁶³⁵ [30] p.25

Figure 165: Chillicothe (1) Overlay

Figure 166: High Bank Overlay⁶³⁶

Figure 167: Newark (2) Overlay

Figure 168: Newark (3) Overlay (Best)

⁶³⁶ [30] pp.26-27

Figure 169: Newark (3) Overlay w/ swatch

Figure 170: No swatch; note this is the Squier-Davis Survey

P Plates⁶³⁷

⁶³⁷ [16] pp.150-156

Plate P1 - SAFIRE Phase 1, multiple atmospheres in plasma chambers⁶³⁸

Plate P2 - SAFIRE Phase 1, petroglyph atmosphere comparisons

⁶³⁸ Everythingselectric.com

Plates P3 & P4 - Peratt Formations⁶³⁹

Plate P5 - Yelverton EU Geology, "Dendritic ridges formed via electric fields"⁶⁴⁰

⁶³⁹ <http://eixdelmon.com/peratt-instabilities-plasma-columns-z-pinch/>

⁶⁴⁰ www.everythingselectric.com Suggested review: www.youtube.com/user/Mr2Tuff2 and www.youtube.com/watch?v=VShbfmI8zU

Plate P6 - Arc-blasted and Wind-blasted Earth⁶⁴¹

⁶⁴¹ Andy Hall

Plate P7 - Waveform layered mountains from arc-blasted winds, Utah⁶⁴²

Plate P8 - Valles Marineris (Mars), elevation scans

Plate P9 - Electric Canyon created in lab⁶⁴³

⁶⁴³ Billy Yelverton (Mr2Tuff2)

Plate P10 - Spiral Galaxy⁶⁴⁴

Plate P11 - Electric Field generated dendrites⁶⁴⁵

⁶⁴⁴ www.everythingselectric.com

⁶⁴⁵ Billy Yelverton

Plate P12 - BC in lab, plasma in vacuum looks curvilinear⁶⁴⁶

Plate P13 - Anode Mound formed via arc (simulated Vajra)⁶⁴⁷

⁶⁴⁶ SuspiciousObservers

⁶⁴⁷ Billy Yelverton

Appendix A - Glossary of Terms⁶⁴⁸

Active Galactic Nuclei - An active galactic nucleus (AGN) is a compact region at the center of a galaxy that has a much higher than normal luminosity over at least some portion—and possibly all—of the electromagnetic spectrum, with characteristics indicating that the excess luminosity is not produced by stars.

Aether/Ether - a very rarefied and highly elastic substance formerly believed to permeate all space, including the interstices between the particles of matter, and to be the medium whose vibrations constituted light and other electromagnetic radiation.

Alfvénic Magnetism - In magnetohydrodynamics, the Alfvén's theorem, also known as Alfvén's frozen in theorem, states that in a fluid with infinite electric conductivity, magnetic field lines are frozen into the fluid and have to move along with it.

Amplitude - the maximum extent of a vibration or oscillation, measured from the position of equilibrium.

Angular Momentum - the quantity of rotation of a body, which is the product of its moment of inertia and its angular velocity.

Anode - the positively charged electrode by which the electrons leave a device *or* the negatively charged electrode of a device supplying current such as a primary cell.

Anticyclone - a weather system with high atmospheric pressure at its center, around which air slowly circulates in a clockwise (northern hemisphere) or counterclockwise (southern hemisphere) direction.

Antimatter - “molecules formed by atoms consisting of antiprotons, antineutrons, and positrons. Stable antimatter does not appear to exist in our universe.”

Birkeland Current - A Birkeland current is a set of currents that flow along geomagnetic field lines connecting the Earth's magnetosphere to the Earth's high latitude ionosphere. The strength of the Birkeland currents changes with activity in the magnetosphere (e.g. during substorms).

c - The speed of light in vacuum, commonly denoted *c*, is a universal physical constant important in many areas of physics. Its exact value is 299,792,458 metres per second.

Capacitance - the ability of a system to store an electric charge. The ratio of the change in an electric charge in a system to the corresponding change in its electric potential. The SI unit of capacitance is the farad (symbol: **F**), named after the English physicist Michael Faraday. A 1 farad capacitor, when charged with 1 coulomb of electrical charge, has a potential difference of 1 volt between its plates. symbol: **C**

Cathode - the negatively charged electrode by which electrons enter an electrical device *or* the positively charged electrode of an electrical device, such as a primary cell, that supplies current.

Charge - Electric charge is the physical property of matter that causes it to experience a force when placed in an electromagnetic field. There are two types of electric charges; positive and negative (commonly carried by protons and electrons respectively). Like charges repel and unlike attract. SI unit: Coulomb. symbol: **Q**

Charge Density - the electric charge per unit area of a surface, or per unit volume of a field or body.

Coaxial - having a common axis. (of a cable or line) consisting of two concentric conductors separated by an insulator.

Conductivity

Electrical: the degree to which a specified material conducts electricity, calculated as the ratio of the current density in the material to the electric field that causes the flow of current. It is the reciprocal of the resistivity.

Thermal: the rate at which heat passes through a specified material, expressed as the amount of heat that flows per unit time through a unit area with a temperature gradient of one degree per unit distance.

⁶⁴⁸ Sources: Google and Wikipedia, unless otherwise noted.

Convection - the movement caused within a fluid by the tendency of hotter and therefore less dense material to rise, and colder, denser material to sink under the influence of gravity, which consequently results in transfer of heat.

Coriolis Effect - an effect whereby a mass moving in a rotating system experiences a force (the *Coriolis force*⁶⁴⁹) acting perpendicular to the direction of motion and to the axis of rotation. On the earth, the effect tends to deflect moving objects to the right in the northern hemisphere and to the left in the southern and is important in the formation of cyclonic weather systems.

Counter-rotation/rotating - (of two corresponding or similar moving parts) rotating in opposite directions.

Curvature - the degree to which a curve deviates from a straight line, or a curved surface deviates from a plane.

Cyclone - a system of winds rotating inward to an area of low atmospheric pressure, with a counterclockwise (northern hemisphere) or clockwise (southern hemisphere) circulation; a depression.

Dark Energy - a theoretical hypothetical repulsive force that counteracts gravity and causes the universe to expand at an accelerating rate.

Dark Matter - (in some cosmological theories) non-luminous material that is postulated to exist in space and that could take any of several forms including weakly interacting particles (*cold dark matter*) or high-energy randomly moving particles created soon after the Big Bang (*hot dark matter*).

Diamagnetic - (of a substance or body) tending to become magnetized in a direction at 180° to the applied magnetic field.

Dielectric/Effect - the energy storing capacity of the material (by means of polarization). A common example of a dielectric is the electrically insulating material between the metallic plates of a capacitor.

Diffusion - the intermingling of substances by the natural movement of their particles: "the rate of diffusion of a gas"

Dwarf Star - a star of relatively small size and low luminosity, including the majority of main sequence stars.

e (Euler's Number) - The number e is a famous irrational number, and is one of the most important numbers in mathematics. The first few digits are: 2.7182818; The natural log of e is 1. $\ln(e)=1$

Earthspot - The hypothetical⁶⁵⁰ junction of low pressure zones changing temperatures, with electromagnetic tunnels observed in correlation with sunspot+solar flare activity, or coronal hole activity, depending on charge.

Eigenvector - a vector that when operated on by a given operator gives a scalar multiple of itself.

Electric/current sheet - A current sheet is an electric current that is confined to a surface, rather than being spread through a volume of space.⁶⁵¹

Electrical Circuit - a path in which electrons from a voltage or current source flow. The point where those electrons enter an electrical circuit is called the "source" of electrons. The point where the electrons leave an electrical circuit is called the "return" or "earth ground".

Electrical Tension - Voltage, electric potential difference, electric pressure or electric tension (formally denoted ΔV or ΔU , but more often simply as **V** or **U**, for instance in the context of Ohm's or Kirchhoff's circuit laws; see Appendix B.IV) is the difference in electric potential between two points.

Electric Field - a region around a charged particle or object within which a force would be exerted on other charged particles or objects. The SI unit of electric field strength is **newtons per coulomb** (N/C) or volts per **meter**(V/m). The force experienced by a very small test charge q placed in a field E in a vacuum is given by $E = F/q$, where F is the force experienced. Symbol: **E**

Electrogravity - a research subject based upon the original work of Nikola Tesla, and hypotheses advanced by Thomas T. Brown and Brown's subsequent extensive experimentation and demonstrations of the effect.

⁶⁴⁹ Please note this is not a real force, and this is not a correct theorem, but is included for thoroughness. See Birkeland, Bagashov

⁶⁵⁰ Sf. Careaga, see "Weatherman's Guide to the Sun," B Davidson, 2017

⁶⁵¹ <https://phys.org/news/2012-08-thin-current-sheets-space-action.html>

Electromagnetic Force - (EMF) A fundamental force in nature, the electromagnetic force acts between charged particles and is the combination of all electrical and magnetic forces. The electromagnetic force can be attractive or repulsive.

Electronegativity - a measure of how strongly atoms attract bonding electrons to themselves

Electrotropism - a kind of tropism which results in growth or migration of an organism, usually a cell, in response to an exogenous electric field.

Electroquake - Earthquakes induced by the plasma-electromagnetic sky, especially solar coronal holes.⁶⁵²

Electroweak Force - relating to or denoting electromagnetic and weak interactions regarded as manifestations of the same interaction.

Energy - power derived from the utilization of physical or chemical resources, especially to provide light and heat or to work machines.

Euler's Formula (see right)

Evolutionary Theory - The theory of evolution by natural selection, first formulated in Darwin's book "On the Origin of Species" in 1859, is the process by which organisms change over time as a result of changes in heritable physical or behavioral traits.

Extrapolation - the action of estimating or concluding something by assuming that existing trends will continue or a current method will remain applicable. In mathematics: the extension of a graph, curve, or range of values by inferring unknown values from trends in the known data.

Extrinsic - not part of the essential nature of someone or something; coming or operating from outside.

EZ Water - H_3O_2 is more viscous, more ordered, and more alkaline than regular water (H_2O), and its optical properties are different. The refractive index of EZ water is about 10% higher than ordinary water.⁶⁵³ (see: Structured Water)

Flux - In electromagnetism, electric flux is the measure of flow of the electric field through a given area

Force - strength or energy as an attribute of physical action or movement; something that causes a change in the motion of an object. $F=ma$ (SI unit is **N** for Newtons)

Fractals - a curve or geometric figure, each part of which has the same statistical character as the whole. Fractals are useful in modeling structures (such as eroded coastlines or snowflakes) in which similar patterns recur at progressively smaller scales, and in describing partly random or chaotic phenomena such as crystal growth, fluid turbulence, and galaxy formation.

Frequency - the rate at which a vibration occurs that constitutes a wave, either in a material (as in sound waves), or in an electromagnetic field (as in radio waves and light), usually measured per second.

Friction - the resistance that one surface or object encounters when moving over another.

Gaia Hypothesis - the theory, put forward by James Lovelock, that living matter on the earth collectively defines and regulates the material conditions necessary for the continuance of life. The planet, or rather the biosphere, is thus likened to a vast self-regulating organism.

Galactic Electric Circuit - the electric circuit composed of or pertaining to the galactic scales: clusters, globulars, nebulae, dwarf and galactic superstructures.⁶⁵⁴

Gaussian - being or having the shape of a normal curve or a *normal distribution*.

Gravity - the force that attracts a body toward the center of the earth, or toward any other physical body having mass. For most purposes Newton's laws of gravity apply, with minor modifications to take the general theory of relativity into account. (see figure at right)

⁶⁵² Sf. Careaga

⁶⁵³ www.pollacklab.com

⁶⁵⁴ Sf. Careaga

Gravity Waves - a wave propagated on a liquid surface or in a fluid (Aether) through the effects of gravity.⁶⁵⁵

h (Planck's Constant) - the unvarying ratio of the energy of a quantum of radiation to its frequency and that has an approximate value of 6.626×10^{-34} joule-second.

Heavy Water - water in which the hydrogen in the molecules is partly or wholly replaced by the isotope deuterium [a hydrogen isotope], used especially as a moderator in nuclear reactors.

Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle - The statement in quantum mechanics, formulated by Werner Heisenberg, that it is impossible to measure two properties of a quantum object, such as its position and momentum (or energy and time), simultaneously with infinite precision.

Hysteresis (magnetic) - the dependence of the state of a system on its history.

Ideal Gas - a hypothetical gas whose molecules occupy negligible space and have no interactions, and that consequently obeys the gas laws exactly.

Imaginary Number (i) - An imaginary number is a complex number that can be written as a real number multiplied by the imaginary unit i , which is defined by its property $i^2 = -1$

Inductance - the property of an electric conductor or circuit that causes an electromotive force to be generated by a change in the current flowing. (symbol: **L**; Reduced to base SI units, one henry (**H**) is the equivalent of one kilogram meter squared per second squared per ampere squared ($\text{kg m}^2 \text{s}^{-2} \text{A}^{-2}$))

Inertia - a property of matter by which it continues in its existing state of rest or uniform motion in a straight line, unless that state is changed by an external force.

Instant Petrification - rapid organic mineralization via electrolytic ion diffusion in high energy arc discharge⁶⁵⁶

Intrinsic - belonging naturally; essential.

Intrinsic Redshift - Intrinsic redshift specifically refers to variations in the observed redshift of individual objects (galaxies, quasars ...) that vary from object to object such that two objects at the same distance might have vastly different redshifts.

Ions/Ionized - an atom or molecule with a net electric charge due to the loss or gain of one or more electrons.

Langmuir Probe - a device used to determine the electron temperature, electron density, and electric potential of a plasma. It works by inserting one or more electrodes into a plasma, with a constant or time-varying electric potential between the various electrodes or between them and the surrounding vessel.

Langmuir Waves - Plasma oscillations, also known as Langmuir waves (after Irving Langmuir), are rapid oscillations of the electron density in conducting media such as plasmas or metals in the ultraviolet region. They are parallel in form to *Jeans instability waves*, which are caused by gravitational instabilities in a static medium.

Laplace Transformation - an integral transform named after its discoverer Pierre-Simon Laplace (/ləˈplɑːs/). It takes a function of a real variable t (time) to a function of a complex variable s (frequency). (see right)

Lattice - a regular repeated three-dimensional arrangement of atoms, ions, or molecules in a metal or other crystalline solid.

Lightyear - a unit of astronomical distance equivalent to the distance that light travels in one year, which is 9.4607×10^{12} km (nearly 6 trillion miles).

Liquid Metallic Hydrogen - Metallic hydrogen is a phase of hydrogen in which it behaves like an electrical conductor.

Lorentzian - the set of equations that, in Einstein's special theory of relativity, relate the space and time coordinates of one frame of reference to those of another.

Magnetar - a "neutron" star with an extremely strong magnetic field.

⁶⁵⁵ In Einstein's theory of General Relativity, this fluid medium is space-time. In electromagnetic cosmologies, it is the EMF force field itself.

⁶⁵⁶ Sf. Careaga; see: P. Mupp, "Ancient Destructions."

Magnetic Field - a region around a magnetic material or a moving electric charge within which the force of magnetism acts. SI Unit: Gauss. Symbol: **B**

Magnetic Flux - In electromagnetism, the magnetic flux (often denoted Φ or Φ_B) through a surface is the surface integral of the normal component of the magnetic field **B** passing through that surface. The SI unit of magnetic flux is the weber (**Wb**) (in derived units: volt seconds), and the CGS unit is the maxwell.

Magnetic Reconnection - is a physical process in highly conducting plasmas in which the magnetic topology is rearranged and magnetic energy is converted to kinetic energy, thermal energy, and particle acceleration.

Magnetic Flux Ropes - Magnetic flux ropes are twisted bundles of electrical current and magnetic field which can exist in magnetized plasmas⁶⁵⁷

Magnetosphere - the region surrounding the earth or another astronomical body in which its magnetic field is the predominant effective magnetic field.

Marklund Convection - named after Göran Marklund, is a convection process that takes place in filamentary currents of plasma. It occurs within a plasma with an associated electric field, that causes convection of ions and electrons inward towards a central twisting filamentary axis.

Mass - the property of matter that measures its resistance to acceleration. Roughly, the mass of an object is a measure of the number of atoms in it. The basic unit of measurement for mass is the kilogram (**kg**). (See Newton's laws of motion; compare weight, inertia.)

Membrane - a pliable sheetlike structure acting as a boundary, lining, or partition of various kinds.

Modulation - the process of varying one or more properties of a periodic waveform, called the carrier signal, with a signal that typically contains information to be transmitted.

Momentum - the quantity of motion of a moving body, measured as a product of its mass and velocity. $P=mv$

MOND - a class of theories known as modified gravity, and is an alternative to the hypothesis that the dynamics of galaxies are determined by massive, invisible dark matter halos.

Nebulae - a cloud of gas and dust in outer space, visible in the night sky either as an indistinct bright patch or as a dark silhouette against other luminous matter.

Neutron Star - a [hypothetical] celestial object of very small radius and very high density, composed predominantly of closely packed neutrons.⁶⁵⁸

Nonlinear - In mathematics and physical sciences, a nonlinear system is a system in which the change of the output is not proportional to the change of the input.

Nova/Supernova - a star showing a sudden large increase in brightness and then slowly returning to its original state over a few months.

Ozone Layer - a layer in the earth's stratosphere at an altitude of about 6.2 miles (10 km) containing a high concentration of ozone, which absorbs most of the ultraviolet radiation reaching the earth from the sun.

P-wave - a longitudinal earthquake wave that travels through the interior of the earth and is usually the first conspicuous wave to be recorded by a seismograph. Expand. Also called primary wave.

Penumbra (of the sun) - the less dark outer part of a sunspot, surrounding the dark core.

Period - A Time period (denoted by 'T') is the time needed for one complete cycle of vibration to pass in a given point. As the frequency of a wave increases, the time period of the wave decreases.

Permittivity - the ability of a substance to store electrical energy in an electric field. Symbols: κ , ϵ , ϵ' or ϵ

Pinch - A pinch is the compression of an electrically conducting filament by magnetic forces.

⁶⁵⁷ <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/0741-3335/56/6/064002> ; see: Birkeland Currents

⁶⁵⁸ Without any other mechanism of explanation, gravity is expected to be capable of doing this; however, high rotation rates proposed preclude this possibility.

Phi - The Golden ratio ϕ is a special number (1.6180339887) found by dividing a line into two parts so that the longer part divided by the smaller part is also equal to the whole length divided by the longer part.

Photoelectric Effect - the emission of electrons or other free carriers when light shines on a material.

Electrons emitted in this manner can be called photo electrons. This phenomenon is commonly studied in electronic physics, as well as in fields of chemistry, such as quantum chemistry or electrochemistry.

Photovoltaic Effect - the creation of voltage and electric current in a material upon exposure to light and is a physical and chemical property/phenomenon. The photovoltaic effect is closely related to the photoelectric effect.

Photon - a particle representing a quantum of light or other electromagnetic radiation. A photon carries energy proportional to the radiation frequency but has zero rest mass.

Planck Distance/Length - The Planck length is the scale at which classical ideas about gravity and space-time cease to be valid, and quantum effects dominate. This is the quantum of length, the smallest measurement of length with any meaning. And roughly equal to 1.6×10^{-35} m or about 10^{-20} times the size of a proton.

Plasma - an ionized gas consisting of positive ions and free electrons in proportions resulting in more or less no overall electric charge, typically at low pressures (as in the upper atmosphere and in fluorescent lamps) or at very high temperatures (as in stars and nuclear fusion reactors).

Plasma Sheath (aka Double Layer) - The *Debye sheath* (electrostatic sheath) is a layer in a plasma which has a greater density of positive ions, and hence an overall excess positive charge, that balances an opposite negative charge on the surface of a material with which it is in contact. See: Langmuir, Tonks, Bohm⁶⁵⁹

Platonic Solids - one of five regular solids (a tetrahedron, cube, octahedron, dodecahedron, or icosahedron).

Plumes - A mantle plume is an upwelling of abnormally hot rock within the Earth's mantle. As the heads of mantle plumes can partly melt when they reach shallow depths, they are thought to be the cause of volcanic centers known as hotspots and probably also to have caused flood basalts.

Polarized - restrict the vibrations of (a transverse wave, especially light) wholly or partially to one direction.

Power - the rate of doing work, the amount of energy transferred per unit time. In the International System of Units, the unit of power is the joule per second (**J/s**), known as the watt (**W**) in honour of James Watt, the eighteenth-century developer of the steam engine condenser.

Pulsar - a celestial object that emits regular pulses of radio waves and other electromagnetic radiation at rates of up to sixteen thousand pulses per second.

Quanta - a discrete quantity of energy proportional in magnitude to the frequency of the radiation it represents.

Quarks - any of a number of subatomic particles carrying a fractional electric charge, postulated as building blocks of the hadrons. Quarks have not been directly observed, but theoretical predictions based on their existence have been confirmed experimentally. (See right)

Quasar - a massive and extremely remote celestial object, emitting exceptionally large amounts of energy, and typically having a starlike image in a telescope.

Radiation - the emission of energy as electromagnetic waves or as moving subatomic particles, especially high-energy particles that cause ionization.

Radio Jets - An astrophysical jet is an astronomical phenomenon where outflows of ionised matter are emitted as an extended beam along the axis of rotation. When this greatly accelerated matter in the beam approaches the speed of light, astrophysical jets become *relativistic jets* as they show effects from special relativity (see: Relativity Theory).

⁶⁵⁹ <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/0963-0252/18/1/014004>

Ray Tube - The cathode ray tube (CRT) is a vacuum tube that contains one or more electron guns and a phosphorescent screen, and is used to display images. It modulates, accelerates, and deflects electron beam(s) onto the screen to create the images.

Redshift - the displacement of spectral lines toward longer wavelengths (the red end of the spectrum) in radiation from distant galaxies and celestial objects. This is interpreted as a Doppler shift that is proportional to the velocity of recession and thus to distance.

Relativity Theory - a theory-hypothesis, formulated essentially by Albert Einstein, that all motion must be defined relative to a frame of reference and that space and time are relative, rather than absolute concepts.

Resistivity - a measure of the resisting power of a specified material to the flow of an electric current. $R = V/I$ (see: Ohm's Law, Appendix B.IV.9)

Right-hand Rule - uses the shape the right hand to established the standard orientation of vector quantities normal to a plane, especially when calculating a vector product or the helicity of particle spin. (see right)

Rossby Waves - also known as planetary waves, are a natural phenomenon in the atmosphere and oceans of planets that largely owe their properties to rotation. Rossby waves are a subset of inertial waves. Atmospheric Rossby waves on Earth are giant meanders in high-altitude winds that have a major influence on weather.

Schrödinger's Cat Phenomenon - a cat imagined as being enclosed in a box with a radioactive source and a poison that will be released when the source (unpredictably) emits radiation, the cat being considered (according to quantum mechanics) to be simultaneously both dead and alive until the box is opened and the cat observed.

Schumann Resonances - a set of spectrum peaks in the extremely low frequency (ELF) portion of the Earth's electromagnetic field spectrum. Schumann resonances are global electromagnetic resonances, generated and excited by lightning discharges in the cavity formed by the Earth's surface and the ionosphere.

Solar System Circuit - the electric circuit composed of or pertaining to the solar system scales: the sun, planets, moons, comets, asteroids, and rogue objects, as well as the stellar sheath and boundary region.⁶⁶⁰

Solar Wind - the continuous flow of charged particles from the sun that permeates the solar system.

Space-time - the concepts of time and three-dimensional space regarded as fused in a four-dimensional continuum.

Space-time dilation - the stretching of space-time of a moving object relative to a second stationary observer *or* to differently moving objects in different reference frames.⁶⁶¹ (see right for time-dilation equation of Special Relativity)

Starwater - a multi-episode literature review of water in the universe, where it comes from, why earth has so much water, and the latest discoveries; water made from solar wind interaction with the Ozone Layer.⁶⁶²

String Theory - (aka M Theory) a cosmological theory hypothesis based on the existence of cosmic strings in an 11-dimensional (hypothetical) space-time. See: Supersymmetry

Strong Force - the force that holds particles together in the atomic nucleus and the force that holds quarks together in elementary particles. Note: As the name implies, this is the strongest force known in nature. (see right)

Structured Atom - an atomic theory based upon Platonic solids, electrons, and protons alone; comprising solely of electromagnetic forces (ie; eliminating the strong force)⁶⁶³

⁶⁶⁰ Sf. Careaga

⁶⁶¹ Sf. Careaga; <http://www.emc2-explained.info/Time-Dilation/#.Wvopx0gvzrc>

⁶⁶² <https://www.suspiciousObservers.org/starwater/>

⁶⁶³ <https://etherealmatters.org/sam>

Structured Water - a molecular arrangement of water molecules that exists when water is near hydrophilic surfaces. (see EZ Water)

Sunspot - a spot or patch appearing from time to time on the sun's surface, appearing dark by contrast with its surroundings.

Supersymmetry - a very general type of mathematical symmetry that relates fermions and bosons.

Surface tension - the tension of the surface film of a liquid caused by the attraction of the particles in the surface layer by the bulk of the liquid, which tends to minimize surface area.

Tau - An arc of a circle with the same length as the radius of that circle subtends an angle of 1 radian. The circumference subtends an angle of 2π radians.⁶⁶⁴ Symbol: τ

Terrella - a small magnetised model ball representing the Earth, that is thought to have been invented by the English physician William Gilbert while investigating magnetism, and further developed 300 years later by the Norwegian scientist and explorer Kristian Birkeland.

Thermodynamics - the branch of physical science that deals with the relations between heat and other forms of energy (such as mechanical, electrical, or chemical energy), and, by extension, of the relationships between all forms of energy.

Tropism - the turning of all or part of an organism in a particular direction in response to an external stimulus.

Tufting - (aka solar granules) when the [solar surface (heliopause)] current density is too high for the anode surface to accommodate, a bright secondary plasma forms within the primary plasma.⁶⁶⁵

Unified Field - a type of field theory that allows all that is usually thought of as fundamental forces and elementary particles to be written in terms of a pair of physical and virtual fields.

Vacuum Tube/Crookes Tube - an electron tube containing a near-vacuum that allows the free passage of electric current.

Van Der Waals Forces - weak, short-range electrostatic attractive forces between uncharged molecules, arising from the interaction of permanent or transient electric dipole moments.

Viscosity - the state of being thick, sticky, and semifluid in consistency, due to internal friction or a quantity expressing the magnitude of internal friction, as measured by the force per unit area resisting a flow in which parallel layers unit distance apart have unit speed relative to one another.

Vortex - a mass of whirling fluid or air, especially a whirlpool or whirlwind.

Vortex Algebra - Vortex-matrix Algebra; a subset of linear algebra that postulates the cross product of two vectors is a matrix rather than an orthogonal vector.⁶⁶⁶

Wave-particle Duality - is the concept in quantum mechanics that every particle or quantic entity may be partly described in terms not only of particles, but also of waves. It expresses the inability of the classical concepts "particle" or "wave" to fully describe the behavior of quantum-scale objects.

Waves - a wave is a disturbance that transfers energy through matter or space, with little or no associated mass transport. Electromagnetic waves do not require a medium.⁶⁶⁷

Weak Force - the weak interaction (the weak force or weak nuclear force) is the mechanism of interaction between subatomic particles that causes radioactive decay and thus plays an essential role in nuclear fission.

Work - measure of energy transfer that occurs when an object is moved over a distance by an external force at least part of which is applied in the direction of the displacement.

Z Pinch/ Bennett Pinch - also known as a zeta pinch, is a type of plasma confinement system that uses an electrical current in the plasma to generate a magnetic field that compresses it; see: Pinch.

⁶⁶⁴ <https://tauday.com/>

⁶⁶⁵ <https://www.everythingselectric.com/electric-sun/>

⁶⁶⁶ Sf. Careaga; see "Votrix Algebra," R. Distinity, 2018

⁶⁶⁷ A strong hint that they are the medium.

The Inappropriate Use of Terms

Before continuing further, the author wishes to insert a short comment about the growing inappropriate use of terms to either a) use recycled science without giving credit for *a priori* knowledge (previous research) or b) hide a lack of classical understanding.

It is not merely terming Birkeland Currents as “Magnetic Flux Ropes” which confuses the matter, but is after all utilitarian. It is an entire host of terms that really have completely different meaning, sometimes non-electromagnetic meaning:

1. Solar “Wind”⁶⁶⁸
2. Geomagnetic “Dynamo”⁶⁶⁹
3. Jets
4. Sprites, elves, etc...
5. Magnetic “tunnels”
6. Magnetic “portals”
7. “Gravitational” lens
8. Tidal lock
9. Magneto*hydro*dynamics⁶⁷⁰
10. Hydrogen Burning⁶⁷¹
11. Quantum weirdness
12. Dirty Snowballs

The use of incorrect terminology as regards astronomy⁶⁷² has led us down a path of confusion and in some ways reveals a blatant attempt to distort the facts to continue supporting Newtonian-Einsteinian gravity, rather than plasma-electromagnetism (weak, strong, and gravity included) as the dominant force binding everything all together.

In the following section, the author will quote from Nehemiah Hawkins’ Electrical Guides⁶⁷³, and set some of the record straight on proper views as pertains to:

1. Electromagnetism
2. Energy
3. Force
4. Mass
5. Matter
6. Various technical terms

⁶⁶⁸ Flattery to Chinese *feng-shui* (*wind-water*) notwithstanding, the frequent confusion of hydrodynamical terms or references with electromagnetic behaviors in space extend well beyond the idea of a current. They extend into impossible idea, such as “Wind” in space. This is a problem in cometology, for example, where the idea of a “snowball” (an Earthen phenomenon) literally blinds scientists to the obvious collimating “streams” (not jets!) upon comet surfaces. 5/12 of the terms listed are water or fluid related.

⁶⁶⁹ “a machine for converting mechanical energy into electrical energy; a [DC] generator.” ~Google
This is, as opposed to some churning mass of magma making a magnetosphere (theoretically).

⁶⁷⁰ “magnetohydrodynamics is the study of the effects of a magnetic field (magneto) on the behavior and motion (dynamics) of a fluid (hydro) that is hot enough for electrons to be separated from their host atoms. Such a gas is called a plasma and is often considered to be the fourth state of matter.” [sic] ~NDG Tyson,
<http://www.haydenplanetarium.org/tyson/read/1994/05/01/confused-person%E2%80%99s-guide-to-astronomical-jargon>

⁶⁷¹ Not only is fusion not occurring inside the core of the sun, but the idea of atoms that fuse are “burning” is bogus. Ibid.

⁶⁷² <http://www.skyandtelescope.com/astronomy-terms/>

⁶⁷³ <https://sites.google.com/site/electricuniversegateway/home/hawkin-s-electrical-guides>

7. Work
8. Power
9. Various quantum terms if related

Hawkins' Electrical Guides Definitions

1. "1, Electricity and magnetism are one and the same thing; 2, what is really known about it has come as a discovery and not as an invention. Thus, we say the intrepid explorer discovered the pole, not that he invented it."
2. "Magnets are bodies, either natural or artificial, which have the property of attracting iron, and the power, when freely suspended, of taking a direction toward the poles of the earth."
3. "By means of simple experiments it may be ascertained that the magnet has the following general properties, viz : 1, power of attraction; 2, power of repulsion; 3, power of communicating magnetism to iron or steel; 4, polarity, or the power of taking a direction toward the poles of the earth; 5, power of inclining itself toward a point below the horizon."
4. "magnetism is a department of electrical science which , treats of the properties and effects of the magnet. The same terms are also used to denote the unknown cause of magnetic phenomena, as when we speak of magnetism as excited, imparted, and so on."
5. "Lightning and the Northern Lights are displays of electricity on a grand scale."⁶⁷⁴
6. "the term electricity has been used to denote the unknown cause of electrical phenomena, and broadly the science which treats of electrical phenomena and their causes."
7. "Electricity, whatever it may prove to be, is not matter nor is it energy; it is however a means or medium of transmitting energy."
8. "If electricity is to transmit or convey energy along a wire, this energy must be imparted to the electricity from some external source, that is to say, before electricity can perform any work it must be set in motion, against more or less resistance. This involves that pressure must be applied, and to obtain this pressure, energy must be expended from some external source."
9. "Energy may be defined as the capacity for performing work."
10. "Without the expenditure of energy no useful work can be accomplished."
11. "Although electricity is not energy, electricity under pressure is a form of energy spoken of as electrical energy."
12. "In an expenditure of energy in this form, the electricity acts simply as a transmission agent or medium to transmit the energy imparted to it in causing it to flow."
13. "Usually, mechanical energy is converted into electrical energy, and a dynamo is employed for effecting the transformation."
14. "Potential energy is the capacity for performing work which a body possesses by virtue of its position."
15. "Kinetic energy is the capacity for performing work which a body possesses by virtue of its motion."
16. "Energy cannot be created or destroyed. This is the law known as the conservation of energy.... It teaches further, that energy can be transmitted from one body to another or transformed in its manifestations."
17. "electricity can not be created or destroyed, although its distribution may be altered."
18. "Lippman states that every charge of electricity has an opposite and equal charge somewhere in the universe more or less distributed; that is, the sum of positive charges is always equal to the sum of negative charges."
19. "The true nature of electricity has not yet been discovered. Many think it a quality inherent in nearly all the substances, and accompanied by a peculiar movement or arrangement of the molecules. Some assume that the phenomena of electricity are due to a peculiar state of strain or tension in the ether which is present everywhere, even in and between the atoms of the most solid bodies. If the latter theory be the true one, and if the atmosphere of the earth be surrounded by the same ether, it may be possible to establish these assumptions as facts."
20. "it is positively assured that electricity never manifests itself except when there is some mechanical disturbance in ordinary matter."
21. "light itself is founded on electricity, and that light waves are merely electro-magnetic waves."
22. **"The theory " that; electricity .is related to or identical with, the luminiferous ether," has 'been' accepted -by the most prominent scientists."**

⁶⁷⁴ "Electricity is a term derived from the Greek word for amber, that being the substance in which a property of the agent now denominated electricity was first observed." (Hawkin's Electrical Field Guide, N Hawkins, 1917)

23. "Electricity, it is also conceded, is without weight, and, while it is without doubt, one and the same, it is for convenience sometimes classified according to its motion, as:
1. Static electricity, or electricity at rest;
 2. Current electricity, or electricity in motion;
 3. Magnetism, or electricity in rotation;
 4. Electricity in vibration (radiation)."

Useful Definitions

AGN - Active Galactic Nuclei

BC - Birkeland Current

C-henge - a henge mound where a BC has had a crater-rim discharge, leaving an opening, expanded upon and smoothed by the culture for use as a bridge; see: henge

Cosmic Egg - the Aten; the plasma sheath (debye boundary) of the Cosmic Star-god

EPEMC - Extended Plasma-electromagnetic cosmology

Earthwork - megalithic and geoglyphic sites created using dirt and stone.

Gods - planetoids and celestial bodies, usually anthropomorphised; many cultures duplicated their representations via naming the body and associating it with the god, as if a spirit lived upon the disc or sphere.

HEGEME - Hollow Expanding-Growing Electromagnetic Earth

Henge - a circle, as in a henge-mound

GEC - Galactic Electric Circuit

Glyph - image, usually pertaining to an animal, print, or language, eg. hieroglyph, see: petroglyph

Magnetic Flux Rope (or simply Flux Rope) - a Birkeland Current

Marklund Convection - the process of creating plasmoids by increasing plasma ion flow in a plasma stream

Megafauna - lit: giant animals

PEC - Planetary Electric Circuit

PEMS - Plasma Electromagnetic Sky

Petroglyph - an image engraved upon rocks from the prehistoric era; also: rock art, cave drawings, etc...

Plasma - the primary state of matter, aka the "fourth" state of matter [6]; also: "ionized gas"

SEC - Solar Electric Circuit (see SSC)

Serpent Mound - an earthwork in the general curvilinear shape of a serpent, usually consuming an object; see: S Plates

SSC - Solar System Circuit

SGEC - Supra-galactic Electric Circuit

Thunderbolt (of the Gods) - a BC descending from the ionosphere to connect to ground (Earth)

Vajra - see Thunderbolt

Z-pinch - a zeta or Bennett pinch is a magnetic compression to an invisible center, which may or may not be charged (relative to Earth).

Appendix B - Known Physical Laws of the Universe

I - The Laws of Energy⁶⁷⁵

The laws of energy encompass general statements of known facts about energy, according with studies of the 8 major laws of the Universe: Causality, Evolution/Flux, Relativity, Conservation, Vibration, Rotation, Polarity, and Resonance. To be one of the laws of energy, the axiom must comply with all 8 laws simultaneously (albeit it may appear in different form or applicability), as well as unify the laws, especially their compliments.

1. Energy is abundant; however it prefers wells (sinks) of lowest states of equilibrium.
2. Energy tends to flow along lines of least resistance and highest conductivity; but not always.⁶⁷⁶
3. Energy is produced via differential gradients inducing tension between polarities.
4. Energy is relatively difficult to attain freely.
5. Entropy is balanced with Order, but the ratio between them will affect overall relative appearance of abundance or scarcity of energy.
6. Energy left alone tends to dissipate rather than condensate.
7. Forces bind energy into concentrations and potential reservoirs.
8. Energy may freely transform along prescribed mechanisms and principle controlled means, through forces and fields (force and non-force).
9. Energy conforms to thermodynamic principles in the main, except during reversion or abnormal (forced) circumstances, where it may flow along balancing lines.
10. Energy is neither permanently consumed nor permanently destroyed, it merely transforms, even into quiescent/etheric states which are not directly measured.
11. Energy is.
 - a. The forms of Energy are infinite.
 - b. The time of Energy is eternal.

II - The Laws of Thermodynamics

1. Zeroth law of thermodynamics – If two thermodynamic systems are each in thermal equilibrium with a third, then they are in thermal equilibrium with each other.
2. First law of thermodynamics – Energy can neither be created nor destroyed. It can only change forms. In any process, the total energy of the universe remains the same. For a thermodynamic cycle the net heat supplied to the system equals the net work done by the system.
3. Second law of thermodynamics – The entropy of an isolated system not in equilibrium will tend to increase over time, approaching a maximum value at equilibrium.
4. Third law of thermodynamics – As temperature approaches absolute zero, the entropy of a system approaches a constant minimum.⁶⁷⁷
5. Fourth law of thermodynamics - Intensive properties are independent of the mass of the system; Extensive properties depend on the mass of the system⁶⁷⁸; all equations must balance intensive and extensive properties.⁶⁷⁹

⁶⁷⁵ By Sf. Ramon Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

⁶⁷⁶ One of the most paradoxical facts regarding the Way/Dao of Energy is this “balancing” clause.

⁶⁷⁷ <http://physicsforidiots.com/physics/thermodynamics/>

⁶⁷⁸ P.T. Landsberg, Thermodynamics with Quantum Statistical Illustrations, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1961, p. 142

⁶⁷⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t8Nm9bnWOTs>

6. Planck's Law - The spectral radiance of a body for frequency ν at absolute temperature T is given by

680 681

7. Boyle's Law - The absolute pressure exerted by a given mass of an ideal gas is inversely proportional to the volume it occupies if the temperature and amount of gas remain unchanged within a closed system ⁶⁸²
8. Ideal Gas Law - The ideal gas law is the equation of state for an ideal gas, given by: $PV=nRT$ where
- P is the pressure
 - V is the volume
 - n is the amount of substance of the gas (in moles)
 - R is the gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)
 - T is the absolute temperature ⁶⁸³
9. Joule's Gas Law - The internal energy of a fixed mass of an ideal gas depends only on its temperature (not pressure or volume). ⁶⁸⁴

III - The Laws of Motion and Gravity

1. Newton's First Law - In an inertial frame of reference, an object either remains at rest or continues to move at a constant velocity, unless acted upon by a force.
2. Newton's Second Law - In an inertial reference frame, the vector sum of the forces \mathbf{F} on an object is equal to the mass m of that object multiplied by the acceleration \mathbf{a} of the object: $\mathbf{F} = m\mathbf{a}$. (It is assumed here that the mass m is constant.)
3. Newton's Third Law - When one body exerts a force on a second body, the second body simultaneously exerts a force equal in magnitude and opposite in direction on the first body. ⁶⁸⁵
4. Newton's Law of Gravitation - In non quantum, non-relativistic space,
5. Einstein's General Relativity derivation - In relativistic space, ^{686 687}
6. Euler's First Law - The linear momentum of a body, \mathbf{p} (also denoted \mathbf{G}) is equal to the product of the mass of the body m and the velocity of its center of mass
7. Euler's Second Law - The rate of change of angular momentum \mathbf{L} (sometimes denoted \mathbf{H}) about a point that is fixed in an inertial reference frame (often the mass center of the body), is equal to the sum of the external moments of force (torques) acting on that body \mathbf{M} (also denoted $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ or $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}$) about that point. ⁶⁸⁸

IV - The Laws of Electromagnetism

1. Gauss' Law - The electric flux leaving a volume is proportional to the charge Q inside.
2. Gauss' Law of Magnetism - There are no magnetic monopoles; the total magnetic flux through a closed surface is zero.

⁶⁸⁰ <https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/plancks-law-wavelength-frequency-angle.788629/>

⁶⁸¹ $h =$ Planck's constant, $6.626070040(81)\times 10^{-34} \text{ J}\cdot\text{s}$ or $4.135667662(25)\times 10^{-15} \text{ eV}\cdot\text{s}$; such that $E = hf$

⁶⁸² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Boyle%27s_law

⁶⁸³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ideal_gas#Ideal_gas_law

⁶⁸⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Joule%E2%80%93Thomson_effect#Joule's_second_law

⁶⁸⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Newton%27s_laws_of_motion

⁶⁸⁶ Gravity is not a factor in quantum scales as it is far too weak to be measured and is generally regarded as basically 0.

⁶⁸⁷ Tensors notwithstanding, this law of gravitation will stand until overthrown with something better.

⁶⁸⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Euler%27s_laws_of_motion

3. Faraday's Law of Induction - The voltage induced in a closed loop is proportional to the rate of change of the magnetic flux that the loop encloses.⁶⁸⁹
4. Ampere's Circuit Law - The magnetic field induced around a closed loop is proportional to the electric current plus displacement current (rate of change of electric field) that the loop encloses.⁶⁹⁰
5. Lorentz Force Law - the combination of electric and magnetic force on a point charge due to electromagnetic fields. A particle of charge q moving with velocity \mathbf{v} in the presence of an electric field \mathbf{E} and a magnetic field \mathbf{B} experiences a force:
6. Lenz's Law - the direction of current induced in a conductor by a changing magnetic field due to induction is such that it creates a magnetic field that opposes the change that produced it.⁶⁹¹
7. Kirchhoff's First Law of Currents - At any node (junction) in an electrical circuit, the sum of currents flowing into that node is equal to the sum of currents flowing out of that node or the algebraic sum of currents in a network of conductors meeting at a point is zero.
8. Kirchhoff's Second Law of Voltages - The directed sum of the electrical potential differences (voltage) around any closed network is zero, or The algebraic sum of the products of the resistances of the conductors and the currents in them in a closed loop is equal to the total emf available in that loop.⁶⁹²
9. Ohm's Law - Resistance is defined by the ratio of electrical tension to electrical current; $V = I \cdot R$ ⁶⁹³
10. Ampere's Law with Maxwell's Addition - magnetic fields can be generated in two ways: by electric current and by changing electric fields.⁶⁹⁴
11. Steinmetz's Law - Hysteresis, lagging of the magnetization of a ferromagnetic material, such as iron, behind variations of the magnetizing field.⁶⁹⁵

V - The Laws of Life⁶⁹⁶

1. The life-force (Q_i)⁶⁹⁷ is mysteriously abundant, but conforms otherwise to the above listed laws.
2. Life orders structure and material, and acts contrariwise to Entropy.
3. All objects follow the pattern: conception, birth, growth, steady state/stagnation, decrease, death, decay, conversion, transformation, re-emergence. This is the *Axiom of Becoming*.
4. Life is found in various modes and scales and conforms to no known pre-set ideals.
5. Life's fundamental elements do not conform to predetermined principles but may spontaneously evolve.
6. Life's balancing principles alternate between (relatively) long-term peaceful or uniform periods and (relatively) short-term violent or sudden (even cataclysmic) periods of forced evolution; the so-called "catch up" phenomenon.
7. Life is. It is neither likely nor unlikely, though it may be influenced into more or less likelihood by the availability of resources.

⁶⁸⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Faraday%27s_law_of_induction

⁶⁹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maxwell%27s_equations

⁶⁹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lenz%27s_law

⁶⁹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kirchhoff%27s_circuit_laws

⁶⁹³ V=voltage (volts), I = current (amps), R = resistance (ohms)

⁶⁹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Amp%C3%A8re%27s_circuital_law

⁶⁹⁵ <https://www.britannica.com/science/hysteresis>

⁶⁹⁶ By Sf. Ramon Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

⁶⁹⁷ Q_i seems to be related to, but not equivalent with, Charge (Q) in all manners of behavior.

Table 15 - SI Units in Physics; credit: E Dollard⁶⁹⁸

⁶⁹⁸ <http://www.gestaltreality.com/energy-synthesis/eric-dollard/metric-dimensions-relations-of-the-aether-by-e-p-dollard/>

Appendix C - Catastrophe Grades

- Grade 1 - local catastrophe; eg. flash flood, tornado
- Grade 2 - regional minor disaster, ie an earthquake or blizzard
- Grade 3 - regional major disaster, eg. a hurricane, tunguska event
- Grade 4 - national and international minor disasters, eg. tsunami, VEI 5-6
- Grade 5 - international or global major disaster, eg. megatsunami, VEI 7-8
- Grade 6 - global shifting disaster, eg. Younger Dryas event, 535 AD comet,
- Grade 7 - Earth local disaster, eg. Extinction comet, Shoemaker type event for Earth (or Mars)
- Grade 8 - Life Threatening event, ie a X-20+ or CME "killshot," Superwave, etc...

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